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The electrosensory lateral line lobe in mormyrid fish : a stepping stone to the understanding of the cerebellum ?
(Part 2/2 : the cerebellum)

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The electrosensory lateral line lobe in mormyrid fish : a stepping stone to the understanding of the cerebellum ? (Part 2/2 : the cerebellum)

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Keywords : Decorrelation, adaptive filtering, memory addressing, electrosensory lateral line lobe, mormyrid, unipolar brush cell, cerebellum, granule cells, digitalization, connectivity, basket cells, Purkinje cells, basic algorithm.

ABSTRACT

In the electrosensory lateral line lobe [ELL] of mormyrid fish the granule cells [GrCs] in the eminentia granularis posterior seem to be exclusively devoted to act as ‘pointers’ into the memory bank of parallel fiber [PF] to medium ganglion cell [MGC] synapses where the ‘negative images’ of the correlated component in the electroafferent inputs are stored. Quite a number of simulation studies (if not all ?) in the field embrace this concept.

Given that the cerebellum proper displays very similar cytoarchitecture around its Purkinje cells [PuCs] it would be odd if it would not apply the same memory addressing system too.

Several implementation issues were already discussed in Part 1 in the context of the ELL. They will be expanded on here in the context of the much larger cerebellum with topics on AND-gating, digitalization, connectivity, modality control, input space use.

Next, issues related to the differences in the 'principal cells' (MGCs in the ELL, PuCs in the cerebellum) will be discussed : How is the cerebellum to handle the two 'signal types' DS and GS (*) ? What with the BIE and the TDFS (*) ? How is the role of the broad spikes in the MGCs of the ELL and that of the climbing fibers in the cerebellum to be compared ?

(*) See definitions hereafter.

It will be stressed that ascending fibers have a specific function, quite different from that of the parallel fibers, a view that only some in the field seem to acknowledge. A tentative role for the molecular layer interneurons (especially the basket cells) will be proposed.

Finally, a key question will be addressed : what might be the ‘basic algorithm’ of the cerebellum, if it is not the filtering out of self-inflicted sensory disturbances to which the ELL is devoted ?

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Concepts and abbreviations already defined in Part 1 will be (re)used : DS, GS, AS, A-path, ISU, ILF, BIE, RTL, CWA, UWA, TDFS. A short recap of their definitions :

- DS The ‘signal to be decorrelated’. In the cerebellar context it will become the ‘driving signal’.
- GS The ‘guiding signal(s)’ which are those inputs to the GrCs which – combinatorially used – are intended to fire specific GrCs at specific times (implementing a memory addressing system into the PuC synapse memory bank).
- AS The ‘activating signal’ : the output signal of such a GrC which is to activate a specific PF-PuC synapse at a specific time.
- A-path Activation path : the (mental) image of the sequence of activated PF-PuC synapses (which in reality are spatially scattered).
- ISU ‘Input Space Unit’ : a collection of GrCs which receive a same set of ‘modalities’ as inputs, inputs which act as coordinates that specify which GrCs are to fire (the GrCs being the ‘nodes’ in this ISU).
An A-path is a string of sequentially activated nodes in such an ISU.
- ILF The ‘Input Load Factor’ : a factor to take into account that the AS can differ in strength across GrCs (and hence at the PF-PuC synapses) (the ‘local’ ILF), and to take into account that the amount of activated PF-PuC synapses on a PuC can differ from moment to moment (the ‘global’ ILF). The effect of the variability of AS strength across synapses and of time-varying activated PF volume on the PuC represents a potential problem for the PuC output.
- BIE The ‘Backpropagating Integration Effect’ : the phenomenon that the algebraic summing of all inputs at the soma of the MGC cells in the ELL, the result of which is ‘backpropagated’ by the B-spike to the plasticity sites in the dendrites, resolves the ILF variability problem (for correlated activity) ... in the ELL.
- RTL The ‘Relevant Time Lapse’ : the period of time during which it is important to maintain ‘good quality’ of the A-path (since this quality can deteriorate or become corrupted).
- CWA ‘Correlated Wrong Addressing’ : an A-path corrupting factor due to GrCs in the A-path that fire more than once (or prolonged) during the RTL. Causes can be deficient GS uniqueness or deficient AND-gating at the GrC.
- UWA ‘Uncorrelated Wrong Addressing’ : due to activated PF-PuC synapses that do NOT pertain to the A-path. They are activated by ‘passing through’ traffic of PFs originating in ISUs that have no correlation with the ‘local’ DS. The variability in it is an intruding corrupting signal since it escapes decorrelation.

TDFS The ‘Traffic Density Fluctuating Signal’ : the name given to this UWA-caused corrupting signal. For the ELL it was suggested that the outputting neurons ‘neutralize’ the TDFS by an ‘antiphase annulling technique’.

Part 2 consists of the following sections :

- | | |
|--|---|
| A) AND-gating | G) Patch and PF types |
| B) Digitalization | H) From MGC to PuC |
| C) Connectivity | I) MLIs |
| D) Modality control | J) The basic algorithm |
| E) Input space issues | K) The cerebello-cerebral conversation |
| F) DS and GSs on the scale of the cerebellum | Addendum : 'Random connectivity examined' |

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INTRODUCTION

Since this article builds on its 'prequel' Part 1, I can only advise – for a good understanding - to read Part 1 first [110] [Beunis \(2022a\)](#). Below I cospaste the 'General conclusion' of Part 1.

I chose to focus on the ELL first because I became convinced that the ELL is 'the stepping stone' to understand the cerebellum.

Although some sections in Part 1 elaborate more on what is specific for the ELL, much of what was formulated there is to be considered to be also of relevance for the cerebellum itself. Conversely, much of what is to follow in Part 2 is still also of relevance for the ELL.

You will realize that – almost to the end of this article – I take the premise that the cerebellum does what the ELL does.

As a consequence there is some explaining to do considering the cytoarchitectural differences with the ELL. While it is quite plausible that the cerebellum might be involved in 'filtering out unwanted self-inflicted consequences', it surely is not its main objective. Only in the 'basic algorithm section' I will make the transition and it will appear that decorrelation still stands.

The eye blink reflex [EBR] is believed by many 'to show the way'. I believe it does not, but that it relies on a system that can 'cohabit' perfectly with the cerebellar basic algorithm (cfr [109] [Beunis \(2021b\)](#)). Same for saccades and vestibulo-ocular reflex.

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General conclusion (Part 1)

Abbreviations used in this section :

AS	The activating signal	GrL	Granular layer
ASS	Activating signal strength	GS	Guiding signal
B-spike	Broad spike	ILF-VP	Input load factor variability problem
BIE	The backpropagating integration effect	JLN	Juxtalobar nucleus
CC	The correlated component	MF	Mossy fiber
DS	The signal to be decorrelated	MGC	Medium ganglion cell
EffC	Efferent cell	PF	Parallel fiber
EGp	Eminentia granularis posterior	PriC	Principal cell
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	PuC	Purkinje(-like) cell
EOCD	Electric organ corollary discharge	SS	Synapse strength
FFI	Feedforward inhibition	TDFS	The traffic density fluctuation signal
GoC	Golgi cell	UBC	Unipolar brush cell
GrC	Granule cell	UC	The uncorrelated component

With the GrL of the cerebellum in mind, it is striking to find a GrL in the EGp of the ELL in which GrCs seem to be exclusively devoted to the sequenced activation of PF-MGC synapse populations : they are not involved in the processing of the electrosensory input itself (the DS) which comes in by the basilar MGC dendrites. Obviously, it raises the question to what extent the state of affairs is different in the cerebellum.

The signals which the GrCs in the EGp-GrL receive by MFs are baptized 'guiding signals' (GSs), they are derived from corollary discharge, secondary UBC activation or internal 'body-state' parameters, and they determine the activation sequence by the use of combinatorial input to AND-gating GrCs.

To obtain decorrelation, the memory activating sequence should evolve 'aligned in time' with the DS so that each DS timeslice can be bound to an exclusive MGC synapse set. This way the MGC can 'compute' averages of each DS timeslice

as the DS repetitively occurs. It involves a method (like the use of B-spiking) to integrate the DS in an appropriate plasticity mechanism at the synapses.

The averaging finally results in the storing of a CC image which is the inverse of the CC in the received DS and when apical and basilar output are algebraically summed at the soma, the MGC produces an output signal of which the modulation represents the UC in this electrosensory DS.

The characteristics, the interrelationships and the combinatorial capacities of the GSs were explored, and a lot of 'caveats' were formulated : memory addressing needs to be reliably reproducible, and the average related memory content at each address is to be safeguarded against corruption by the compounding of different timeslice DS values (the 'uniqueness' requirement). All this is also potentially relevant for the cerebellum.

It is indeed a worry if a process that generates 'timing diversity' should prove to trigger the same GrCs more than once during the sequence unwinding in synchrony with the DS : it would be devastating for decorrelation.

The 'synchrony' itself is questioned if it depends on a trigger signal (the EOCD) and ensuing cascaded UBC activity (time-locked) – it is more guaranteed when it can depend on internal reference signals (state-locked), even when UBCs are co-engaged for resolution requirements.

GoCs in the GrL may play an important role in minimizing repeated GrC firing by imposing a high level of inhibition (enforcing strict AND-gating) and by brisk FFI to cut the firing short.

In MGCs, the B-spike is the means by which (basilar) DS info is brought to the apical sites where it is to direct the plasticity process, and it is the soma membrane potential which determines it by its effect on B-spike force and/or burst frequency. It implies the necessity to add 'excitatory lift' to the DS (done by way of the JLN EOCD input) to raise the membrane potential into the range (the limits of which were explored) where the DS can be of influence on the B-spike.

It is stressed that SSs and presynaptic ASSs co-determine MGC output, and that consequently SSs should compensate for ASS differences across GrCs. The summation process at the soma (together with the B-spike backpropagating the result) automatically appears to take care of this compensation (hence it is called the 'backpropagating integration effect' – the BIE) and it does so also for the differences in activated PF volumes across timeslices. A BIE though can only be effective when a bidirectional B-spike associated plasticity rule is in vigour.

However, another potential MGC output corrupting signal is identified that cannot be dealt with by the BIE : it is caused by the presynaptic activations by 'passing-through' traffic in the PF population which is uncorrelated with the DS. It is proposed that this 'traffic density fluctuating signal' (TDFS) is apically 'picked up' by the EffCs (assuming that without a B-spike mechanism they are not dedicated to decorrelation, and that their basilar DS input is 'neutralized'), and that the EffCs annul the antiphase TDFS component in the MGC output by merging their output with it.

It raises the question how the cerebellum itself might tackle the ILF-VP and TDFS phenomena.

The foregoing considerations incite to approach the cerebellum from a somewhat different angle of view. Does it implement decorrelation as does the ELL, or does it apply 'a variation on the theme' ? What to expect from PuCs that have no basilar dendrites ? What to expect from a seemingly homogeneous GrC population that sends up AFs that bifurcate into PFs which cross the PuC dendritic trees ? Cerebellar GrCs have more dendrites than those in the EGp of the ELL : it must be challenging for AND-gating and it also poses connectivity issues ...

All this (and more) is discussed in Part 2.

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Here too, all sections end with a recapitulating conclusion. Literature citations frequently show that an idea is already 'living' in the field. A comparison with the 'perceptron' hypothesis is the topic of a 'Discussion' section at the end.

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METHOD

As for 'Part 1', demo programs were written in Visual Foxpro 9.0 . By no means they are 'simulations', but they serve the purpose to 'render' (and test) the underlying reasoning.

As pc programs they cannot really be run in this article, but screenshots ('stills') can be shown, and 'videolinks' are provided to mp4 files which are a 'recording' of the specific demo runs.

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A) AND-GATING

Abbreviations used in this section :

CWA	Correlated wrong addressing	GrL	Granular layer
EGp	The eminentia granularis posterior in the ELL	ISU	Input space unit
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	MF	Mossy fiber
GS	The signal(s) that guide the activation process	PF	Parallel fiber
GrC	Granule cell	PuC	Purkinje cell

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

Let's assume that one of the functions of the GrL is to operate as a 'memory addressing device', as the EGp in the ELL seems to do. In that function each GrC 'points' to a memory location (the depending PF-PuC synapse), activating this synapse only when all the MF-GrC inputs are active : an AND-gating operation.

Fig. 1

In silico, AND-gates are circuits by themselves (Fig. 1), with thresholding at each input, and the circuit expecting as well as outputting clearly distinguishable 'zeroes or ones'.

The 'bio' GrC however is an 'integrate and fire' neuron, summing variable input signals, and it has but one central thresholding mechanism to control its output.

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The difference between the summing of $n-1$ inputs and the summing of all n inputs shrinks with n increasing, and fluctuations in the input signal strengths, by 'bridging' this difference may lead to 'false positives' (firing with less than n inputs 'on' - a CWA hazard) and 'false negatives' (not firing with all n inputs 'on').

In systems like the ELL, where GrCs on average only have 3 dendrites, a high enough firing threshold (by inhibition) may be sufficient to turn the 'summing of inputs' crudely into an AND-gating mechanism.

[1] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

"The small number of excitatory inputs is consistent with anatomical observations that mormyrid granule cells have, on average, three claw-like dendritic endings and previous physiological observations indicating that granule cells receive other sources of mossy fiber input in addition to corollary discharge, e.g. proprioceptive input from spinocerebellar mossy fibers."

[2] (Chabrol et al. 2015)

"Under physiological conditions, GCs receive Golgi cell-mediated inhibition, 98 % of which is thought to be mediated by tonic activation of GABAARs. Moreover, it is thought that a minimum of 3 active MF inputs are necessary to drive GC firing in the presence of tonic inhibition."

A low incidence of 'failed AND-gating' may be tolerable, but surely this incidence rises sharply when n – the number of GrC dendrites - increases, and then the threshold tuning becomes critical or even outright ineffective.

The GrC has to seek a balance between the number of inputs and the variability of the signals at these inputs if it is to obtain reliable AND-gating : more inputs can be afforded if the signals are more 'standardized'.

4 inputs may already be a very optimistic 'maximum' in the face of the inevitable noise in biological systems, even when input signals are 'formatted' to reduce variability.

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Note that in the transistor AND-gate diagram (Fig. 1) the process of AND-gating in silico is cascaded : the output of the first transistor is an input for the second one, and hence the number of inputs at the transistors is always 2, but the cascade itself can be prolonged to make it an x input AND-gating chip.

Fig. 2

'Cascaded AND-gating' was already suggested (in Part 1) as a possible strategy in vivo to reduce the number of inputs at each stage (see Fig. 2) since some MFs are found to carry 'precombined' signals.

[3] (Huang et al. 2013)

"The proprioceptive pathway appears to be intersected by corollary discharges at multiple stages. Previously, corollary and sensory information has been shown to converge in the first stage of proprioceptive processing - in the precerebellar neurons of the spinal cord (Hongo and Okada, 1967; Hongo et al., 1967; Hantman and Jessell, 2010). The present findings indicate that one synapse further up the proprioceptive pathway - at cerebellar granule cells - this convergence occurs again."

[4] (Ishikawa et al. 2015)

"Some granule cells appear to be unimodal, some have multisensory input delivered by separate mossy fibers, and some have multisensory input delivered by a single mossy fiber."

The precerebellar sites where this precombination occurs should then have to apply AND-gating as well and it would also imply that there is a need for at least one MF-line per different precombination to import the results into the GrL.

Hence the drawback of precombination is that more input lines are needed to represent all the possible (or maybe better, all the relevant) precombinations in the GrL, but it might help to add a dimension to some ISUs. Keeping the number of GrC dendrites low is 'safer' for AND-gating, but the reality in vivo is that GrCs on average have four of them

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The most parsimonious explanation (to get rid of the problem) would be that – in the cerebellum - GrCs with more than 4 dendrites are not used for AND-gating (e.g. unimodal GrCs receiving redundant inputs).

However, might 'surnumerary' inputs on AND-gating GrCs be used in a way that it is not impeding for the AND-gating of the 'basic' inputs ?

I mentioned (see Part 1) that multimodal GrCs can receive 'independent' modalities (the number of which determines the dimensionality of the ISU they belong to), and 'interrelated' modalities (which may add to the 'robustness' of the A-path). More inputs may allow for 'redundancy' (same or interrelated input on more than one dendrite with activity that is always simultaneous) – two inputs 'acting as one'. Their 'combined force' should not 'monopolize' the GrC however, causing it to fire without the support of the non-redundant inputs. It might involve input-specific 'supplementary' measures.

Inputs might be 'mutually exclusive' - never firing together. Take an ISU described as (a/b/c)(d)(e) ('/' indicating mutual exclusivity) where a, b and c might purposefully act as accessory 'switches' to 'enable' a (d)(e) ISU in specific circumstances : it would be a 5-dendrite GrC that fires when 3 inputs are active.

'Active modality control' might exclude some inputs from participating (see later).

GrCs start their lives with more dendrites, and these are 'pruned' during maturation, but what is the final distribution of their numbers ? Does it drop sharply when >4 ? Are >4-dendrite GrCs in a phase of connectivity reorganisation ?

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Let's – in the following section – focus on the 'standardization' (or 'digitalization') of the input signals (the GSs).

CONCLUSION

Proper AND-gating (firing only when all inputs are 'on') is crucial for GrCs when they are supposed to function as pointing devices into a PuC memory bank, and that is not evident for an 'integrate and fire' GrC.

If just 'summing' of inputs is to approximate the requirements for reliable AND-gating, then high thresholds (imposed by high inhibition levels) have to be combined with 'digitized' signal formats, but even then signal variability might quickly put a limit to the number of inputs a GrC can AND-gate reliably. I estimate this limit to be 4, and it raises the question what GrCs do with more inputs than that, IF it are AND-gating GrCs.

The presence of precombined signals in MFs suggests that sometimes a strategy is used to AND-gate in stages, since it allows to have one input less on the GrC. Yet they have on average four of them in the cerebellum.

Several possibilities which might make sense of 'surnumerary' inputs are suggested : redundant inputs (if combined force is well controlled), inputs which are 'mutually exclusive', inputs which are actively excluded from the AND-gating process.

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B) DIGITALIZATION

Abbreviations used in this section :

FFI	Feedforward inhibition	LTD/P	Long term depression/potential
GoC	Golgi cell	MF	Mossy fiber
GrC	Granule cell	PPV	Preferred parameter value
GrL	Granular layer	PuC	Purkinje cell

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

Signal variability being 'the demon' for threshold calibration (causing false negatives and false positives when AND-gating is desired), the signals to GrCs better be kind of 'standardized' to make them more apt for digital processing.

It would help if there were already a clear segregation of 'digital ones (bursts) and zeroes (silences)' at the level of the input signals themselves.

In 'digital mode' an MF should only be active (having maximum firing frequency) at a specific 'preferred parameter value' [PPV] of the modality it represents and in principle the 'source' of the MF could have evolved to take care of that.

Outside the PPV the input better be as silent as possible to reduce unwanted impact on the summing process.

Many MFs have been observed to fire maximally at a PPV in all kinds of modalities.

[5] (Chen et al. 2017)

"Tuned GCs exhibited 'preferred angles' for position and set point, which corresponded to the highest rates of MF input. Individual GC tuning curves remained relatively broad such that progressive deviations from the preferred angle were associated with progressive, but gradual, reductions in EPSC rate. A small number of GCs also exhibited significant tuning to whisking phase."

"Our results demonstrate that GCs are highly selective for distinct kinematic features of whisking. This selectivity is conferred predominantly via increases in MF EPSC rate, which causes predictable membrane potential depolarisations and action potential firing at preferred angles."

[6] (Groh 2001)

"The parameters of many sensory (and some premotor) signals are represented by the pattern of activity among an array of neurons each of which is optimally responsive to a different parameter value. This type of code is commonly referred to as a place code."

"The individual neurons that make up sensory maps respond maximally to different "preferred" values of the sensory parameter being encoded, and their responses decrease if the actual stimulus either exceeds or falls short of that particular favorite parameter value. These non-monotonic response functions dictate the second key feature of sensory maps: the representation of the sensory parameter must be distributed across an array of neurons with different preferred parameter values. The discharge rate of any one neuron is ambiguous - except at the peak of the tuning curve, the same response level corresponds to at least two possible values of the sensory parameter. Thus, only by examining the responses of a population of such receptors is it possible to deduce what the stimulus actually looks, sounds, feels, smells, or tastes like. If these tuned neurons are topographically organized according to their preferred parameter values, a given stimulus will evoke activity at a given site in the population, hence the term place code."

I think however that 'population stochastics' are not helpful for the individual GrC if it is to react as unambiguously as possible to GSs. It better applies a 'high-pass filter' to 'sharpen' its response when MFs have 'broad tuning curves' ('to catch the peak only'). It has been demonstrated that GrCs can be high-pass filters, and downstream - as we will see later - there is a still more potent high-pass filter at work at the PF-PuC synapse.

[7] (Mapelli et al. 2010)

"By using voltage-sensitive dye imaging in rat cerebellar slices (Mapelli et al., 2010), we found that mossy fiber bursts optimally excited the granular layer above ~ 50 Hz and the overlying molecular layer above ~ 100 Hz, thus generating a cascade of high-pass filters."

...

The same 'standardization' should apply to all inputs : the different sources of the inputs might emit signals with different (maximal) spiking rates. For AND-gating based upon summing under high inhibition, the effect of all inputs on the GrC better be 'balanced' lest to see one dominant input 'monopolizing' the GrC.

It means that a 'one' on one input should be equal in (depolarizing) strength as a 'one' on another input to avoid one 'one' to be mistaken for 'two ones' when it comes to reaching threshold and triggering the GrC to fire.

Brisk FFI sets 'a time window' for signal transmission at EVERY input site, such that say a 3-dendrite GrC that would fire when receiving a 1+1+1 input (implying equal strength inputs) will not do so when receiving a 1/2+1/2+2 input (the '1/2' inputs being too (s)low to even start participating in the depolarisation build-up) and that although the sums - without FFI - in both cases equal 3 .

[8] (Mapelli et al. 2014)

"After a mossy fiber bursts, inhibition generated by the feedforward loop reaches granule cells in 4-5ms, thereby limiting the duration of granule cell discharge. Time-windowing allows the granule cell to fire just a few spikes."

[9] (Galliano et al. 2010)

"(iv) Golgi cells determine a time window through which granule cell spikes are allowed to pass in response to mossy fibre bursts. This occurs through feed-forward inhibition, which limits the duration and intensity of granule cell excitation (Kanichay Silver, 2008; D'Angelo De Zeeuw, 2009) ."

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Calibration by LTP at the MF-GrC synapse might be a means to lift all input strengths above a certain threshold to the same level (an LTP saturation level ?), while below this threshold LTD would suppress the signal - kind of a segregation into 'zeroes and ones'.

[10] (Le Guen et al. 2010)

"A second essential process in granular layer control of cerebellar timing is presynaptic plasticity at the mossy fiber to granule cell synapse. Indeed, LTP and LTD at this synapse are supposed to control the first-spike delay of the granule cell response to burst mossy fiber stimulation, driving spikes inside or beyond the time-window."

[11] (Gall et al. 2005)

"We report the plasticity/[Ca²⁺]_i relationship for GrCs, which are typically activated by mf bursts (Chadderton et al., 2004). Mf bursts caused a remarkable [Ca²⁺]_i increase in GrC dendritic terminals through the activation of NMDA receptors, metabotropic glutamate receptors (probably acting through IP₃-sensitive stores), voltage-dependent calcium channels, and Ca²⁺-induced Ca²⁺-release. Although [Ca²⁺]_i increased with the duration of mf bursts, long-term depression was found with a small [Ca²⁺]_i increase (bursts < 250 ms), and long-term potentiation (LTP) was found with a large [Ca²⁺]_i increase (bursts > 250 ms). LTP and [Ca²⁺]_i saturated for bursts > 500 ms and with theta-burst stimulation. Thus, bursting enabled a Ca²⁺-dependent bidirectional Bienenstock-Cooper-Munro-like learning mechanism providing the cellular basis for effective learning of burst patterns at the input stage of the cerebellum."

"The plot shows a BCM-like shape, with no changes at very low [Ca²⁺]_i, LTD for moderate [Ca²⁺]_i, and, after a neutral point, LTP at relatively high [Ca²⁺]_i."

It is kind of a 'flip-flop' mechanism and a 'change of state' would require a clear and sustained change in the strength of the input signal.

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Alternatively, it has been suggested that MFs, if they can be chemically 'marked' to be 'modality specific' (see next section), might possess synapse variants adapted to the signal characteristics of their source.

The same might be true on a population scale if GoCs are modality specific (see next section), in delivering inhibition better matched to the source signal characteristics (e.g. strength) to all glomeruli under their control.

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CONCLUSION

To get an 'integrate-and-fire' GrC to function as a reliable AND-gate (avoiding false positives and negatives), the basic requirement is to maintain a high firing threshold.

Next, the inputs should be 'digitized', by having the sources using discrete input lines to signal different PPVs.

Even then, the input signals better be 'standardized' regarding GrC depolarizing power to minimize the calibration demands on the firing thresholding.

The 'time windowing' mechanism might be a way to ensure that only inputs of equal depolarizing power can join forces to trigger a GrC into firing.

A flip-flop mechanism based on a Ca-threshold (hence signal strength) dependent LTP/LTD might be a way to 'digitize' inputs by segregating stronger and weaker signals into their more contrasting and equalized 'extremes' ('ones' and 'zeroes'). It presupposes an equally 'long-term' constancy of the input strength to set or toggle the state.

Alternative adaptive mechanisms might involve modality specific synapse differences at the MF level and modality specific GoC inhibition.

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AND-gating is demanding

The GrL harbours quite some adaptive mechanisms, and it should incite thinking about interpreting some of these as 'digitalization tactics' to enable the GrL to function as a reliable PuC memory bank addressing device.

Apart from having reliable AND-gating performed upon a number of 'digitized' inputs, these inputs must also carry the right combination of signals to turn a GrC into a 'pointing device', and this brings us to the issue of connectivity.

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C) CONNECTIVITY

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path : a chain of sequentially activated synapses	GrC	Granule cell
CWA	Correlated wrong addressing	GrL	Granular layer
DS	The signal to be decorrelated - later also : the driving signal	ISU	Input space unit
EGp	The eminentia granularis posterior in the ELL	MF	Mossy fiber
EOCD	Electric organ corollary discharge	PPV	Preferred parameter value
GoC	Golgi cell	RTL	The relevant timelapse
		UBC	Unipolar brush cell

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

In the cerebellum GrCs of ‘unimodal’ and ‘multimodal’ type have been identified.

When unimodal they receive redundant inputs of a same modality. In that case GrCs could just be ‘relaying’ a signal, and it has been observed that faithful signal transmission is possible under appropriate conditions. If inhibition is raised (eventually pushing summation into AND-gating) a filtering function emerges (rejecting the non-identical / non-synchronous portions of the inputs which might be introduced by noise) but it is at the cost of some truncation of the signal.

[12] (Dean et al. 2009)

"The initial results of these recordings do not support the idea that the granule layer performs complex signal decomposition. In some studies, granule cells seemed to receive functionally equivalent MF inputs on all four dendrites, indicating that they might function as coincidence detectors with a pronounced noise-filtering capability accompanied by simple linear integration for suprathreshold synaptic input."

[13] (Huang et al. 2013)

"For example, a granule cell receiving all synaptic inputs from the same mossy fiber source (i.e., 'unimodal') may serve to filter noise by requiring the summation of inputs in order to fire action potentials (Jörntell and Ekerot, 2006; Ekerot and Jörntell, 2008; Bengtsson and Jörntell, 2009) ."

When multimodal, more than one modality converges onto a single GrC, requiring MFs carrying these different modalities to 'overlap and interdigitate' intensively.

[13] (Huang et al. 2013)

"Strong viral-reporter expression and high-resolution, large-area confocal microscopy revealed many areas of the cerebellum where ECN and BPN axons co-terminate. Such areas include the vermis, lateral vermis, simple lobule, paraflocculus, Crus1, Crus2, paramedian lobule, and copula of the pyramis. Within these areas, ECN and BPN axons terminate within very close proximity (<50 μm), well within the length of the dendritic arbors of granule cells. Therefore, various cerebellar microcircuits potentially process both proprioceptive and pontine information."

Addressing a specific node in a more-dimensional ISU not only requires a multimodal approach, but also that a GrC should connect to ALL the ‘independent’ inputs that define the ISU. If some of these inputs are lacking it will cause GrCs to fire more than once during the RTL (causing CWAs). Mindful of the 'tail wagging' mormyrid (see Part 1) – it would create a situation in which a higher-dimensional ISU finds its specificity spoiled by the presence of its lower-dimensional subcombinations :

[14] (Sawtell 2010)

"In short, PF inputs that represent either body position or motor command timing (proprioceptive and EOCD PFs) will lead to plastic changes at a specific position but at all times or at a specific time but at all positions. Clearly, a simple addition of such changes will not lead to plastic changes restricted to both position and time. Restricting plastic changes to certain positions and times requires PF inputs with activity confined to certain positions and time with respect to the EOD motor command (multimodal PFs) . Hence, the critical step is a nonlinearity in the response to position and timing signals such that only the conjunction of the two evokes a response. As shown here, precisely such an operation occurs in individual GCs that fire only at restricted body positions and times relative to the EOD motor command."

...

I found it intriguing that the mormyrid performs so well while displaying so much connectivity randomness in its GrL (EGp) and found it still more intriguing that simulations 'implementing' random connectivity can nonetheless produce good results.

[15] (Solinas et al. 2010)

"Previous models [originally the theoretical models of Marr (1969), Albus (1971), Tyrrell and Willshaw (1992), Dean et al. (2010) but also the computational model of Maex and De Schutter (1998), Medina and Mauk (2000)] were based on the statistical properties of the granular layer connectivity."

I decided to put this ‘randomness puzzle’ to a test – using computer programming to do it.

To my surprise I had to conclude that ‘random connectivity’ performs relatively better than I ‘intuitively’ expected, though only on the conditions that there is a ‘mapping’ of PPVs and that the resolution of the timeslicing can cope with the frequencies in the DS.

It led me also to the insight that 'surnumerary dendrites' (the GrC having more dendrites than necessary to be connected to the available set of independent modalities) boost the chances of a GrC to gather a more complete set (logically so in retrospect) and that it might be a cardinal reason for their presence. I refer for this analysis to the addendum at the end of this article. I cannot be sure if the 'testing concept' or the method was right, I leave it to the critical scrutiny of the interested reader.

On final consideration however I judge the results to be not good enough when =>3D ISUs come into play, and anyway I strongly doubt that 'nature' would leave it altogether to 'chance' and would not have evolved ways to 'pimp' or control the connectivity in the GrL, certainly in the cerebellum : the whole brain is a miracle of it. Let's assess it.

...

Almost each MF terminal ends (as a rosette) in a specialized structure : the glomerulus, and it is established that each glomerulus contains ONE MF terminal, that 50-odd GrCs each send ONE dendrite into a glomerulus , and that hence each GrC-dendrite claw enters a different glomerulus.

[16] (Arenz et al. 2009)

"Within the glomerulus, one MF terminal synapses onto the dendrites of about 50 granule cells, as well as onto the dendrites of Golgi cells. In addition, Golgi cell axons form inhibitory synaptic contacts onto granule cell dendrites. The glomerulus as a whole is encapsulated in a glial sheath."

[17] (Vittori et al. 2009)

"Quantitative analysis assessed that the presynaptic terminal is contacted in average by 30-50 GC dendrites in the rat (Palkovits et al., 1972; Jakab and Hamori, 1988), each of them coming from separate GCs."

This 'different glomerulus' must also be from a different MF, since :

[18] (Palkovits et al., 1972)

"The distance between rosettes on the average mossy fiber is more than twice the average distance between glomeruli or the average length of granule cell dendrites."

Next, it also seems established that each glomerulus is entered by no more than ONE GoC axon, and that this specific GoC apparently CANNOT serve any of the other glomeruli contacting the 50-odd GrCs that send a dendrite into this particular glomerulus.

[19] (D'Angelo et al. 2013)

"In theory , a single Golgi cell should not innervate a granule cell more than once (and therefore should not innervate other glomeruli within reach of the dendrites of proximal granule cells) and each glomerulus should be innervated by a single Golgi cell." (My underscore)

"Golgi cell connection rules are more complex. It can be assumed that only one Golgi cell axon enters a glomerulus, forming inhibitory synapses on all the afferent granule cell dendrites, and that a Golgi cell axon entering a glomerulus cannot access the neighboring glomeruli if they share granule cells with the first one. This should prevent a granule cell from being inhibited twice by the same Golgi cell (see Solinas et al., 2010)."

This is quite a remarkable restriction ("in theory" : nowhere did I find the underpinning reason) but a large scale simulation of the GrL incorporates it (even when referring to Mapelli 2010 stating that 'experimentally' this might not hold).

[14] (Solinas et al. 2010)

"(a) The GrC dendrites could not reach glomeruli farther than 40 μm (mean dendritic length 13.6 μm).

(b) A single GrC was not allowed to project more than one dendrite inside the same glomerulus.

(c) Only one GoC axon was allowed to enter a glomerulus forming inhibitory synapses on all the afferent GrC dendrites.

(d) A GoC axon entering into one glomerulus was prevented from accessing the neighboring glomeruli sharing GrCs with the first glomerulus. This prevented a GrC from being inhibited twice through the same GoC, a case that does not seem to hold experimentally (see Mapelli et al., 2010). (My underscore)

(e) Each GoC was allowed to access at most 40 glomeruli resulting in a maximum of ~2000 GrCs inhibited by the same GoC.

(f) GoCs received excitation from 50 glomeruli and 100 GrCs through parallel fibers (pfs) randomly selected within the network."

Accepting such a restriction each GrC is inhibited only ONCE by the same GoC i.e. through only ONE of the GrCs dendrites in the glomerulus and inside it the GoC terminals inhibit a majority (60% or maybe all) of the local GrC dendrites.

[15] (Solinas et al. 2010)

"Secondly, since glomeruli receive about 50 dendrites from as many different GrCs, the additional issue is whether a GoC innervates all the GrCs impinging on the same glomerulus. Even minimal stimulation (i.e. one that activates a single synaptic contact) can elicit a direct and an indirect spillover-mediated component in GrC IPSCs (Mapelli et al., 2010). Since spillover is a sign of release on neighboring synapses in the glomerulus (Rossi and Hamann, 1998), a GoC axon should inhibit numerous (if not all) GrC dendrites in the same glomerulus."

[20] (Holtzman et al. 2011)

"It is unlikely that all granule cells will be equally affected on a short timescale, since ~60% receive direct synaptic input from Golgi cells (Jakab & Hamori, 1988), whilst the remainder may 'sense' increases in glomerular GABA using 'slow' spillover mechanisms (Crowley et al. 2009)."

[19] (D'Angelo et al. 2013)

"Given that glomeruli receive an average of 53 dendrites (an estimate obtained from rat cerebellum : Jakab and Hamori, 1988) from as many different granule cells, another issue is whether a Golgicell innervates all the granule cells impinging on the same glomerulus. Even a minimal stimulation (i.e. that activates a single synaptic contact) can elicit a direct and an indirect spillover-mediated component in granule cell IPSCs (Mapelli et al. , 2010). Since spillover is a sign of release on neighboring synapses in the glomerulus (Rossi and Hamann, 1998) , this indicates that a Golgicell axon forms more than one synapse inside a glomerulus and inhibits numerous (if not all) granule cell dendrites in that glomerulus."

[21] (Crowley et al. 2009)

"Ultrastructural studies show that within a glomerulus the number and size of connections made by Golgi cell axons to granule cells is highly variable and 40% of granule cells are not directly contacted by a Golgi cell axon (Jakab and Hamori, 1988) ."

"Electron microscopic reconstructions indicate that dendrites from many granule cells are contained within a single glomerulus, but Golgi cell axons make direct contacts onto only 60% of them (Jakab and Hamori, 1988)."

3 to 5 independent GoCs seem to inhibit a GrC, each GoC by way of a different GrC dendrite.

[19] (D'Angelo et al. 2013)

"Ultrastructural measurements have revealed that each granule cell receives, on average, three Golgi cell inhibitory synapses on as many different dendrites (Hamori and Somogyi, 1983; Jakab and Hamori, 1988)."

"Multiple IPSCs in a granule cell can be recruited by increasing the stimulation intensity (Mapelli et al. , 2010) , which is consistent with 3-5 independent Golgi cells connected. Indeed, the frequency of spontaneous IPSCs, which are synaptic events determined by intrinsic activity in Golgi cells, exceeds the pacemaker frequency shown by single Golgi cells."

[15] (Solinas et al. 2010)

"First, ultrastructural measurements have revealed that each GrC receives on average three GoC inhibitory synapses (Hamori and Somogyi, 1983), but has left open the problem on whether these synapses originated from the same or from different GoCs. Typically, GrC IPSCs can be recruited by raising stimulation intensity (Mapelli et al., 2010), suggesting that three to four independent GoCs are indeed connected."

...

Apparently ... once a GoC contacts a glomerulus it is as if all 50 odd participating GrCs transmit a (chemical) signal through their dendrites to all the other glomeruli to close the door for this particular GoC.

A chemical signal however cannot be that specific : it cannot distinguish between what is identical, and hence, if this 'particular' GoC is refused to contact the GrC twice, then it must be that ALL other GoCs are prevented to contact these GrCs (it reminds of the oocyte permitting entrance to only one spermatozoid, closing the door for all the others).

Since other GoCs clearly DO contact these GrCs, then the only way out of this 'impasse' is to postulate that different subtypes of GoCs must exist, and that the chemical differences between the subtypes make them distinguishable for the transmitted chemical signal.

...

But what is the point of getting rid of the 'repetition' in the combinatory possibilities of different GoC types contacting a GrC (abc is allowed, aab or bcc is not) ? Is it to 'balance' the effect of the different GoC types upon individual GrCs ?

GoC axons can contact about 40 glomeruli and hence inhibit about $40 \times 50 = 2000$ different GrCs. On the population level, this 'individual balancing' would be pointless since the averaging of the random variability in the repetition would by itself lead to the same result.

[19] (D'Angelo et al. 2013)

"Golgi cells are the largest and most numerous interneurons of the granular layer (Golgi, 1874; Ramon y Cajal, 1888, 1995) , which contains one Golgi cell to every several hundred or thousand granule cells (~6000 in cats : Palkovits et al. , 1971; ~1200 in humans : Andersen et al. , 1992; ~400 in rats : Korbo et al. 1993)."

"Each Golgi cell can inhibit as many as 40 different glomeruli and a total of about 2000 granule cells, accounting for the 1:430 Golgi cell:granule cell ratio and the aforementioned convergence and divergence ratios."

"Recent calculations seem to indicate a specific organization of excitatory connectivity. Golgi cells were suggested to receive excitatory inputs from about 40 mossy fibers on basal dendrites (Kanichay and Silver, 2008) ."

...

It seems to me that it can only be meaningful if the selectivity is pushed one step further : let GoCs be MODALITY specific by way of a system of matching chemical markers.

In that case, the GoC 'chooses' to insert its axon in a glomerulus that is entered by a rosette of an MF of the 'right' modality.

Such a 'matching' however does not prevent a GrC to be contacted more than once by the same GoC type, e.g. when this GrC receives the same modality MFs on more than one dendrite.

A 'repelling' mechanism remains necessary, and there has to be such a mechanism for each GoC type (while for the oocyte there is but one sperm 'type' to deal with).

It sounds complicated, but then ontogeny IS an incredibly complex interplay of attracting and repelling chemotaxis, and of 'matching' and 'blocking' molecules to build an organ like the brain.

...

With MF-GrC connections during ontogeny being established before GoCs invade the GrL, the repelling procedure to avoid redundant inputs should occur in the GrCs, not in the GoCs.

[22] (Houck et al. 2015)

"Precedent for molecularly diverse mossy fibers exists, however, raising the question of whether nucleocortical mossy fibers may be molecularly distinct from other mossy fibers (Sillitoe et al., 2003; Gebre et al., 2011)."

[23] (Consalez et al. 2013)

"Differences in gene expression have revealed multiple granule cell subtypes [e.g., Otx 1/2- Frantz et al., 1994; nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate (NADPH)-oxidase -Hawkes and Turner, 1994; fibroblast growth factor (FG) 1- Alam et al., 1996; Eph receptors and Ephrins - Rogers et al., 1999, etc.; reviewed in Hawkes and Eisenman (1997); Ozol and Hawkes (1997)]. Multiple granule cell subtypes can be explained in two broad ways: either they represent granule cell lineages or they are a secondary response to their local environment (for example, the local mossy fibers or PCs). In many cases, we cannot distinguish these possibilities."

"An alternative mechanism might be that granule cell subtypes are specified by the type of mossy fiber (or UBC) afferent input they receive. As noted earlier (section "Review of cerebellar compartmentation") mossy fiber terminal fields from different sources and of different molecular phenotypes are restricted to parasagittal stripes that align with PC stripes (e.g., somatostatin immunoreactive- Armstrong et al., 2009; vesicular glutamate transporter immunoreactive-Gebre et al., 2012). Perhaps differential mossy fiber innervation specifies granule cell subtype."

With MFs governing the repelling, the dendrites of GrCs are forced to find an MF carrying a different modality and not just 'another MF'.

When GoCs enter the scene, they can repeat their own 'self-repelling' procedure, but it would be better if they use 'matching' molecules, such that each GoC type is bound to enter its axon only in glomeruli of the 'right' modality (of which it now only finds one on the same GrC).

The 'matching strategy' would also allow for GoCs to be contacted directly (outside the glomeruli) only by MFs of this same modality (while their dendrites inside the glomeruli can remain modality unspecific).

...

The 'connectivity rule' here then says that every dendrite of a GrC must be recipient of a different modality AND must be 'served' by a different GoC-subtype (which likely is also modality specific): the two conditions are linked (but the rule might not be applied everywhere or for every modality).

[24] (Galliano et al. 2010)

"In some of Golgi's original drawings the axonal fields of Golgi cells overlap (e.g. see Figs 2 and 3), although in subsequent drawings the Golgi cell axonal fields appear well isolated (e.g. see Eccles et al. 1967; Ramon y Cajal, 1995; Ito, 1984). This overlap would be important to allow the combinatorial inhibition of granule cells and has recently been observed using fluorescence staining in vivo (see Barmack & Yakhnitsa, 2008). Consistently, the analysis of Golgi cell-granule cell neurotransmission has recently shown that each granule cell receives inhibition from different Golgi cells, implying overlap of the axonal fields (Mapelli et al. 2010)."

[25] (Heine et al. 2010)

"The Golgi cells we recorded appeared to be exclusively driven by eye movement-related inputs and were unmodulated by vestibular or visual signals. This specificity of input is surprising not only because the large ascending dendritic fields of the Golgi cells suggest that they receive a broad convergence of diverse inputs, but also because vestibular, visual, and oculomotor signals are often already combined at the level of many VPFL (ventral paraflocculus) projecting neurons (Mustari et al., 1988; Nakamagoe et al., 2000). The fact that VPFL Golgi cells respond specifically to the eye movement inputs suggests a highly specific connectivity in the input layer of the cerebellar cortex that to our knowledge has not been previously reported."

In such a system ONE GoC would 'govern' a specific modality of all (2000 ...) its subject GrCs and - eventually - the GoC could be 'governed' by specific MFs of this same modality.

[24] (Galliano et al. 2010)

"The very specific gating nature of the inhibitory feedback was investigated (Precht & Llinias, 1969) showing that the activity of a given granule cell-Purkinje cell set was more powerfully inhibited by homonymous activation of mossy fibres (in that case from the vestibular system) than from mossy fibres innervating the same granule cells from the contralateral vestibular nerve. This indicated that Golgi cell inhibition was probably glomerulus specific and not a random inhibitory feedback, as originally supposed."

"The presence of robust GABA receptor-mediated spillover responses to Golgi cell axon stimulation, which indicates diffusion of GABA onto neighbouring dendrites (Rossi & Hamann, 1998), suggests that Golgi cell terminals can inhibit clusters of granule cells sending their dendrite in the same glomerulus (Mapelli et al. 2010)."

IF such a connecting rule exists, it probably is only enforced in GrL patches where multimodality must be combinatorial and where GrCs must act as AND-gates, since unimodal GrCs are also frequently observed. In such multimodal patches it would be pointless to have rosettes distanced from each other in order to prevent a GrC to contact a same MF more than once if it is also not prevented that this same GrC contacts other MFs which carry identical information.

...

It is important to realize that such a rule has a PPV separation effect while not relying on PPV mapping (the distancing effect which is so important for connectivity - cfr the addendum), since it also does not allow for MFs of same modality but different PPV to connect to the same GrC.

Mapping certainly occurs in the GrL, but it raises the question how many dimensions the GrL can accommodate. As a surface it lends itself 'naturally' for 2D, but 3D (engaging 'depth' ?) and certainly >3D becomes topologically very problematic.

A connectivity rule which forbids that MFs of same modality (whatever the PPV it conveys) can connect to a same GrC offers an elegant solution : it can add a dimension by 'chemical separation', without a need for 'topological separation'. Note however that 'topological separation' allows for redundant PPV inputs while 'chemical separation' does not : the latter 'rule' is stricter. Only 'chemical separation' can guarantee complete connectivity control, by ruling out any randomness. GrCs however must also 'guarantee' to provide for enough dendrites to accommodate at least the number of independent inputs.

A 'chemically separated' MF set might bring in e.g. a 3rd dimension by being uniformly distributed over the 2D surface of two PPV mapped dimensions – and that without any topological problem. The number of nodes however needs to be multiplied with the amount of the PPVs on this added dimension to accommodate all the combinatory possibilities of the now 3D ISU, and the GrCs will then need a minimum of 3 dendrites.

It is conceivable that such '3D enrichment' is only applied to certain regions in the 2D map, in PPV ranges where it matters to 'expand' the A-path possibilities in function of an additional dimension (in the mormyrid, only the body surfaces around fins and chin appendage may need to have 'a proprioceptive dimension' added to the UBC-enriched EOCD GrC inputs, to be able to filter out the electrical disturbance of fins and chin appendage muscles on the electroreceptors by movement-specific A-paths).

Instead of 'imagining' a more-dimensional ISU of which the specificity is downgraded by the presence of its less-dimensional subcombinations, we might e.g. 'see' a 2D surface which in places expands into a 3D volume where it is needed.

It also suggests that such a process might be a dynamical one when a novel need for an expansion arises.

...

While the number of input lines (MFs) and hence 'the bandwidth' for incoming information most probably stays fixed, one can still wonder if the number of terminals (the rosettes) is adaptable in adult life and if GrCs can rearrange their contacts with them (since that would be an implicit consequence of turnover of rosettes).

The PhD-thesis (2008) of Claudia Vittori (not a published article) explicitly describes the formation of new branching points and terminals upon MF's - after placing mice in an 'enriched environment (EE)' - and of filopodia (thin outgrowths of rosettes possibly exiting the glomerular sheath) - after a protocol with fear conditioning (FC).

[17] (Vittori 2009)

"When considering the average MFT density or the average branching frequency per each experimental subject, we found that EE condition clearly triggered an increase in the axonal density and branching points. Interestingly, the inter-individual variation and the distribution range of the average values was kept similar upon EE. This argues for a response of similar amplitude by all the experimental subjects involved. These findings provide first evidence that MF to GC connectivity considerably rearrange upon EE as mossy axons are able to build up a higher number of terminals and to increase their branching behaviour."

[26] (Gilmer et al. 2017)

"MF filopodia are long, thin, boutonbearing processes that extend from MFRs. They have recently been shown to form synapses on GrCs (Gao et al., 2016), raising the question of their potential role in GrC combinatorial diversity."

[17] (Vittori 2009)

"I. Presynaptic remodelling : When we examined terminal density as well as branching frequency of long axonal tracts projecting to the vermal lobule V, we found that these properties were affected by 20 days of EE conditions during adulthood, being both evaluated parameters increased upon the experience. When we looked at the morphology of the MFTs placed by the axons in the apical region of lobule V, we found that their shape and surface complexity were not affected; instead, the average MFT size was heavily decreased, thus well correlating, from an anatomical point of view, with the increased number of MFTs we observed. Conversely, FC experience did not influence the above mentioned axonal connectivity properties, but rather focused its striking effect on the MFTs, which collectively responded with dramatic remodelling of surface complexity, shape, size and process outgrowth. Based on our data, it appears correct to state that all the axons responded equally and homogeneously, in the examined lobular subregion, in terms of surface complexity, whereas shifts in size and process properties affected only a subset of the population."

The latter is also mentioned by Gao (2016) for nucleo-cortical MF-fibers.

[27] (Gao et al. 2016)

"Mice were trained to blink their eyes in a well-timed response to a light cue (CS) so as to avoid an air-puff to the eye (US) that was presented 250 ms after CS onset (Heiney et al., 2014). The density of filopodia boutons originating from nucleocortical MFs in the deeper lobule simplex of well-trained mice was significantly increased by 69.8% ($p = 0.001$) compared with that in naive mice."

"The nucleocortical MF rosettes had a larger diameter as well as more and longer filopodia-like structures compared with pre-cerebellar MFs from pontine nuclei. At the ultrastructural level, nucleocortical MF terminals contained higher densities of mitochondria and synaptic vesicles compared with neighboring, unlabeled MF rosettes, whereas the size of mitochondria and length of post-synaptic density (PSDs) did not differ. These data highlight a prominent projection of nucleocortical MFs with unique molecular and morphological features and suggest that they carry an efference copy signal of cerebellar premotor output commands."

"The high density of filopodia-like structures in the lobule simplex suggests that structural plasticity of the filopodia of nucleocortical MFs might also be involved in eyeblink conditioning, similar to what has been reported for extra-cerebellar MFs during other incremental learning paradigms (Ruediger et al. 2011)."

Vittori also finds changes in the dendrites-per-GrC number (Fig. 3) and describes GrC-dendrites that seem to be in the process of bifurcating, with each bifurcation targeting a different rosette.

Fig. 3 from [17] (Vittori 2009)

"We compared the number of dendrites characterizing mGFP-labelled GCs. In the control population, 39% of the GCs was characterized by 4 dendrites, being the most represented group, while 33% displayed 5 dendrites and 23% had 3 dendrites."

"We found that in EE mice this distribution was shifted towards a minor number of dendrites. In particular, 50% of GCs was characterized by 4 dendritic processes, still representing the biggest group as in the control population, but only 17% of the GC population had 5 dendrites. Consequently, upon EE about 31% of the GCs was characterized by 2 or 3 dendrites, while this group represented only the 24% of the control population."

"As, in general, every claw is able to contact one MFT, this shift means that the GC population is contacting a lower number of MFTs. At the same time, fewer postsynaptic counterparts are available to MFTs for synaptic transmission."

"In the GC population included in our studies, we found that ~40% of the cells at P30 and ~33% of the cells at P50 displayed at least one dendrite ending in two or more terminal claws. We could not directly visualize that presynaptic counterparts, but in most cases it was evident that two claws belonging to the same dendritic branch could not share the presynaptic terminal because of the reciprocal distance."

Logically then, GrCs must be able to retract dendrites from glomeruli and insert dendrites into other glomeruli, and this phenomenon is also a strong argument against random statistics being the 'connecting rules' between GrCs and MFs.

...

CONCLUSION

The space between rosettes made by a single MF in all cases prohibits GrCs to be contacted more than once by this same MF.

Random connectivity of GrCs with different MFs is no issue if these MFs are modality redundant, but when MFs of different modalities are available, and when ISUs - defined by a coordinate system in which modalities are the axes - are to be constructed, then it becomes important to get rid of the 'repetitive fraction' in the combinatorial possibilities.

Mapping of PPVs prevents GrCs to be contacted by MFs of same modality but carrying different PPVs, but does not prevent it when they carry the same PPV (a purely redundant input). This last restriction might be implemented by molecules specific for the modality of the MF, which - when injected into the GrC by the MF - block other MFs of the same modality to make contact with this particular GrC ('chemical' separation).

It also allows for the 'accommodation' of ISUs with more dimensions than the GrL topologically can afford, and it is to be envisaged that the 'adding' of a dimension might only be applied to PPV ranges in the other dimensions where it is needed.

In the proposed scheme the MFs should contact GrCs first since MFs are the carriers of the specific 'modality markers' and hence the 'repelling and blocking' mechanisms should already have turned the GrCs into multimodal integrators before GoCs arrive to establish their 'matching' (axonal) connections.

This view is arrived at indirectly by the 'theoretical' observation of researchers that GoCs might be prevented to inhibit a GrC more than once.

The connecting selectivity implies that chemically different GoC types must exist, but with no discernible intrinsic functional differences between GoC types this seems a pointless arrangement when considered at the population level, unless it can be linked to modality specificity.

The demonstration of dynamic activity-dependent reshuffling of input connectivity adds to the organizing possibilities.

Let's now focus on the possibility of dynamic input number control.

...

D) MODALITY CONTROL

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path : a chain of sequentially activated synapses	FFI	Feedforward inhibition
AF	Ascending fiber	GoC	Golgi cell
CB-like	Cerebellum-like	GrC	Granule cell
CWA	Correlated wrong addressing	GrL	Granular layer
DS	The signal to be decorrelated - later also : the driving signal	MF	Mossy fiber
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	PF	Parallel fiber
FBI	Feedback inhibition	PPV	Preferred parameter value
		TDFS	Traffic density fluctuation signal

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

Controlling the inhibition status of GrCs is a first and important role for GoCs.

With a smothering inhibition no GrCs will fire, but lowering it gradually the first GrCs to fire will be those with the strongest sum of inputs.

Taking a measure of the traffic in the PFs / AFs with their apical / basolateral dendrites, and with their own threshold adequately tuned, GoCs - by feedback - can stabilize the inhibition at this level (and the input via AFs ensures that FBI is dominantly local).

[28] (Cesana et al. 2013)

"The presence of ascending axon synapses onto GoCs constitutes a substrate for a specific feedback circuit onto local GrCs. Assessing the number of ascending axon contacts to GoCs is crucial to evaluate the functional impact of this circuit."

"We show here, by light and EM immunocytochemistry, that GrC ascending axons form numerous synaptic contacts onto GoC basolateral dendrites in the same parasagittal module. Combining white matter stimulations and ultrafast 2-photon Ca²⁺ imaging in GoC basolateral dendrites, we reveal activity of this synaptic articulation, which is involved in a powerful feedback circuit. These contacts represent a large fraction of overall local GrC inputs and therefore form an important feedback pathway in the modular organization of the granular layer."

Any slack in the inhibition however that allows GrCs to fire with less than all inputs 'high' ruins proper AND-gating and hence deteriorates the unambiguosness in the construction of an A-path.

...

In the section on AND-gating it was discussed how difficult it becomes to ensure proper AND-gating when more and more inputs are involved, posing the problem of the 'surnumerary inputs'.

Some GrCs can have up to 7 (!) dendrites, making the tuning for AND-gating by FBI an impossible job in these cases.

Possible 'escapes' were already proposed (GrCs not used for AND-gating, mutually exclusive inputs, redundant inputs) but maybe it can also be actively controlled which and how many inputs partake in the AND-gating done at the GrCs.

If GoCs can be modality specific, they might be used to 'silence' specific inputs.

The GrC as a whole doesn't care from which GoC via which dendrite it receives its inhibition, but if it is 'shunting inhibition' (GoC terminals being proximal to the MF terminal on the GrC dendrite) I gather that it can be meant to act in-place rather than on the neuron as a whole, and that it might serve a special purpose.

[29] (D'Angelo et al. 2013)

"Golgi-cell-granule cell synapses consist of small boutons located proximally to granule cell dendritic endings, which, in turn, receive excitatory mossy fiber terminals."

[30] (Mapelli et al. 2014)

"GABAergic inhibition operates mostly through a shunting mechanism."

"The IPSPs exert a strong inhibitory effect on granule cells limiting the excitatory post-synaptic potentials (EPSPs) rather than by hyperpolarizing the cell."

In this setup the excitation from a particular MF would be 'neutralized' and - the GoC being modality specific - it would effectively execute a shutdown of that modality for all the GrCs under its control.

...

The intraglomerular GoC dendrites are the ones that are responsible for feedforward inhibition (FFI), due to the direct MF-to-GoC excitation.

The 'command' for a GoC to execute a modality specific shutdown, however, cannot be given by this route since it would spread via the intraglomerular GoC dendrites to all GoC types, lest we should hypothesize that those GoC-dendrites are also modality-picky... Moreover, if this 'command' would (together with the other inputs) cause the GrC to fire, FBI would be triggered, and FBI, since based on GrC output, cannot be modality specific.

Hence, the shutdown command should come via a direct and pure extraglomerular MF-to-GoC connection, only that way can a specific GoC be singled out.

[31] (Holtzman et al. 2009)

"Because anatomical evidence for mossy fibre synapses with Golgi cells has been obtained (axo-dendritic; Hamori Szentagothai, 1966; axo-somatic synapse; Marron-Palay Chan-Palay, 1974), together with our own tracer results, the most straightforward explanation is that the axon reflex responses we observed were driven mainly (if not exclusively) by monosynaptic mossy fibre contacts on Golgi cells."

It has been observed that direct MF-GoC stimulation can coincide with or even precede the MF-GrC stimulation.

[32] (Duguid et al. 2015)

"We made, to our knowledge, the first voltage-clamp recordings of sensory-evoked inhibition in granule cells in vivo and show that, surprisingly, sensory-evoked inhibition often precedes mossy fiber excitation activated by the same stimulus."

[31] (Holtzman et al. 2009)

"Eccles et al. (1967b) reported that following juxtastigmatic stimulation, Golgi cell excitation slightly precedes that of granule cell excitation, and that this may suppress granule cell firing through feedforward inhibition."

Inhibition coinciding or even preceding excitation can only be explained by assuming that a distinct MF stimulated the GoC extraglomerularly, since otherwise the inhibition would be 'a step too late'. A modality specific shutdown is not to cause full-fledged FFI. If FFI were slightly advanced too it would silence the GrC altogether, while the purpose of FFI is to 'cut the GrC short' after it started firing.

Hence, the signal coming over the GoC-'commanding'-MF would have to be comparable in force to the signal coming over the MF that targets the GrC, if it is to just annul it. It may not prevent a GrC to fire when the remaining inputs 'go high'.

...

The mere existence of such direct extraglomerular MF-lines to GoCs strongly suggests that 'deliberate' commands (e.g. from the cerebrum) might control the exclusion (or inclusion) of a modality in the AND-gating process of a whole population of GrCs.

It certainly would be a very complicating factor when it comes to interpreting results from research involving MF stimulation.

...

Gap junctions between basolateral dendrites of GoCs 'of different modality' might spoil the issue, but I get the impression that gap junctions are dominantly located between apical dendrites (where for sharing the 'PF-traffic control' measurements they are useful).

[33] (Valera et al. 2016)

"Since dendritic gap junctions might have shunted and filtered GC inputs located in distant apical GoC dendrites (Vervaeke et al., 2012), potentially resulting in undetectable current at the soma, one subset of GoCs (n = 6) was recorded with the gap junction blocker carbenoxolone (100 mM) in the bath."

[34] (Vervaeke et al. 2010)

"Here we show that Connexin-36 is necessary for electrical coupling between GoCs and that GJs are mainly located on the apical dendrites."

[29] (D'Angelo et al. 2013)

"Recently, functional evidence for gap junctions connecting Golgi cell apical dendrites was reported (Dugue et al., 2009; Vervaeke et al. 2010)."

Maybe gap junctions don't exist between basolateral dendrites or only between those of GoCs of the same subtype.

Reciprocal inhibition between GoCs themselves can be seen as a correcting mechanism : if one GoC-type shuts down a specific modality, the other GoC-types inhibit somewhat less, buffering or adapting the total inhibition load on the GrC as to enable the remaining inputs to fire the GrC in concerted effort.

[35] (Hull et al. 2012)

"These experiments therefore provide direct evidence that Golgi cells form inhibitory GABAergic synapses onto other Golgi cells."

[36] (Eyre et al. 2016)

"Several studies have reported the lack of chemical inhibitory connectivity between GoCs, ruling this out as the major source of their inhibitory inputs (Dieudonne, 1998; Dugue, et al., 2009; Vervaeke et al., 2010), although some connectivity among GoCs has been reported (Hull and Regehr, 2012) ."

(Is this conflictual issue resolved ? I clearly vote for Hull and Regehr).

"The issue of whether GoCs provide chemical GABAergic innervation to each other has been debated; two recent studies using paired recordings found no evidence for this connection (Dugue, et al., 2009; Vervaeke et al., 2010), but Hull and Regehr (2012) demonstrated a GoC-to-GoC connection probability of 20% . A potential reason for this discrepancy might be the consequence of tonic presynaptic GABAB receptor-mediated inhibition of GABA release from GoC axons. Dugue, et al. (2009) and Vervaeke et al. (2010) did not eliminate GABAB receptor-mediated presynaptic inhibition, whereas Hull and Regehr (2012) performed their experiments in the presence of a GABAB receptor antagonist."

[37] (De Schutter et al. 2017)

"GoCs are connected together by gap junctions and have also been reported to inhibit each other sparsely."

[35] (Hull et al. 2012)

"Reports of molecular diversity among Golgi cells (Geurts et al., 2001; Simat et al., 2007) raise the intriguing possibility that only specific subpopulations of Golgi cells are synaptically connected. There is, however, no evidence to date for such an arrangement."

...

Why should a modality be ‘silenced’ when MFs bring it in ? An essential difference between a CB-like structure like the ELL and the cerebellum itself is that the first is to handle correlations that DO arise, while the latter is (also) to handle correlations that MIGHT arise.

In the section on connectivity I evoked the picture of a 2D grid that can develop regional ‘expansions’ into 3D where the local addition of a supplementary (independent) modality permits the generation of more specifically adapted A-paths, and such a region is to ‘provide’ more GrCs for the 3D combinatory possibilities.

We can however imagine that the 2D grid has already an abundant set of GrCs allocated to it from the start and that MFs carrying the 3rd modality are already in place and cover its whole surface.

In that case there is no need for ‘expansion’ : each ‘node’ in the 2D grid has access to a large set of GrCs. This set can be used as a ‘unit’ (all GrCs working in parallel – 2D) or can be ‘diversified/segmented’ along the supplementary parameter (creating ‘subnodes’ for 3D). If the 3rd parameter input however shows no correlation at all with the DS it better be silenced since its contribution in the AND-gating would cause erratic ‘on and offs’ all over the 2D surface, slowing down (but not degrading) the decorrelation process (cfr the ‘spatial diffusion’ concept in the CWA section in Part 1). If it does correlate with the DS– or starts to do – then the silencing should be disabled (only locally if need be).

This view might fit more with a cerebellum that – on top of the genetically programmed ‘allocation’ of GrC amounts and prewiring of ‘essential’ MFs – also allows for ‘experimental space’ by providing prewired input lines which might or might not be useful for the development of specific skills during life.

...

CONCLUSION

While maintaining a high enough global inhibition level (controlled by FBI) is a necessary requirement if GrCs are to be kept in 'AND-gating modus', GoCs might also be recruited in a modality specific manner to 'shut down' specific inputs of a whole set of GrCs.

The 'shutdown command' is to be delivered in a way that it cannot spread to GoCs that subserve another modality. Hence an MF that targets a GoC directly and does not collateralize to a glomerulus (dendrites from several GoC-types might be present there) is to be used : with inhibition coinciding or even preceding the excitation that seems to be the case. Gap junctions between basolateral dendrites of GoCs of different modality better not exist to avoid 'command sharing'. Calibrated shunting inhibition should not cause FFI.

Reciprocal GoC inhibition might adapt the level slightly downwards to enable AND-gated firing with one input less.

Why should higher centers implement modality control to silence inputs that were provided in the first place ?

One reason could be that the inputs and the scope of an ISU are often genetically determined : it might already include modality inputs of which the usefulness can only appear later during life (evolution will judge and keep or change the blueprint). If or while these inputs remain unused (do not correlate with the DS) they better stay silenced (e.g. until a pianist learns to correlate his fingers with what he hears or reads – if he 'got the talent' for it).

Let's say some more now on ISUs.

...

E) INPUT SPACE ISSUES

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path : a chain of sequentially activated synapses	GrC	Granule cell
CN	(Deep) Cerebellar nuclei	GrL	Granular layer
D	Depress(ion)	ISU	Input space unit
DLN	Deep Learning Network	MF	Mossy fiber
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	PN	The pontine nuclei
GS	The signal(s) that guide the activation process	PPV	Preferred parameter value

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

When the sources (of MFs) are cerebral I am convinced that they can adapt not only the 'format' but also the content coming over the MFs.

When considering an ISU it is to be understood that it contains 'the set of all possible A-paths' that can be taken in it, but the actual A-path that is taken in real time is still to be viewed as a one-dimensional route outlined by the specifics of the actual GSs.

All paths are not equally probable however : physical restraints, for example, may 'forbid entrance' into specific areas of the input space because of impossible combinations of body state parameter values.

A dog may be able to scratch its head with its hindleg, but humans cannot.

GrCs which represent 'the local points' in such 'forbidden areas' will stay silent since the sum of their inputs will never reach AND-gating threshold, and hence constitute kind of a waste of resources.

...

It is reasonable to believe that the number of long-distance lines (like cerebro-pontine fibers), once established, stays fixed, implying that we get of each modality the number that is genetically programmed, hence determining the 'bandwidth' for each modality.

Genetic variation in the number of long-distance lines is possible though, and that may give each of us different talents and abilities (some of which may be extraordinary), but this specific 'set of ISUs' is given for life.

Of course, this set expanded in the course of evolution - the cerebellum incorporating more and more ISUs, creating more 'guiding power' (control) upon actions (in the most general sense), resulting in greater survival chances.

But still, for each ISU, a problem of efficient use of resources may arise.

...

The 'input space problem' mentioned by some - especially with multi-D ISUs - arises when it is expected that all possible (and impossible ?) situations should be represented by a 'point' (node) in the ISU.

[38] (Spanne et al. 2013)

"The exponential growth of the space spanned by all input dimensions and all the resulting implications are what Bellman coined as the curse of dimensionality."

It is my conviction that this problem is avoided (for a great deal) by the source of MFs adapting the 'content' of the signal they carry.

Fig. 4

Considering e.g. a 2D ISU, we automatically visualize a grid with evenly distributed values on x and y axis (cfr Fig. 4a), but in cerebello the MFs not necessarily have to represent evenly distributed values and we might get something like in Fig. 4b.

It means that an ISU can have sparse and dense regions of MF resolution (the intervals between PPVs being wider or narrower).

I am thinking of sources that are capable to provide adequate GS-resolution, but - within the restriction of a structurally fixed amount of available MFs - can assign more resolution to certain parameter ranges to the detriment of others (adaptive resolution), thereby 'shaping' an ISU (and hence reducing the 'consumption' of GrCs) to what is really needed.

[38] (Spanne et al. 2013)

"It would require all possible recombinations to be present at the level of the granule layer, requiring an enormous amount of GrCs, most of which would remain superfluous if there were no nonlinear interactions between the recombinated dimensions that actually needed to be approximated. In contrast, if it was sufficient to only use specific projections in the input space, selected to enable the system to approximate specific non-linear functions, the number of MFs and GrCs needed could possibly be substantially reduced."

"Input dimensions that never interact (that we will refer to as 'superfluous projections') would not need to converge at all, and it would be possible to approximate additive functions of two or more input dimensions even if they did not converge until the PC layer.

"In relation to the potential number of projections that could be formed within the complex sensorimotor space of our bodies, the cerebellum and the number of GrCs that are available poses a severe limit on the number of projections that can be represented. It follows that the selection of these projections is an important step for the organism so that the most useful calculations, relative to the sensorimotor apparatus available, is made available to the cerebellum."

...

In the cerebral cortex 'modalities' are represented by areas which also got their share of cortical columns by genetic ruling.

In primary areas the internal organization follows rules depending on input nature.

When we advance into association areas, we can find subareas specifically dedicated to special classes of associations (e.g. face recognition) and these subareas no doubt are 'defined' by the specific interarea tracts that converge upon them.

But the detailed organization inside subareas must rely on 'self-organizing mapping algorithms' of 'deep learning networks' [DLNs], which ultimately assign a 'meaning' to a certain locus, and the output lines emerging from a locus are to convey the info to the cerebellum.

These output lines, once established during ontogeny, will - like the MFs - stay fixed in position and number for life, but the specific 'content' they transmit will have to evolve together with the learning process at their cerebral source.

...

Typical DLNs produce output in sparse code, and - important - the number of different outputs it can produce depends on the amount of entity classes it is asked to learn to discriminate.

The 'convergence problem' only poses a resource problem if one expects the cortical area to provide the space to have the total range of all possible entities to be represented in sparse code.

I believe that is only done insofar as there is a need for it.

Fig. 5 from [39] (Michael Nielsen 2015)

If written digits are to be recognized, then a DLN with 10 output lines suffices (cfr Fig. 5), but I presume that 'in vivo' we will see an output field (and not 10 individual lines) being 'segmented' into ten parts (be it distributed or not).

If more entities have to be 'learned' the more the segmentation proceeds.

In a 'supervised' training process, it is the training instance that decides which output lines should be connected to which entity recognition and we may wonder if the cerebellum's feedback to the source plays a role in this process by 'indicating its wishes'.

But the relevant point that I want to make for now is that the content of MFs can change in parallel with the growing discriminative and associative power at their source.

More drastically still : when a cerebral cortex area is deafferented and neighbouring areas start to encroach upon the unemployed territory (the competition balance being broken), I can imagine that it will drill down to the cerebellum where MFs might even change their 'modality' and not just the parameter value they represent.

...

Just observing the development of a baby, we can see that its cerebellar coordinative capabilities go parallel with its developing sensory-associative and -discriminative power in the cerebrum.

Hence, I believe that - depending on the demands for GSs for activities that develop accuracy while training - the MFs will be provided with gradually more and more fine-tuned information by their sources (in the cerebrum) in the parameter-ranges that really matter, thereby avoiding to spend undue resources of MFs (and GrCs) to parameter-ranges almost never used.

But if a novel activity changes the demands, the MFs will adapt and shift content, in parallel with the changes that the activity causes in the cerebro-cortical areas.

If subcortical sources are able to do the same (and how) is an open question but see :

[38] (Spanne et al. 2013)

"A number of observations suggest that the spinal cord is an appropriate place to take the decisions of which projections that are relevant. Simulations using a realistic network structure and local sensory feedback patterns have shown that the spinal circuitry does provide a number of useful sensorimotor functions that can be played on by using motor commands. The connectivity of the circuitry is established through plasticity processes whose outcome depends on the configuration of the sensorimotor apparatus and the existence of spontaneous movements. In other words, the development of the spinal circuitry is adapted to the development of the sensorimotor apparatus and the correspondence between movement and sensory feedback. It is likely that individual neurons of the spinal circuitry during the development 'finds' appropriate combinations of sensors and motor command signals, associations that are helpful for brain movement control by providing such assistive sensorimotor functions. The close correspondence between the sensor signals and motor command signals in the individual neurons could be a means for the spinocerebellar system to avoid superfluous recombinations (which the system can certainly not afford)."

...

CONCLUSION

When the cerebral cortex provides the GSs, which in turn define ISUs, then we may presume organisational developments in the cerebral cortex to be of great influence on the cerebellar GrL.

Hence, a refinement in sensory discriminative power should go parallel with a better 'resolution' of the parameterization of ISUs, and the depth of resolution in parts of these ISUs most probably will be adapted to real world requirements and limitations, with reafferentation (a change of modality) as extreme consequence.

With the amount of cerebro-cerebellar connection lines probably genetically determined it is suggested that resolution refinement is a gradual process of output resources segmentation by 'self-organizing mapping algorithms' in DLNs, where cerebellar feedback itself might play an important role, 'to indicate the needs'.

'Adaptive resolution' most probably is the way for DLNs to deal with the 'dimensionality demon', when non-overlapping specific output lines are to be selected to represent only the states that matter. Even in the spinal cord it is observed.

A 'talent' may be the reflection of exceptional internal cerebral connectivity, or from exceptional cerebro-cerebellar connectivity, both in first instance determined by genetic factors (while personal training can only optimize the given possibilities).

...

Let's – in the following sections – focus on the cytoarchitectonic differences between the cerebellum and the ELL.

...

F) DS AND GSs ON THE SCALE OF THE CEREBELLUM

Abbreviations used in this section :

AF	Ascending fiber	GS	The signal(s) that guide the activation process
AS	the activating signal : the output signal of a GrC that activates a PF-PuC synapse	GrC	Granule cell
B-spike	Broad spike	GrL	Granular layer
BIE	The backpropagating integration effect	ISU	Input space unit
CF	Climbing fiber	JLN	Juxtalar nucleus
CN	(Deep) Cerebellar nuclei	MF	Mossy fiber
D	Depress(ion)	MGC	Medium ganglion cell
DS	The signal to be decorrelated - later also : the driving signal	MoL	Molecular layer
EGp	The eminentia granularis posterior in the ELL	PF	Parallel fiber
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	PriC	Principal cell
		PuC	Purkinje cell

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

Some crucial cytoarchitectonic issues which differentiate the ELL from the cerebellum have to be addressed.

For the time being, accept the view that the cerebellum is a decorrelating machine as if it were a giant ELL (this view will be 'adapted' in the section on 'the basic algorithm').

...

The ELL of the mormyrid processes three different kinds of electrosensory signals (passive, active and communication, each with their own mapping), but these DSs can be considered to relate in the same way to the ISUs in the EGp (i.e. the same GSs and hence A-paths can be used for the three of them).

The ELL DSs are 2D-mapped, being a projection of the body surface, and all points on this map have to undergo their proper decorrelation process.

In the EGp itself it is not necessary to 'replicate' the ISUs in the EGp for each of the three DSs nor for each point in their maps. Instead, different 'instances of ISUs' can be allocated to each such point by having the PFs traverse a whole series of PriCs (MGCs in particular). Each PriC harbours another set of 'synapse memory' that is available for the decorrelation process of signals coming out of the underlying region, since PriCs are positioned above the DS-maps and hence are mapped themselves.

The PFs are supposed to reach out far enough to 'cover' all the DS-maps.

The GrCs engaged in putting through the afferent signals (the DSs) to the PriCs are located in the deep GrL of the ELL, and they are 'special' : they can be inhibitory, they are contacted by the JLN and maybe by other instances, they are not used for combinatorial AND-gating, and - being an extension of the afferents - they share their mapping.

[40] (Requarth et al. 2014)

"ELL principal cells integrate somatotopically organized input from electroreceptors with input from a mossy fiber- granule cell-parallel fiber system that conveys a wide variety of information, including both CD and proprioceptive feedback related to movements (Bell et al., 2008)".

Each ISU then, represented by an exclusive set of GrCs in the EGp, by way of its exclusive PFs, can 'serve' a host of DSs lying in the 'PF-beam', DSs for which in the ELL a local subset of PF-PriC synapses is used as a memory block that manages the averaging of the signal timeslices generated by the local point in the map, and that in function of the 'broadcasted' A-paths.

In the cerebellum, we have to expect that the number of ISUs and DSs is several orders larger, and that PFs will traverse a multiple of DS territories.

The cerebellum being remarkably similar to the ELL in having GrCs sending PFs through arrays of PuCs, it strongly suggests that it is also able to decorrelate DSs with the help of GSs.

...

There is, however, a pertinent question : with PuCs lacking basilar dendrites, where do the DSs come in ? With basilar DS input gone, the B-spike also loses its rationale : it might have been no match any more for the scope of a PuC with its huge, extensively ramified and synapse laden dendritic tree – the B-spike unable to travel from the soma to the outskirts of such a dendritic tree. Instead, the CF 'climbing up' the tree seems to take over the B-spike function by delivering its 'message' forcefully all over the PuC by extracellular route.

But CFs seriously cannot be carrying detailed DS info content as sensory afferents did in the ELL, although they seem to give the command to adjust synapses, as the B-spike did.

The only other fibers that 'climb up' the PuC dendritic tree are the AFs, and they 'deliver' (as Gundappa-Sulur, De Schutter and Bower have indicated) at the dendrite ends (with synapses that are not being individually adjusted).

[41] (Gundappa-Sulur et al. 1999)

"Perhaps most surprisingly, serial reconstructions of postsynaptic spines and their associated dendrites demonstrated that spines contacted by ascending segment synapses are located exclusively on the smallest diameter distal regions of the Purkinje cell dendrites, whereas parallel fiber synapses are found exclusively on intermediate- and large-diameter regions of the spiny branchlets. Based on two independent calculations, we estimate that 20% of the granule cell synapses onto a Purkinje cell are actually made by the ascending segment. By using computer simulations of a single Purkinje cell dendrite, we have also demonstrated that synchronous activation of these distal ascending segment inputs could produce a substantial somatic response. Taken together, these results suggest that the two different regions of granule cell axons may play very different physiologic roles in cerebellar cortex. J.Comp. Neurol. 408:580-596, 1999."

"Within the cerebellum, some preliminary results suggest that metabotropic glutamate receptors may be associated with parallel fiber synapses and not with those of the ascending segments (T. Knöpfel, personal communication). Given the possible importance of these receptors in mechanisms of synaptic modification like LTD (De Schutter, 1995a), this finding is consistent with our previous speculation that LTD may not occur in ascending segments."

Dean apparently refutes this, but I am convinced that De Schutter's view is the functionally sound one.

[42] (Dean et al. 2010)

"It has also been reported that the synapses made by the ascending axon and by the PFs differ in their susceptibility to long-term depression in PCs in vitro, but this does not seem to be a prominent trait in PCs in vivo, where inputs from granule cells located beneath and from granule cells not located beneath the PC seem equally susceptible to potentiation and depression. Furthermore, a recent in vitro study of ascending and PF inputs to PCs using optical stimulation indicates that the two inputs are functionally equivalent."

With CFs ruled out, it seems then that the only alternative to bring in the DS, is the channel already used by the GS : the MF-GrC-PuC route.

And, apparently, the DS is to be delivered at signal relaying AF-PuC synapses, and the ASs at adjustable PF-PuC synapses.

...

Does the cerebellar GrL combine the functions of what were two different GrC populations (EGp and 'deep GrL') in the ELL ? Are the GrCs now coping with a DS as well as with GSs, sending DS and ASs over the same highways to the PuCs, all this enormously upsized to a supermarket of DSs and GSs ? Can a 'patch' be dedicated to the processing of a particular DS (eventually mapped), and also be capable of generating A-paths based on locally distributed GS modalities ?

'Microzones' are a set of patches that serve a common goal, with the outputs of their PuCs converging onto a same focus in the CN, and these microzones - transversally small but sagittally elongated with an orientation orthogonal to the PFs - are optimally positioned to 'capture' a maximum of A-paths coming over all these PFs.

Sometimes, several transversally separated microzones must join their resources to form microcomplexes, as needed to 'serve' the specific goal or target effectors of this 'elementary' unit.

...

With the PFs being several mms long, all the generated A-paths are transmitted to the numerous PuCs in their reach, to all patches 'whom it may concern'.

A particular PuC then, will 'sense unrolling A-paths', not just the one generated in its own patch, but many more which have been generated in a host of neighbouring patches in the row : just move or sense or think and a plethora of A-paths are being unrolled, all over the cerebellum.

It happens continuously, independent of the presence of a DS, and it is pure GrL activity, intended for the PuCs but not dependent on them : you might think them away and just see an immense patchwork generating and transmitting A-paths.

...

The cerebellum harbours thousands of microzones, each containing a set of patches, each patch containing numerous GrCs, the total of which runs in the billions, and all these GrCs give rise to a PF.

With the size of the cerebellum, a tremendous wiring density problem arises, prohibiting that all patches may connect to all other patches, and that PFs can keep running to span the whole width of the (human) cerebellum (in 'small' cerebella they might do, and I never encountered a publication mentioning the issue in which species the PF length begins to fall short relative to the cerebellar width).

It is a topological problem (tackled by evolution) to find on the basis of 'vital relevance'

- 1) the best reciprocal placement of patches, replicating them in different surroundings when necessary ('fractured' somatotopy), and
- 2) the best distribution of inputs (collateralization), with boundaries and chemotaxis all under the control of marker molecules.

Hence, with PFs having their sagittal position and limited length, the same DS might have to be distributed to several patches (mapping again) where other sets of PFs transmit A-paths based on other GSs (combinations of modalities).

[43] (Schwarz et al. 1999)

"The hypothesized pontine representation of motor strategies implies that signals that are likely to be coupled in a sensorimotor context are mapped close together. The computational objective for such an arrangement might lie in the fact that spatially precise and local operations are used to couple and to integrate a set of functionally related signals, a design that seems to be required in view of the lack of long-range connections in the cerebellar cortex."

The same necessity of distribution might hold for GSs, which - in that case - implies that ISUs are effectively replicated in several locations of the GrL.

Much of all this is accepted view of course, but I place it in the context of DS, GS, AS and A-path concepts.

...

Let's zoom in on the PFs for a moment.

Since cerebellar GrCs emit AFs that bifurcate at different heights in the molecular layer [MoL] into PFs (and stop going higher up), the AF density decreases from the deep layer to the superficial layer, and so does the density of the thin terminal branches of the PuC-dendrites.

[41] (Gundappa-Sulur, De Schutter and Bower; 1999)

"Given the known geometry of granule cell axons, if ascending segment synapses terminate exclusively on Purkinje cell dendrites <1.3 µm in diameter, then one would expect Purkinje cell dendrites in deeper regions of the molecular layer to have a larger percentage of these very small, spiny branchlets than dendrites in superficial layers. This prediction is based on the assumptions that the ascending segments bifurcate into parallel fibers in roughly equal proportion at all horizontal levels of the molecular layer (Palay and Chan-Palay, 1974) and that ascending segment axons make an equal number of synapses along their entire vertical length prior to branching (Pichitpornchai et al., 1994) . If both of these assumptions are correct, then there should be many more ascending segment synapses and, thus, more Purkinje cell dendrites <1.3 µm in diameter in deeper than superficial regions of the molecular layer."

"The restriction of ascending segment synapses to the smallest diameter Purkinje cell dendrites results in an increase in small-diameter dendrites in the deeper regions of the molecular layer . We found many more small-diameter dendrites in the lower half of the dendrite than in the upper half."

While the number of bifurcations and hence the number of originating PFs may be assumed to be constant at each horizontal level, PFs get more 'room' in higher regions and apparently they colonize it by getting longer.

Since an unrolling A-path engages a whole series of PFs, and since PFs differ in length (depending on their vertical position in the MoL), A-paths generated in a far-off patch in the row will suffer from more and more 'deletions' with growing distance as PFs activated for a particular step in the path drop out (providing space for others that 'join in'), but that doesn't ruin the capacity of the remaining steps to be fully usable for a decorrelation procedure.

It is nevertheless better to avoid such 'wearing off by distance' and hence topology is of importance : DSs better find a mix of correlatable (or otherwise relevant) modalities in close (transversal) proximity.

...

CONCLUSION

The comparable PF-PuC relationship in the ELL and the cerebellum strongly suggests that the latter can implement decorrelation too, but the absence of basilar dendrites raises the question of where the DS is delivered.

CFs take over the 'plasticity commanding task' of the B-spikes and also seem to offer a more powerful solution for conveying info until into the outermost dendrites of the huge PuC tree, but paradoxically it looks as if they are not really intended and conceived to be info-rich DS carriers.

AFs - non-existing in the ELL - are far better suited for it and 'inject' their DS info right into the dendritic endings, but this 'blending' of DS and GS infrastructure – anatomically segregated in the ELL - is kind of asking for problems (it will be the focus in the next section).

Apart from this there is a scaling problem :

- in the ELL, ISUs defined by a few GS inputs (EOCD+UBCs, proprioception ...), can serve a few related DS-input types, each of them body surface mapped, and each point (small region ...) in such a map has its block of allocated synapse memory in the overlying PriCs to manage the signal decorrelation.
- in the cerebellum, the number of DSs and A-paths is upsized enormously, creating wiring density problems, coercing evolution to judicious selection of which DSs are to meet which A-paths, resulting in a strategy of fractured somatotopy and collateralized distribution.

Regions serving a particular DS type are called 'patches' (which may be topically organized), and the collection of patches with PuCs serving a particular common goal are called microzones, which on occasion combine to form microcomplexes.

PFs cannot span the entire cerebellar width anymore, and are of different lengths due to packing restrictions.

The restricted lengths of PFs can cause A-paths to suffer from 'step deletions', degrading its quality in function of the transversal distance between the 'origin' of the A-path and its destination PuCs, hence this distance better be somewhat limited to stay in reach of enough of the shortest PFs.

...

G) PATCH AND PF TYPES

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path : a chain of sequentially activated synapses	GS	The signal(s) that guide the activation process
AF	Ascending fiber	GoC	Golgi cell
AS	The activating signal : the output signal of a GrC that activates a PF-PuC synapse	GrC	Granule cell
B-spike	Broad spike	GrL	Granular layer
CF	Climbing fiber	MF	Mossy fiber
DS	The signal to be decorrelated - later also : the driving signal	MGC	Medium ganglion cell
EGp	The eminentia granularis posterior in the ELL	MLI	Molecular layer interneuron
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	MoL	Molecular layer
FFI	Feedforward inhibition	PF	Parallel fiber
		PuC	Purkinje cell

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

The cerebellar GrL may appear structurally 'homogeneous', but researchers observe patches with striking prevalence of unimodal GrCs (same input on all dendrites), as well as patches which are 'hotspots' of multimodal GrCs (combining inputs of different modalities).

[42] (Dean et al. 2010)

"In some experimental systems granule cells seem to receive modality- and receptive field-specific input from all afferent MF inputs, and there is even evidence that granule cell inputs might be submodality-specific (for example they respond to either skin hair deflection or stimulation of tactile skin receptors; they can be activated by either phasic or tonic tactile skin input, et cetera) ."

"It has been reported that MFs that are driven by the same modality but which code the input in different ways terminate on separate sets of granule cells, and that granule cells only receive MF inputs with similar coding."

[45] (Huang et al. 2013)

"Lastly, some cerebellar areas are dominated by EB granule cells. These areas include paramedian lobule, the paraflocculus, and Crus2 . These areas are 'hotspots' for the intersection of ECN and BPN pathways, where the majority of proprioceptive granule cells also receive BPN inputs."

Hence, depending on the input types, we might view these patches as being respectively destined for the relaying of a DS or for the generation of an A-path by way of GSs.

Many a researcher apparently finds it difficult to reconcile 'prevailing theory' with the existence of such disparate GrC input patterns.

[46] (Jörntell et al. 2006)

"The concepts of pattern discrimination and sparse coding in granule cells have heavily influenced current models about the function of the cerebellar granule layer (Marr, 1969; Albus, 1971; Tyrrell and Willshaw, 1992; Houk et al., 1996; Schweighofer et al., 1998, 2001; Wolpert et al., 1998; Chadderton et al., 2004; Semyanov et al., 2004). The underlying assumption is that there is a divergent distribution of mossy fiber input to the granule layer so that the individual granule cell samples different types of mossy fiber input and therefore works as an associative element. Sparse coding, meaning that granule cells are silent under resting conditions and fire just a few spikes when the adequate combination of inputs activates the cell, was thought to be a consequence of this organization."

"Our findings disagree with the sparse coding pattern discrimination concept in that

- (1) we did not find a convergence of different types of mossy fiber inputs in granule cells,
- (2) granule cells with some types of mossy fiber input were not silent at rest, and
- (3) all granule cells with strong peripheral input fired tremendously strong spike trains when activated appropriately."

"Various theories of granule cells as temporal pattern generators have been presented, most notably the variations on delay-line coding (for review, see Medina et al., 2000; Medina and Mauk, 2000; Ohya et al., 2003). These theories were not supported in our recordings, in which granule cells were activated by repeated, uniform stimulations."

[47] (Spanne et al. 2013)

"At least for the cerebellar regions involved in limb control, MFs carrying functionally equivalent inputs preferably target the same set of GrCs. A consequence is that the probability of finding GrCs sampling functionally disparate input would be expected to be low. Altogether, the findings of these studies were at odds with previous theoretical predictions that GrCs were expected to integrate MF information from widely separate, functionally disparate sources, and presented a challenge to our understanding of the cerebellar granule layer and thereby of the cerebellar cortex in general."

...

The first determinant of the GrC input pattern is the local availability of MF input modalities (and in research, modalities can be overlooked).

[45] (Huang et al. 2013)

"The observation that our labeling strategy rarely accounted for all presynaptic partners of an individual granule cell suggests that multimodality is likely a more prevalent feature of cerebellar granule cells than indicated by the convergence of the ECN and BPN pathways reported here."

With more MF modalities available, and 'left' to random connectivity there will still be a mixture of 'connectedness' ranging from uni- to multimodal in function of the respective MF densities, but in theory, with all parameters known, combination mathematics should be able to indicate if connectivity 'rules' are in vigour.

Finding patches where GrCs are unimodal despite the close proximity at the cellular level of MFs of different modality suggests a rule that forbids a GrC to contact more than one modality, while finding patches where multimodal GrCs are much more prevalent than chance connectivity permits suggests a rule that constrains/forbids a GrC to contact the same modality more than once.

[45] (Huang et al. 2013)

"We observed three types of granule cell terrain across cerebellar areas. Some cerebellar areas, such as medial vermis, were composed mostly of E and E+ granule cell. In some cases the lack of EB cells was due to the scarcity of BPN inputs to the region, but in other regions the number of granule cells receiving BPN inputs (B, B+) was roughly equivalent to the number receiving ECN inputs. Therefore, vermal areas harbor proprioceptive pathways which are segregated from BPN inputs at the cellular level. Other areas intermingle all three granule cell types, this category includes lateral vermis, simple lobule, copula of the pyramis and Crus1."

It certainly would be interesting to have more detailed insight in the actual connectivity.

...

What would be the implications of having 'DS and GS patches' ?

Let's define what a 'pure DS-patch' would be : a patch with GrCs receiving DS but no GS inputs. These GrCs should 'broadcast' the DS faithfully to the entire dendritic tree of the PuCs lying overhead (like the B-spikes did in MGCs) : it requires a dense activity of MFs, GrCs and AFs.

With unimodal GrCs, the inhibition status and the AND-gating, present or not, are not of much relevance. The passage through the GrC relay however better does not affect the DS by truncation or filtering or by whatever degrading effect, but eliminating a bit of noise is OK.

[44] (Dean et al. 2010)

"Although there is disagreement about whether granule cells always receive similar MF inputs, and about whether granule cell firing can be triggered by a single MF or requires multiple MF inputs, the recent recording data suggest that the granular layer transmits MF inputs with relatively modest alterations - certainly far more modest than those required by typical adaptive-filter models."

[46] (Jörntell et al. 2006)

"Regardless of input type, the temporal patterns of granule cell spike activity, both spontaneous and evoked, appeared to primarily follow the activity in the presynaptic mossy fibers, although much of the nonsynchronized mossy fiber input was filtered out. In contrast to the prevailing theories of granule cell function, our results suggest a function of granule cells as signal-to-noise enhancing threshold elements, rather than as sparse coding pattern discriminators or temporal pattern generators."

Maybe the level of inhibition by GoCs is calibrated to that end, but there might be other mechanisms like suggested by Schwartz that allow low-frequency MF signals to be relayed quite faithfully by GrCs.

[48] (Schwartz et al. 2012)

"We find that low-frequency MF input modulates the intrinsic firing of Purkinje cells, and that this signal transmission through the GC layer requires synaptic activation of Mg²⁺-block-resistant NMDA receptors (NMDARs) that are likely to contain the GluN2C subunit. Slow NMDAR conductances sum temporally to contribute approximately half the MF-GC synaptic charge at hyperpolarized potentials. Simulations of synaptic integration in GCs show that the NMDAR and slow spillover-activated AMPA receptor (AMPA) components depolarize GCs to a similar extent. Moreover, their combined depolarizing effect enables the fast quantal AMPAR component to trigger action potentials at low MF input frequencies. Our results suggest that the weak Mg²⁺ block of GluN2C-containing NMDARs enables transmission of low-frequency MF signals through the input layer of the cerebellar cortex."

By engaging all the PuC terminal dendrites the DS is to influence via the AFs the postsynaptic side of all the downstream presynaptically activated PF-PuC synapses. PuCs in a DS patch expect passing PF traffic to provide the A-paths (generated in GS-patches elsewhere) to activate these PF-PuC synapses sequentially.

A DS patch does not generate an A-path by itself however (by lack of GS input), and hence its peculiarity is that - while its AFs do continue into PFs - there is no A-path to send elsewhere. A DS crossing the bifurcation point would be a stranger in AS-territory, at best doing no harm.

In the ELL, the deep GrCs do not add to PF traffic, AFs are 'not applicable' and the B-spike distributes the DS all over the overlying MGCs.

A DS also should not be cut short by an FFI time-windowing effect.

...

Now let's define what a 'pure GS-patch' would be : a patch with GrCs receiving GS but no DS inputs. GrCs here require a state of strong inhibition by GoCs to have GSs transformed into ASs by strict AND-gating, distributing the ASs - timeslice by timeslice - over a series of AFs/PFs to build an A-path (a family of A-paths) : a sparse activity of GrCs, AFs and PFs.

A GS patch however, by lack of a DS input to process, has the peculiarity of placing its overlying PuCs in a situation of 'technical unemployment' - an unacceptable waste of resources.

In the ELL, the GrCs of the EGp serve a whole population of MGCs with their A-paths, but they are not allotted to specific MGCs - the deep GrCs are.

In the cerebellum though - with 'uniform' GrCs all having an AF bifurcating into a PF - it looks as a weird situation.

However, let's follow what anatomy suggests.

...

If the AFs of DS-patches continue into PFs, then - maybe - it is their 'intention' to send their DS by way of the PFs also to other patches in their reach, and these better should be the GS-patches where 'unemployed' PuCs are awaiting DS-input to start working.

[49] (Valera et al. 2016)

"Several studies have shown that PCs are excited by a unique set of GCs localized in the same microzone as themselves (Cohen and Yarom, 1998; Bower and Woolston, 1983; Brown and Bower, 2001; Isope and Barbour, 2002) . These results suggest that local GCs provide the major input to PCs and that the majority of GC-PC synapses are silent (Ekerot and Jörntell, 2001; Isope and Barbour, 2002) . In contrast, other studies demonstrated that PCs can be driven by a restricted subset of GCs belonging to a different microzone (Ekerot and Jörntell, 2003; Dean et al., 2010; Jörntell and Ekerot, 2002; Ekerot and Jörntell, 2001) ."

"These findings demonstrate that while local GCs make a strong connection with PCs most of the time, exceptions may occur. Also, GCs located at several hundred micrometers from the recorded PC can make strong connections via their PFs, while neighboring patches can be silent, indicating that information originating in distant microzones can have a strong influence on a given PC."

It would solve the riddle of the 'peculiarities'.

There are consequences to face however : it would imply having two types of PFs : PF populations transmitting A-paths and PF populations transmitting a DS.

...

It is important to stress here that – in principle - I follow the view of De Schutter and Bower i.e. that PuCs are not PF-driven but AF-driven and that PFs only modulate the AF signal, requiring the modulatory input to be located downstream of the AF input.

[50] (Bower 2010)

"This modulatory regulation of the dynamic balance between the large voltage dependent membrane conductances directly influences the response of the Purkinje cell to input from the ascending branch (Santamaria and Bower, 2005) . Specifically, because the synapses of the ascending synapses contact only the smallest spiny branchlets of the Purkinje cell (Gundappa-Sulur et al., 1999; Lu et al., 2009), their voltage effects traverse regions of the dendrite under voltage clamp control of parallel fibers and feed-forward inhibition. We have interpreted this geometrical arrangement to suggest that the local parallel fiber/feed-forward voltage clamp mechanism serves functionally to modulate inputs from the ascending segment axons."

[51] (Santamaria et al. 2002)

"Based on anatomical, physiological, and model-based studies, it has been proposed that synapses associated with the ascending segment of granule cell axons provide the principle excitatory drive on Purkinje cells which is then modulated by the more numerous parallel fiber synapses.

In this study we have evaluated this idea using a detailed compartmental model of a cerebellar Purkinje cell by providing identical ascending segment synaptic inputs during different levels of random parallel fiber and molecular interneuron input.

Results suggest that background inputs from parallel fibers and molecular layer interneurons can have a substantial effect on the response of Purkinje cells to ascending segment inputs.

Interestingly, these effects are not reflected in the average firing rate of the Purkinje cell and are thus entirely dendritic in effect.

These results are considered in the context of the known segregated spatial distribution of the parallel fibers and ascending segment synapses and a new hypothesis concerning the functional organization of cerebellar cortical circuitry."

If, however, DS transmitting PFs exist, this view is to be adapted to accept that these PF-types can be considered to drive PuCs too. These PFs should ‘act’ as AFs though : they should synapse onto the smallest dendrites of PuCs (PF synapses have been spotted on these terminal dendrites).

[52] (Huo Lu et al. 2009)

"The results confirmed that there are regions of the Purkinje cell dendrite receiving exclusively ascending or parallel fiber synapses and that ascending segment synapses are only found on small-diameter dendrites. In addition, we describe for the first time small-diameter dendritic regions contacted by both types of excitatory synapses".

These PF-PuC synapses should also be of the same nature as AF-PuC synapses, following the same plasticity rules, since only this way can it be assured that DS delivery on the PuCs is as faithful as when done via the direct AF road.

It raises the question what determines the ‘nature’ of a PF-PuC synapse. Is the GrC of which it originates genetically ‘tagged’ ? The fact that several messenger molecules cross the synaptic cleft could mean that the PuC 'checks' what kind of PF it is contacting, with a different plasticity rule being applied dependent on the result.

Another possibility could be that the transmitted signal itself (short high frequency burst or sustained low frequency signal) determines the synapse plasticity rule (and hence also the signal throughput).

[53] (Hawkes 2014)

"On the afferent side Purkinje cell stripes receive mossy fiber pathway input from multiple sources and with very different firing patterns - have pf-PC synapses specialized to accommodate this ?"

[54] (Bidoret 2009)

"We show that bursting activity of PFs is necessary for cerebellar LTD induction. The range of PF frequencies capable of inducing LTD indicates that the system behaves as a high-pass filter with a corner frequency ~ 40 Hz."

"The plasticity rule we describe is physiologically relevant because GCs have been shown to be active in vivo at frequencies ranging from a fraction of a Hertz to >1 kHz. The firing patterns of GCs depend on mossy fiber (MF) input, intrinsic cellular properties and the cellular circuitry of the GCL. MF input to GCs can itself be composed of bursts and the induction of LTP at MF-GC synapses is able to increase the frequency of GC bursts. In addition, the inhibition provided by Golgi cells may shape the relationship between MF input and GC output. In this way, GCL activity may define which inputs may be subject to plasticity at the next synaptic relay."

...

The PuC decorrelation process requires synapse-specific plasticity at the synapses which get input from A-path conveying PFs, but heterogeneous plasticity might find a reason for existence in the formation of synapses between DS conveying PFs and PuCs.

[55] (Broussard 2013)

"One might think that completely specific, spine-based learning, based on these local increases in calcium, would be optimal. However, it turns out that LTD can spread to neighboring synapses, presumably located on other spines. Cerebellar LTD does not even occur at isolated synapses; instead, there must be interaction among synapses in a group. This is accomplished by more widely diffusible messengers, at least two of which cross the synaptic cleft. LTD requires some back-and-forth communication between neurons, analogous to a conversation. This conversation is mediated by at least four substances in the extracellular space: glutamate, gamma-amino-butyric acid (GABA), one or more endocannabinoids, and the gas nitric oxide (NO)."

Note : I doubt that LTD 'does not even occur at isolated synapses', but 'spreading LTD' – or LTP for that matter - might be useful in determining which DS-carrying PFs are allowed or not to connect to a PuC : cfr the observation of [49] (Valera et al. 2016) above and below that PFs may target PuCs of a specific microzone while skipping others.

Heterogeneous plasticity makes only sense if neighbouring synapses from different PFs are somehow related. It would imply that 'related' PFs (e.g. carrying a same DS) are spatially arranged 'to stay close together' and that 'non-related' PFs 'stay out of the way' of the messenger diffusion range. I find that very difficult to accept. The only way out of this impasse is to postulate that synapses/PFs 'recognize their own kind' chemically so that the 'messenger' will only target these synapses and ignore others. See also hereafter.

While A-paths are to be broadcasted to PuCs by PFs as far as they can extend, the DS on DS-PFs might only be intended for PuCs in elected patches. This specificity of delivery would imply that DS-PFs only make synapses on specific PuC groups, ignoring others.

[49] (Valera et al. 2016)

"These findings suggest that neighboring PCs make powerful connections with a specific set of distant microzones while ignoring others."
(Note : The formulation is a bit awkward : it is meant that the PFs originating in one place may not only affect the local PuCs but also other PuCs in more distant zones, while skipping intermediate zones).

[56] (Consalez et al. 2013)

"A subtler question is whether they (PFs) synapse with all the PC dendritic arbors that they pass through. This issue has not been studied experimentally. One scenario is that parallel fibers have a primary function to distribute MF afferent input widely across multiple neighboring stripes, in which case they might be expected to synapse promiscuously with all stripes they encounter, at least initially. How that input is used is another matter. One possibility is that PFs synapse with every PC they intersect but only a subset of those synapses is active: in one study, a large fraction of parallel fiber-PC synapses were found to be silent (Brunel et al., 2004), so sculpting in this fashion is entirely plausible."

It has been observed that MLIs (and not PuCs) may be the specific targets of PFs.

[49] (Valera et al. 2016)

"Strikingly, some hotspots did not overlap perfectly with patches of GCs that elicit strong inputs in PCs from cluster 1, indicating that for PCs and MLIs located in the same area, different groups of GC inputs can be selected. These findings suggest that GCs can relay MF information to PCs through two distinct pathways, the MF-GC-PC and MF-GC-MLI-PC pathways."

"The GC connectivity map onto MLIs suggests that PCs can be potentially inhibited by GCs from specific locations. Indeed, several studies demonstrated that feedforward inhibition participates in controlling the firing rate of PCs in individual microzones (Dizon and Khodakhah, 2011; Santamaria et al., 2007) and prevents the activation of distant PCs."

Such connections might in first order be genetically programmed (implying the use of marker molecules) but might in second order also become modifiable when activity calls for it.

[49] (Valera et al. 2016)

"Our data revealed that :

- (1) clusters of neighboring PCs share common rules for the selection of GC inputs and
- (2) PFs communicate MF information over a long distance in the cerebellar cortex linking cerebellar microzones through GC-PC and GC-MLI synapses while GC-GoC synapses appear mostly restricted to intra-microzonal communication.
- (3) Furthermore, we demonstrated that spatial patterns of connectivity are predictable and consistent between animals, suggesting that specific sets of cerebellar functional microzones are reproducibly combined together following similar operational rules.
(My underscore)
- (4) Finally, the functional synaptic organization of GC inputs to PCs and MLIs and GoCs does not strictly respect anatomical and neurochemical boundaries."

"Because similar patterns of GC inputs to PCs, GoCs and MLIs were found in the different animals tested, a major issue was to assess whether this organization was the result of a genetically encoded developmental program or if it could be modified by activity. We demonstrated that PF stimulation could induce either LTD at individual sites (Hartell, 1996) or LTP at individual sites (Coesmans et al., 2004) indicating that activity-dependent processes can tune GC input maps."

"Our results clearly demonstrate that the heterogeneity of the spatial map is an active process. These results are in agreement with previous in vivo studies (Jörntell and Ekerot, 2002; Schonewille et al., 2010; Gao et al., 2012; Badura et al., 2013), suggesting that distant microzones are associated through PFs by LTP mechanisms. LTP could favor information transfer between a set of GCs from one microzone and a group of PCs from another microzone. Conversely, LTD, which is physiologically induced by the conjunction of PF and CF inputs to PCs, could limit the communication between these microzones."

It hardly needs 'chemotaxis' to have a DS-PF find its target PuCs (or MLIs) : the PFs are already in place and a chemical 'conversation' between DS-PFs and PuCs (or MLIs) can suffice to decide about establishing contact or not (and the signal nature might have a say in it too).

In any case, all these observations suggest that a lot of 'ruling' might be at work to diversify the functioning of a seemingly repeated anatomical pattern in the cerebellum.

...

Maybe 'ruling' allows also to consider 'hybrid patches'.

Could a patch have DS-GrCs and GS-GrCs intermingled ? Random connectivity would result in such intermingling, but at the cost of having a lot of 'intermediate' GrC input patterns, unless two different MF dependent connectivity rules could be enforced without mutual conflict in such a mixed GrC population.

Another possibility would be that GrCs themselves can accommodate DS as well as GS inputs (requiring more dendrites, and modality specific GoCs to monitor which inputs are open or closed) : it looks quite complicated

A variant solution consists in having the 'horizontal' segregation of DS and GS patches being replaced by a 'vertical' one, meaning that the GrL is 'layered' , e.g. the deeper parts of the GrL contain the GrCs that process the DS and the superficial parts contain the GrCs that process GSs - or vice versa.

[46] (Jörntell et al. 2006)

"In addition to the microzonal organization described previously for mossy fiber terminals, we now found that granule cells also had a specific depth distribution depending on the type of input they received. These observations suggest a detailed topographical organization within the three-dimensional space of the granule layer that further argues against a convergence of different types of mossy fiber inputs in granule cells."

[57] (Cerminara et al. 2015)

"Mossy fibres originating from the spinal cord versus the basal pontine nucleus have been shown to synapse with superficial and deep granule cells respectively."

This solution would provide overlying PuCs with a GS as well as with a DS, but leaves the question of unused PFs unless they still are used to send a DS also elsewhere.

...

In whatever form, having a functionally 'mixed' GrL substrate (processing DSs as well as GSs) offers an explanation for the diversity of signalling observed in the GrL, and having different PF types surely is complicating for the interpretation of research based on MoL PF stimulation.

...

A word about the conduction speed differences between PFs : it will have a scrambling effect on the original sequencing in A-paths but that is of no consequence : what matters is that there is timing diversity, and each individual PuC works with the sequence it receives.

Fig. 6 from [50] (Bower 2010)

[50] (Bower 2010)

"With respect to parallel fiber desynchronization, it has been known for a long time that parallel fibers are quite variable in their conduction velocities (Eccles et al., 1966). However, in addition, the structure of the molecular layer itself would seem to assure a more desynchronized parallel fiber volley down the molecular layer. Specifically, action potentials initiated in parallel fiber volley down the folium must first traverse the entire height of the molecular layer before reaching the parallel fiber branch point, while action potentials in deeper parallel fibers start propagating almost immediately. Thus the geometry of the cortex itself appears to contribute to the desynchronization of parallel fibers."

"Interestingly, this initial desynchronization due to the branching pattern geometry of granule cell axons in the molecular layer appears to be further enhanced by the fact that the intrinsic conduction velocities of deeper parallel fibers can be twice as fast as those found more superficial in the molecular layer (Vranesic et al., 1994)."

The signal quality of a DS (conveyed in parallel over a population of DS-PFs) – however - might suffer from it (although see [58] Rokni et al. 2008) and therefore the DS-PFs better should target PuCs or MLIs relatively close by to avoid time-dispersion - unless its modulation in time is not important.

[58] (Rokni et al. 2008)

"As the basic rhythm of the motor system runs around the 10 Hz frequency, the delay along the parallel fibers cannot play an important role for any practical purposes. The activation of Purkinje cells along the parallel fibers is almost synchronous from the point of view of motor performance."

...

CONCLUSION

The memory addressing system that can link specific PF-PuC synapses to specific timeslices or to specific 'states of the body' (implemented by the combinatorial use of 'digitized' GSs by GrCs), is a 'processing device' that needs a DS to process.

As the ELL, the cerebellum is equipped with comparable 'infrastructure' (GrL, PFs) 'inviting' DS input, but while in the ELL the DS input route is obvious, in the cerebellum it is not, and AFs – not CFs - came into focus as the most plausible route to bring in an information-rich DS.

In the GrL however, the connectivity requirements for handling a DS (unimodal redundant) and GSs (multimodal, non-redundant) are conflicting.

In places it seems as if the GrL simply solves the problem by having DS and GS patches spatially separated, each patch 'type' endowed with the appropriate connectivity ruling.

With A-paths conveyed over the PFs, DS patches can function as DS decorrelators, but the continuation of the local AFs into PFs seems to serve no purpose since DS-patches do not generate an A-path themselves.

GS patches however lack a DS to process unless it is assumed that a DS also can be conveyed over PFs, and that is what PFs emanating from DS patches might be doing. Such DS-PFs though should stick to AF policy : synapsing onto the small PuC dendrite terminals, relaying the DS unchanged. The signal itself (low/high frequency) might determine the plasticity rule at the PF-PuC synapse and hence also how the signal is processed through it.

Many 'weird' observations seem to plead for PFs with differential roles and also suggest that there is a lot of genetical programming as to which PuCs or MLIs are to be targeted, with dynamical adaptations not to be excluded.

If connectivity ruling can be so powerful then we can also envisage mixed 'hybrid' GrC patches, which combine the functions of DS and GS patches : it could be done by 'vertical separation' (different GrC types in different GrL depths) or by the use of specific marker molecules by the MFs to recognize 'friend or foe', overriding all tendency to random connectivity (remember the topological and chemical separation discussed in the 'Connectivity' section). In the extreme a same GrC might handle DS as well as GS input if modality specific GoCs govern which inputs are to be functional at a given time.

Spine-specific plasticity is mandatory for A-path activated PF-PuC synapses which are to build a 'negative image'. It is not necessary for DS carrying PFs if they are to form synapses on their targets dynamically : it might be an explanation for the presence of heterogeneous plasticity.

PF conduction velocity differences are of no consequence for the purpose of A-paths, but may degrade DS quality if transmitted over longer distances.

...

H) FROM MGC TO PUC

Abbreviations used in this section :

AF	Ascending fiber	ILF	The input load factor
APFV	The activated parallel fiber volume	ILF-VP	The ILF variability problem
AS	The activating signal : the output signal of a GrC that activates a PF-PuC synapse	IO	Inferior olive
ASS	Activating signal strength	JLN	Juxtalobar nucleus
B-spike	Broad spike	LFuC	Large fusiform cell
BIE	The backpropagating integration effect	LGC	Large ganglion cell
CF	Climbing fiber	LTD	Long term depression
DS	The signal to be decorrelated - later also : the driving signal	LTP	Long term potentiation
	aDS The actual DS	MGC	Medium ganglion cell
EGp	The eminentia granularis posterior in the ELL	MLI	Molecular layer interneuron
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	PEN	Preeminential nucleus
EPSP	Excitatory postsynaptic potential	PF	Parallel fiber
FBI	Feedback inhibition	PuC	Purkinje cell
FFI	Feedforward inhibition	RTL	The relevant timelapse
GoC	Golgi cell	SS	Synapse strength
GrC	Granule cell	StC	Stellate cell
GrL	Granular layer	TDFS	Traffic density fluctuation signal
iBCM	The inverted Bienenstock-Cooper-Munro rule	UC	The uncorrelated component
		VP	Variability problem

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

In Part 1 it was demonstrated how devastating 'Input Load Variability' can be for decorrelation (cfr the relevant section). It is a factor which most (if not all) simulation studies on the subject seem to ignore.

It was suggested that the B-spike phenomenon in the MGCs of the ELL implements a 'backpropagating integration effect' [BIE] that solves this variability problem [VP].

Recapitulating concisely : the 'Input Load Factor [ILF]' consists of two components :

The 'local' ILF takes into account that the AS can differ in strength across GrCs (and hence at PF-PuC synapses).

The 'global' ILF takes into account that the amount of activated PF-PuC synapses can differ across timeslices.

The BIE is the phenomenon that the algebraic summing of all inputs at the soma of the MGC cells in the ELL, the result of which is 'backpropagated' by the B-spike to the plasticity sites in the dendrites, determines plasticity direction while compensating for these two types of input variability by adjusting the synapse strengths [SSs] accordingly.

The BIE however solves the ILF-VP only for correlated activity and it implies that LTD as well as LTP must be B-spike associated (non-associative P escaping its effect).

The question arising now is if the cerebellar PuC – lacking a B-spike – can solve the ILF-VP too.

...

In PuCs, it is suggested that the DS is not delivered via basilar dendrites as in the MGCs, but straight to the apical dendrites by way of the AFs. There is no foregoing summing of the DS with the total 'apical output' at the soma, and there is anyway no B-spike to feed back the result of this summing to the dendrites, so it precludes the local ILF-VP to be dealt with as in the MGCs.

Without the summation effect at the soma the local sites also cannot receive information of 'parallel synapses' being active in other regions of the dendritic tree and that precludes the global ILF-VP to be dealt with as in the MGCs.

...

We can of course fall back on the GrL to keep ILF variability in bounds.

GoC FFI cuts short the GrC burst, but a variability of 1 to 3 spikes remains.

Citing from Part 1 :

"Spikes of the AS can be treated more or less as 'signals with unity value', but when they arrive in bursts at the PF-PuC synapse they certainly cause a 'variability problem' [VP] if a time-window mechanism that allows for integration of more than one spike is at play at the postsynaptic side."

[59] (D'Angelo et al. 2013)

"Once a burst is conveyed through the mossy fibers, it simultaneously activates the granule cells and the Golgi cells, thus engaging the feedforward inhibitory loop. The effect is to inhibit granule cell firing after an interval corresponding to the sum of transmission and excitation delays along the mossy fiber Golgi cell-granule cell pathway. The permissive "time window" lasts about 4–5ms, so that granule cells have time to fire just 1–3 spikes (D'Angelo and De Zeeuw, 2009)."

GoC FBI can keep variations in activated PF numbers between close limits, maybe even better than the EGp in the ELL could do it.

[60] (De Schutter et al. 2001)

"In these theories the inhibitory Golgi cells control the activation threshold of granule cells, thereby keeping the number of active parallel fibers relatively small and constant over large variations in the number of active mossy fibers (Marr, 1969) . This control over the number of active parallel fibers enhances the performance of the perceptron learning rule. Albus (1971) used the word "automatic gain control" to describe the role of the feedback inhibition by Golgi cells. Overall this would restrain the number of active parallel fibers contacting a single Purkinje cell to 1 % (Albus, 1971) or 0.3 to 6 % (Marr, 1969) ."

...

Could the PuC nonetheless compensate for the effects itself ?

Might the Ca⁺⁺ surges caused by CF firing lend themselves to implement a BIE by intracellular feedback as the B-spike did in the MGCs ?

I leave it to the specialists to consider if a (partial ?) summation can take place in the PuC (if not at the soma, then maybe at the base of dendritic branches) by an integration of PuC membrane potential (affected by AFs and PFs) with CF depolarization, the result of which might be backpropagated by axial currents until in the distal dendrites (where plasticity will be triggered and 'directed' by the ensuing Ca⁺⁺ levels).

[61] (Rokni et al. 2008)

"Each Purkinje cell is innervated by a single climbing fiber that establishes multiple synaptic contacts with the lower two-thirds of its dendrite."

[62] (Zang et al. 2019)

"Climbing fibers directly excite and depolarize proximal smooth dendrites (Palay and Chan-Palay, 1974; Roth and Häusser, 2001; Zang et al., 2018), but not distal spiny parts. The axial current from the depolarization of proximal parts constitutes the sole current source to depolarize distal parts and to reach the activation threshold of P-type Ca²⁺ channels."

I fail to see an intracellular feedback here : can expert knowledge on membrane properties and ion channels be of help ?

...

Might PuC output be used to implement a BIE by 'extracellular feedback' ?

I stumbled on one (and only ?) study claiming that PuC collaterals also contact GrCs (where exactly ?), which would create an opportunity for PuCs to use their global output to 'tune down' a DS coming up by the AFs, to compensate for a too strong AS at the PF input (in a DS processing patch). It should be able to follow ASS-variability very closely though.

[63] (Guo et al. 2016)

"We show that Purkinje cells, the sole output neurons of the cerebellar cortex, also directly inhibit granule cells via their axon collaterals. Anatomical and optogenetic studies indicate that this non-canonical feedback is region specific: it is most prominent in lobules that regulate eye movement and process vestibular information."

"PC collaterals are known to form functional synapses onto PCs and most interneurons, with the exception of GoCs (Hirono et al., 2012; Watt et al., 2009; Witter et al., 2016). Here we investigate the existence of a direct feedback from the output to the input layer in the cerebellum via the collateral axons. We discovered that PCs make functional synapses onto GrCs, allowing PCs to provide fast, slow, and tonic inhibition. The prevalence of the PC to GrC synapse is highly heterogeneous between different regions of the cerebellar cortex, suggesting that it serves specialized functions in specific cerebellar behaviors."

[64] (De Schutter et al. 1994B)

"Purkinje cells do not directly influence the synaptic input they receive through feedback excitation or inhibition on a short time scale (i.e., from within the cerebellum itself) except by the very sparse Purkinje axon collaterals that are inhibitory (Bishop 1988; Ito 1984)."

...

There is another essential difference between MGCs and PuCs : in MGCs the B-spike is a 'transform' that faithfully reflects the membrane potential at the MGC soma (which the DS co-determines), while the CF generates a Ca⁺⁺ surge which is in the first place under the control of the inferior olive [IO]. This Ca⁺⁺ surge can be modulated though by the AF and PF inputs at the plasticity sites.

[65] (Najafi et al. 2013)

"What is important about the CF-triggered dendritic calcium signal from a neural coding perspective is that just like the evoked EPSP, its amplitude can be modulated in vitro (Miyakawa et al., 1992; Midtgaard et al., 1993; Callaway et al., 1995; Wang et al., 2000) and in vivo (Kitamura and Hausser, 2011) by a variety of factors that influence the membrane potential of the Purkinje cell."

"Dendritic calcium influx is significantly enhanced if the CF input is preceded by stimulation of the excitatory PF pathway (Wang et al., 2000), which by itself causes a small graded calcium response via activation of voltage-gated calcium channels as well as metabotropic receptor dependent release from intracellular stores (Eilers et al., 1995; Takechi et al., 1998)."

CF firing is necessary for plasticity to occur, but for decorrelation purposes the AF+PF integration is to determine the plasticity direction, not the IO input.

Already at the start of Part 1 it was argued that - for decorrelation - the 'teaching' role of the CFs is not needed, but if CF firing nonetheless is needed to 'enable' plasticity, it implies that this CF activity is not to corrupt the decorrelation process by imposing LTD (or LTP for that matter with a bidirectional iBCM).

Hence, I have to 'postulate' that there is a 'neutral' form of CF firing, and I will even call it 'standard' as I see it as the regular 'background' firing done by the IO.

Defined more explicitly : in a context where a 'Ca-threshold' determines the difference between LTP and LTD, CF firing is 'standard' when it causes a Ca⁺⁺ surge tuned (on average) to be level with this Ca-threshold, and hence the actual direction of plasticity will depend on the (algebraic) additions of PF, AF and StC input of the moment, causing ups and downs in the Ca⁺⁺ surge.

...

Standard CF firing - so defined - allows plasticity, but 'takes no side', and so it is ignored in the plasticity formula of the demo program.

Under these conditions [66] (Gilbert 1993) is no worry any more, and 'standard' complex spikes may keep occurring since - unlike B-spikes - they have no modulatory influence on plasticity here, but - like B-spikes - they do not need to occur 'at every timeslice during an iteration', as long as, over time, the whole RTL is covered.

[66] (Gilbert 1993)

"What is the consequence of the random firing of the climbing fibres in the unanaesthetized animal at a rate of one to two per second ? These random climbing fibre inputs should also cause efficacy changes at parallel fibre synapses on Purkinje cells that would eventually swamp out those involved in the learning of movements."

When CF firing is called 'non-standard' it will mean that CFs fire so vigorously that they cause a larger than 'standard' Ca⁺⁺ surge, thereby rendering the PF, AF and StC input components irrelevant by grossly overriding them.

Like B-spikes, complex spikes are to be considered 'loud noise', when it comes to 'listening' to the weak UC that is being filtered out.

Low frequency CF firing is necessary though to maintain the averaging process, and without it, plasticity would 'freeze'.

...

In PuCs the AFs relieve the CFs of the DS information task and although I certainly believe that CFs are able to carry some information ([65] (Najafi et al. 2013)), I think that here (for decorrelating) they don't and even shouldn't.

[65] (Najafi et al. 2013)

"It is known that the processes underlying spike generation and dendritic depolarization are both influenced by a variety of actors, including the resting potential of the inferior olivary neuron (Llinas and Yarom, 1981; Ruigrok and Voogd, 1995). This opens up the possibility that information maybe transmitted by modulating the number of spikes in the CF burst. Indeed, the era of the "all-or-nothing" CF maybe coming to an end. Recent studies have shown that the burstsize, i.e., the number of spikes in the CF burst, is tightly regulated and provides extra information not available in the conventional binary signal (Maruta et al., 2007; Mathy et al., 2009; Bazzigaluppi et al., 2012; De Gruijl et al.)"

"It has been shown that the number of spikes in the CF burst varies systematically according to the phase of the oscillation in vitro (Mathy et al., 2009), the amplitude of the oscillation in vivo (Bazzigaluppi et al., 2012), and the extent of electrotonic coupling and synchrony in a computer model of the olivary network (De Gruijl et al., 2012). In addition, burstsize can be used to distinguish between spontaneous and sensory-related CF signals evoked by sinusoidal whole-field visual stimulation (Maruta et al., 2007). This last study also found that the number of spikes in the CF burst varied systematically depending on the direction of the visual stimulus."

The forceful Ca⁺⁺ surge generated by CF firing is needed to enable plasticity (justifying their constant although low frequency firing). Concerted PF activity can also produce a Ca⁺⁺ surge which – if strong enough can cause a complex spike. Probably this is an extreme situation not occurring in vivo, but it clearly demonstrates that algebraic summing of Ca⁺⁺ surges caused by CFs and PFs can make quite a difference for the direction of plasticity.

[67] (Mapelli et al. 2015)

"Other mechanisms could amplify local Ca₂C signals and allow LTD induction, as somatic depolarization (Linden et al., 1991) or strong PFs activation (Hartell, 1996; Eilers et al., 1997). Indeed, the simultaneous activation of several PFs stimulated at 1Hz, at relatively high stimulus intensity, may generate postsynaptic Ca₂C transients that remain confined to spines (Midtgaard et al., 1993; Denk et al., 1995), reaching the levels for the LTD induction (Hartell, 1996). However, when the CFs are stimulated a lower stimulus strength is sufficient for LTD induction (Han et al., 2007). Therefore, although it is clear that CF activity facilitates PF-PC LTD, CF involvement is not strictly required (Ohtsuki et al., 2009)."

[68] (D'Angelo 2014)

"The effect of climbing fiber pairing can be substituted by postsynaptic depolarization suggesting that depolarization normally attributed to climbing fibers could be replaced by simultaneous activation of a few tens of parallel fibers. Indeed, simultaneous activation of several parallel fibers generates a postsynaptic calcium transient confined into the spines, whose amplitude increases with the number of active parallel fibers reaching levels similar to those produced in the same region by climbing fiber activation (Midtgaard et al., 1993; Denk et al., 1995). As result, 1-Hz parallel fiber stimulation at relatively high stimulus strength (either single pulses or brief 10-50 Hz bursts) produces a gradual summation of the calcium signal leading to LTD (Hartell 1996). In addition LTD can be induced by intense parallel fiber stimulation. Therefore, climbing fiber pairing may not be an essential requisite but rather a facilitatory and synchronizing factor."

...

The BIE – in the ELL - cannot compensate for the fluctuations in UNcorrelated PF traffic 'passing by' (the TDFS) and hence, for PuCs too, we have to ask : are there TDFS sensors in the cerebellum ? All cell types sampling PFs must be examined.

I rule out GoCs since they 'sample' much more than that and have only very indirect influence on PuCs (I do not follow the view that they communicate with MLIs, cfr the 'conflicting evidence' (again I clearly vote for Hull and Regehr)).

[69] (Jörntell et al. 2010)

"The axons of the interneurons form inhibitory synapses onto PCs and other interneurons, including Golgi cells."

[59] (D'Angelo et al. 2013)

"Golgi cells have also been reported to receive inhibitory innervations from stellate/basket cells and Lugaro cells (Sotelo and Llinas, 1972) ."

"The inhibitory inputs to Golgi cells are GABAergic or glycinergic. Pure GABAergic inputs have been suggested to come from stellate and basket cells, and mixed GABAergic glycinergic inputs from Lugaro cells (Dumoulin et al., 2001)."

"Much less is known about inhibitory connections. Each Golgi cell receives inhibitory input from several dozen molecular layer inhibitory interneurons (stellate cells and Basket cells) (Dumoulin et al., 2001) and from other Golgi cells (Hull and Regehr, 2012). Moreover Golgi cell dendrites are coupled through gap junctions (Vervaeke et al., 2010) and may also be connected with molecular layer interneurons in the same way (Sotelo and Llinas, 1972) ."

"Evidence was recently provided indicating that GABAergic Golgi cells are inhibited by other Golgi cells rather than by molecular layer interneurons (Hull and Regehr, 2012). This report is somewhat controversial, however, in that in vivo electrophysiological recordings have

clearly shown Golgi cell inhibition to be the consequence of a disinaptic pathway passing through granule cells and molecular layer interneurons (Eccles et al., 1967) . The reason for this discrepancy remains to be determined."

[70] (Hull et al. 2012)

"Here, we overturn this view by revealing that Golgi cells make inhibitory GABAergic synapses onto each other and do not receive either inhibitory synapses or electrical connections from MLIs."

I rule out the stellate cells since they are subject to plastic adaptation in parallel with (A-path carrying) PF-PuC synapses (and 'uniform' or 'democratic' apical SS was a condition for LFuCs in the ELL to function as TDFS annullers).

The candelabrum cells may be candidates but clearly there is still too much uncertainty about their connectivity (Ambrosi in 2007 seems surer than Schilling in 2008). Recently in 2022, Osorno gave more detail.

[71] (Schilling et al. 2008)

"Candelabrum cell perikarya are located within the ganglionic (Purkinje) cell layer, and they are usually elongated along the vertical axis. Typically, these cells have one or two long, rarely branched dendrites, which ascend almost vertically into the molecular layer, and several (3-5) short dendrites which project into the granule cell layer, where they run preferentially in the horizontal plane."

"Both types of dendrites are covered with spines. The candelabrum cell axon projects into the molecular layer, where it runs horizontally and emits multiple beaded branches, which ascend vertically through most of the molecular layer, where they are preferentially arranged in parasagittal planes. This axonal plexus may either occupy a territory that essentially overlaps with the area occupied by the same cell's ascending dendrites, or be displaced laterally some variable distance. Candelabrum cells are distributed throughout all parts of the cerebellar cortex at apparently roughly equal density ."

"While the dendritic structure of candelabrum cells suggest that parallel fibers, ascending granule cell axons, but also basket/stellate cells and climbing fibers may provide afferent input to them, their afferents have so far not been identified. The same holds for its target(s), although the axonal structure makes Purkinje cell dendrites (and those of basket/stellate cells) likely targets. Current evidence concurs to indicate that candelabrum cells use GABA and glycine as transmitters."

[72] (Ambrosi et al. 2007)

"The Candelabrum neurons forms a row that joins up with that of Purkinje neuron bodies. From the external body pole, dendrite trunks originate, that ascend through the molecular layer and arborize there in a candelabrum-like fashion, as well as a thin axon that also spreads in the molecular layer. Moreover, basal dendrites originate from the internal body pole and ramify in the GL. The CN receives inputs from axon recurrent collaterals of Purkinje neurons and from granule and basket neuron axons. Its axon forms synapses upon basket and stellate neurons, but not upon Purkinje neuron dendrites."

[73] (Osorno et al. 2022)

"CCs can exert a large influence on PC excitability, and can be thought of as master regulators of PC excitability that are privy to input, output and intrinsic activity. We have shown that a single CC can dramatically alter the inhibition that PCs receive from MLIs, with up to a 60% reduction of inhibitory charge. EM reconstructions confirmed the physiology experiments, but also revealed that CCs inhibit the majority of nearby MLIs. GCs and MFs promote CC firing, reduce MLI firing and disinhibit PCs. This is countered by the activity of PCs themselves, which will have the opposite effect. When PC firing is elevated, it will decrease the firing of CCs that in turn increases the firing of MLIs, thereby resulting in negative feedback to the PC that counteracts the increase in CC firing."

Both LFuCs and candelabrum cells sample PF input at apical dendrites and merge their output with the principal cell : in the ELL the MGCs inhibit excitatory LFuCs, in the cerebellum the candelabrum cells disinhibit inhibitory PuCs via the MLIs. If it implements an 'antiphase annulling technique' however is not evident.

...

Assuming that the ILF-VP and the TDFS can be dealt with in some way (it should, since 'stability' is important in any PuC model), then, in analogy with the ELL, PuCs can be conceived to implement decorrelation too.

The program code used for the ELL (see Part 1, the sections on signal lifting) can be reused for the cerebellum if we remove the B-spike requirements, keep the iBCM rule and use a non-inverted DS :

```
tsMax=250                                && let's cover the 250 timeslices of the DS
icMax=250                                && let's execute 250 iterations to obtain decorrelation
FOR ic = 1 TO icMax                       && ic = Iteration counter
  FOR ts = 1 TO tsMax                     && ts = Timeslice counter
    ABsum = SS ( ic , ts ) * ILF(ts) + DS ( ic , ts ) && the result of 'algebraic summing' of PF and AF input at the plasticity site
    && PF input AF input ILF = Input Load Factor (specific for every GrC)
    && The iBCM rule
    IF ABsum < Ca_threshold
      SSchange = ( Ca_threshold - ABsum ) * P% && SS = synapse strength
    ELSE
      SSchange = ( Ca_threshold - ABsum ) * D%
    ENDIF
    SS ( ic , ts ) = MAX ( 0 , SS ( ic , ts ) + SSchange ) && SS cannot be < 0
  ENDFOR
ENDFOR
```

Cfr Fig. 7

Videolink : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/a4xnsn1ew9zqwpv/demo-1-80.mp4?dl=0>

Fig. 7

Keep in mind the purposes of these demos : although it is called 'PuC simulation' they are in no way meant to be real simulations !

[68] (D'Angelo 2014)

"It has been shown that these forms of LTP and LTD are mutually reversible (Coemans et al., 2004; Lev-Ram et al., 2003) . The postsynaptic Ca²⁺ transient plays an important role in determining the direction of plasticity at parallel fiber - Purkinje cell synapse."

"The model of different Ca²⁺ thresholds for bidirectional plasticity was proposed in 1982 (Bienenstock et al., 1982) and termed "BCM rule". According to the BCM rule, lower and higher Ca²⁺ transients are associated with the induction of LTD and LTP respectively. In parallel fiber-Purkinje cell synapses there is an opposite scenario and lower and higher Ca²⁺ transients are associated with the induction of LTP and LTD respectively."

The Ca-threshold here was set at 42 and it gives an excellent result, but in fact - when this threshold is altered - we encounter the same effects as when the limits of 'lifting' by the JLN in the ELL were explored (see Part 1).

Again, to see clearly why, we have to keep S2 flat (no UC) while adjusting the Ca-threshold to 21 for the loss of the excitatory input by S2 - cfr Fig. 8a.

When set lower (e.g. at 11) we get Fig. 8b in which we see the apexes of S3 transgress the Ca-threshold, causing LTD on synapses that are already at a minimum ('S4 touching bottom'), preventing decorrelation on these signal fractions.

And when set higher (e.g. 31) we get Fig. 8c, showing that it causes a 'lift' of S4, which is not deleterious for decorrelation, but is inefficient concerning energy and synapse economy.

Fig. 8

Videolinks : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/ynzrdapjxvdgmb8/demo-1-81.mp4?dl=0>
<https://www.dropbox.com/s/wdqxahytrhg2ohl/demo-1-82.mp4?dl=0>
<https://www.dropbox.com/s/eiot4onfilbwude/demo-1-83.mp4?dl=0>

Hence, when CFs are to be 'plasticity neutral', calibration is necessary.

In the ELL, the solution consisted in lifting the input signal strength by EPSP injection to an optimum level relative to the B-spike threshold by the JLN and in shifting the B-spike threshold by targeted inhibition by the PEN.

The IO can control CF firing burst vigour, but I think it more plausible that the IO continuously delivers the 'standard' CF firing, unless it really wants to 'intervene' or 'overrule' in the guiding of plasticity for reasons of its own.

[65] (Najafi et al. 2013)

"It appears that at least in some motor learning tasks, CFs are activated in a manner that is compatible with their presumed role as "teachers" (Gilbert and Thach, 1977; Raymond et al., 1996; Simpson et al., 1996; Kitazawa et al., 1998; Raymond and Lisberger, 1998; Ito, 2006, 2013; Medina and Lisberger, 2008; Rasmussen et al., 2008; Soetedjo et al., 2008)."

In the cerebellum I assume that the Ca⁺⁺ surge is calibrated by plasticity changes at the CF-PuC synapses, maybe by direct intracellular feedback in the PuC by the Ca⁺⁺ surge itself.

[67] (Mapelli et al. 2015)

"Plasticity at the CF-PC Synapse : The reduction in complex spike-associate Ca^{2C} transients following the CF-LTD is sufficiently strong to reverse the polarity of postsynaptic plasticity at the PF-PC relay."

[68] (D'Angelo 2014)

"For long time the climbing fiber to Purkinje cell synapse was considered to fire a large all-or nothing action potential independent of strength of climbing fiber stimulation. However, the climbing fiber synapse can also undergo plastic changes (Hansel & Linden, 2000) . Climbing fiber-LTD was induced by a short tetanization of climbing fibers causing a reduction of the slow component of the complex spike. The climbing fiber LTD also results in change in afterhyperpolarization (AHP), which can prolong the complex spike pause. Interestingly, the changes induced in calcium transients following climbing fiber-LTD can affect the induction of both postsynaptically expressed LTD and LTP at the parallel fiber to Purkinje cell synapse (Coemans et al., 2004) . Thus the climbing fiber - Purkinje cell synapse can exert a complex regulatory role on long-term synaptic plasticity and dendritic integration changing the spike output of the Purkinje cell (Ohtsuki, 2009) ."

...

CONCLUSION

PuCs, as MGCs, can be conceived to be decorrelators too, but with implementation differences.

Having the DS information delivered straight at the dendrites by AFs has several consequences : CFs, like B-spikes, provide 'lift' for the plasticity inducing Ca⁺⁺ surge (the CF strategy is more appropriate for the huge PuCs), but they do not have to transmit DS-related info anymore.

With integration no more done at the soma, adjustment of SSs for ILF variability might be lost. GoC FFI surely already enforces an upper limit to the ILF. Might CF-caused axonal currents which reach the terminal dendrites be a means to improve on it ? I'm not convinced and invite the specialists to evaluate the situation. Maybe GoC FBI in the GrL can constrain APFV within tolerable limits. Maybe PuCs themselves can implement a feedback loop of their output via axonal collaterals onto the GrCs in their own (DS) patch. I fear it remain open questions as to how the two components of a potential ILF-VP are to be solved in the cerebellum. I hope it is recognised that the ILF-VP is real and deserves a solution.

Same for the TDFS - which is probably more prominent in the cerebellum than in the ELL - but candelabrum cells - like LFuCs (and LGCs) - might be candidates for annulling it.

While CFs carry no DS but yet are to act as 'enablers' of plasticity ('freezing' the averaging process when they should stop firing), their activity should cause (on average) neither LTD nor LTP.

'Standard' CF firing is defined to act in this 'neutral' way, leaving it to the other contributors to the Ca⁺⁺ surge strength to determine the direction of plasticity, while 'non-standard' CF firing is meant to override these other contributors by enforcing LTD.

In 'standard mode' the IO can maintain regular CF firing without disrupting established plasticity.

A need for Ca⁺⁺ surge calibration is to be expected (analogous to the JLN and PEN regulation of membrane potential and B-spike threshold in the MGC, a Ca⁺⁺ surge has limits to respect), and it is probably implemented at the CF-PuC synapses by some direct intracellular feedback mechanism, instead of the IO itself 'calibrating' its firing.

...

D) MLIs

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path : a chain of sequentially activated synapses	GS	The signal(s) that guide the activation process
AF	Ascending fiber	GrL	Granular layer
APFV	The activated parallel fiber volume	MLI	Molecular layer interneuron
BaC	Basket cell	MoL	Molecular layer
CC	The correlated component	PF	Parallel fiber
iCC	The inverted CC	PuC	Purkinje cell
CN	(Deep) Cerebellar nuclei	StC	Stellate cell
DS	The signal to be decorrelated - later also : the driving signal	TDFS	Traffic density fluctuation signal
iDS	The inverted DS	UC	The uncorrelated component
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	iUC	The inverted UC
		VP	Variability problem

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

Stellate [StC] and basket [BaC] cells respectively occupy the upper and lower regions of the MoL, and they are seen by many as the same cell type, gradually changing appearance and contacting rules with the depth in the MoL (and hence their position relative to the PuC).

[74] (Bower 2010)

"However, our recent quantitative anatomical study of molecular layer interneurons suggests that these cells are, in fact, one homogenous population, whose probability of providing an inhibitory input directly to the soma simply goes up as the soma is deeper in the molecular layer (Sultan and Bower, 1998). Consistent with a single population of neurons, molecular layer interneurons with somas in the middle regions of the molecular layer provide both types of inputs. In this paper we will therefore distinguish between "stellate-like" dendritic and "basket-like" somatic inhibition rather than referring to stellate and basket-type cells."

[75] (Jörntell et al. 2010)

"The cerebellar molecular layer contains two types of GABAergic interneurons - the stellate and basket cells. As with PC dendrites, these interneurons primarily have their dendrites and axons oriented in the sagittal plane. The distinction between the two subtypes of interneurons emanates from early observations that showed that the axons of the deepest-lying interneurons formed dense pericellular nets, shaped like baskets, around the base of the PC soma. These basket-forming cells were believed to be located at the bottom of the molecular layer and/or inside the PC layer. The more superficial stellate cells were believed to form inhibitory synapses with PC dendrites, but not with their somata. Later studies have suggested that the border between the two types of cells is not so distinct; a stellate cell located at middepth in the molecular layer can, for example, send axons that form 'baskets'."

When comparing the opposites in the spectrum, a functional distinction emerges, with StCs taking input from PFs while BaCs take it from AFs, and StCs serving the smaller dendrites while BaCs serve the PuC soma and the main dendrites.

[74] (Bower 2010)

"While on the one hand our anatomical and modeling results suggests that molecular layer interneurons are one population of cells, our models predict that dendritic and somatic inhibition play different functional roles. While all molecular layer neurons receive input from the excitatory granule cell axons (Stell et al., 2007) it is known that these two types of inhibition have distinctly different postsynaptic effects on Purkinje cells. For example, dendritic (stellate-type) inputs have, at best, weak effects on the Purkinje cell soma (Vincent and Marty, 1996) while basket-type inputs are very effective in controlling Purkinje cell somatic spiking (Vincent and Marty, 1996). However, beyond these general descriptions, the functional or computational similarities and differences between these two types of molecular layer inhibition are not well understood (Kreiner and Jaeger, 2004; Barmack and Yakhnitsa, 2008b)."

"As a corollary, we also predict that molecular layer interneurons in the deeper layers of the molecular layer would receive their predominant granule cell synaptic input from ascending granule cell axons, while more superficial molecular layer interneurons would receive a larger proportion of their inputs from parallel fibers. This prediction is consistent with the ratio of these two different types of synapses in the deep and superficial regions of the granule cell layer (Gundappa-Sulur et al., 1999) as well as with the vertically elongated shape of the dendrites of deep molecular layer interneurons (O'Donoghue et al., 1989; Sultan and Bower, 1998; Castejon et al., 2001a,b; Barmack and Yakhnitsa, 2008b)."

[76] (De Schutter et al. 1994b)

"Stellate cell synapses. SYNAPTIC LOCATIONS. Morphological data about stellate cell synapse distributions on Purkinje cell dendrites are incomplete. On the basis of EM data they seem to synapse on both small spiny and thicker dendritic branches (Palay and Chan-Palay 1974) and in general they do not contact the innervation sites of basket cell synapses (ibid), but neither the densities of these synaptic contacts nor their exact sites of termination are known. Because there are more stellate cells than Purkinje cells (Ito 1984) we assumed that stellate cell synapses were present on all the smooth and spiny dendritic compartments."

"Basket cell synapses. SYNAPTIC LOCATIONS. About 30-50 basket cells terminate on each Purkinje cell on the soma and dendritic trunk (Palay and Chan-Palay 1974; Palkovits et al. 1971). Basket cell synaptic receptor channels were placed on the soma and on all compartments of the main dendrite."

A parasagittal section perpendicular upon the PFs shows a greater density of AFs in the lower regions of the MoL, where BaCs are more prominent (and maybe DS-carrying PFs also prefer the lower MoL, better myelinated, less time-dispersion, but shorter).

[77] (Gundappa-Sulur et al. 1999)

"Given the known geometry of granule cell axons, if ascending segment synapses terminate exclusively on Purkinje cell dendrites <1.3 µm in diameter, then one would expect Purkinje cell dendrites in deeper regions of the molecular layer to have a larger percentage of these very small, spiny branchlets than dendrites in superficial layers. This prediction is based on the assumptions that the ascending segments bifurcate into parallel fibers in roughly equal proportion at all horizontal levels of the molecular layer (Palay and Chan-Palay, 1974) and that ascending segment axons make an equal number of synapses along their entire vertical length prior to branching (Pichitpornchai et al., 1994). If both of these assumptions are correct, then there should be many more ascending segment synapses and, thus, more Purkinje cell dendrites <1.3 µm in diameter in deeper than superficial regions of the molecular layer."

"The restriction of ascending segment synapses to the smallest diameter Purkinje cell dendrites results in an increase in small-diameter dendrites in the deeper regions of the molecular layer. We found many more small-diameter dendrites in the lower half of the dendrite than in the upper half."

...

StCs 'cover' a PuC-dendritic-territory (unlike the passing PF with its single synapse), they are interconnected by gap junctions and reciprocal connections, and this precludes any focused signalling onto PuCs as PFs do.

[74] (Bower 2010)

"There is even evidence for electrical synapses between molecular layer interneurons (Sotelo and Llinas, 1972; Mann-Metzer and Yarom, 2000) which could serve to speed or spread the establishment of dendritic inhibition."

StCs could be meant to make an average of the total PF input to the PuC, and deliver it - sign reversed - onto the dendrites where the PF-PuC synapses lie.

Assuming that the plasticity rule for StCs goes parallel with the (A-path carrying) PF-PuC synapses (I-synapses strengthening as E-synapses do), then - with appropriate general gain tuning - the E-load coming from the PFs can be balanced with an equal I-load from StCs (maybe StCs do the same in the ELL).

[74] (Bower 2010)

"It would be entirely consistent with the counterbalancing effect of inhibition proposed here if the same parallel fibers synapsing on a particular Purkinje cell, also activated nearby molecular layer interneurons whose orthogonal axonal project patterns assured a restricted influence on the same Purkinje cell."

"Feed-forward dendritic (stellate-type) inhibition specifically serves to counterbalance parallel fiber excitation in local regions of the Purkinje cell dendrite." (but with gap junctions and reciprocal connections a larger area will be affected with a still more averaged effect)

With a synapse specific addressed excitatory input, and an evenly distributed inhibitory input the net current flow will become zero but locally the signal is still there, oscillating back and forth around zero.

[74] (Bower 2010)

"This in turn, results in no net flow of somatic/ dendritic current following an increase in parallel fiber activity, and therefore no effect of parallel fibers on the intrinsic spiking of the Purkinje cell."

[78] (Schonewille et al. 2010)

"By combining optimally learned levels of potentiated excitation and feed-forward inhibition Purkinje cells are probably equipped with a push-pull mechanism so as to convey and consolidate appropriately formed patterns of spikes and/or pauses that may be read out in the cerebellar nuclei provided that they occur coherently in ensembles of cells (De Zeeuw et al., 2008; Gauck and Jaeger, 2000; Telgkamp and Raman, 2002; Wulff et al., 2009)."

When (in a DS patch by AFs, or in a GS-patch via DS-PFs ?) a DS is coming in, it will be algebraically summed with (or at least be modulated by) the local (A-path)-PF-induced signal. The resulting signal is subsequently going to be amplified by the dendritic booster mechanism demonstrated by De Schutter et al. (an emergent property of his model which I deem to be crucial for the understanding of the cerebellum, while it doesn't get the recognition it deserves). In this way the PuC seems to be conceived to produce output based on the stringing together of sequential and very local (but dispersed) activations in the dendritic tree. It doesn't rule out that a PuC can implement other 'modes of operation'.

[79] (De Schutter et al. 1994c)

"The model predicts that the somatic firing response of Purkinje cells is relatively insensitive to the exact dendritic location of synaptic inputs. We describe a mechanism of Ca²⁺-mediated synaptic amplification, based on the subspiking threshold recruitment of P-type Ca²⁺ channels in the dendritic branches surrounding the input site."

"Because of the dependence of the amplification mechanism on a subspiking threshold recruitment of P channels, it is also gradual and "analog," allowing it to be modulated by the electrotonic structure of the dendritic tree and resulting in an amplification that increases linearly with distance. The more "digital" all-or-none mechanism of dendritic spike generation proposed by others would almost certainly lack this property and therefore reintroduce a dependence on dendritic position and on clustering of synapses."

[80] (Bower 2015)

"Shelton (1985, p 128) , specifically speculated that "active dendritic spikes or active graded potentials may act as a booster mechanism to overcome the electrotonic lengthening of the dendrite due to synaptic activation"."

"Interestingly, this functional difference turns out to actually be manifest in the fine physical structure of the Purkinjecell dendrite itself. Anatomical studies have demonstrated that the synapses associated with the ascending granule cell axon segments are found only on the distal regions of the dendrite (Gundappa-Sulur et al. , 1999; Lu et al. , 2009) , where our network models predict that these synapses will be synchronously active in response to afferent mossy fiber stimuli (Santamaria et al. , 2007) . Our single cell models predict that the active properties of the dendrite mediate a boosting mechanism allowing this distant input to influence somatic spiking (De Schutter and Bower, 1994c) ."

"Anatomical studies have also shown that parallel fiber synapses are found primarily on the more proximal spiny dendrites (Gundappa-Sulur et al. , 1999; Lu et al. , 2009) , where both the network (Santamaria et al. , 2007) and single cell (Jaeger et al. , 1996) models suggest they interact with feedforward inhibition to regulate the activation state of the large dendritic voltage-dependent Ca⁺⁺ and Ca⁺⁺ activated K⁺ conductances. This places parallel fibers in a position to influence or modulate the response of the dendrite to the synchronous ascending segment synapses."

[74] (Bower 2010)

"This influence of parallel fiber excitation and molecular layer inhibition on the dendrite of the Purkinje cell is very different in kind from the "integrate and fire" type functionality that dominates many existing models of Purkinje cell behavior (Medina and Mauk, 2000; Mauk and Ohyama, 2004; Carrillo et al., 2008) . While the local dendritic influence of these two types of synapses could be considered to be a kind of local summing, our previous modeling results have shown that the "firing" of the Purkinje cell is under the secondary influence of the large voltage dependent conductances in the Purkinje cell dendrite and soma (Jaeger and Bower, 1999) and not the result of a simple sum of parallel fiber excitation and molecular layer inhibition."

"Our results, however, suggest the alternate view that parallel fiber inputs are active, but under the control of feed-forward stellate-type molecular layer inhibition and are not intended to drive Purkinje cell output directly."

"Instead of supporting a parallel fiber driven cerebellar learning function (Marr, 1969; Albus, 1971; Mauk and Ohyama, 2004; Ito, 2006; Thompson and Steinmetz, 2009), feed-forward dendritic stellate-type inhibition and parallel fiber excitation together are proposed to regulate the local dynamics of the Purkinje cell dendrite (Jaeger et al., 1997) with the large dendritic Ca and K dendritic currents providing most of the direct influence on Purkinje cell somatic spiking (Deschutter and Bower, 1994c; Sugimori et al., 1994; Jaeger et al., 1997; Womack and Khodakhah, 2003) ."

"It has been pointed out by Mann-Metzer and Yarom (2002) and colleagues that the relatively "jittery" spiking response of molecular layer neurons to synaptic input with a duration that is independent of the strength of that input, is not consistent with a role in precise temporal coding. This behavior is consistent with a modulatory function however."

"This modulatory regulation of the dynamic balance between the large voltage dependent membrane conductances directly influences the response of the Purkinje cell to input from the ascending branch (Santamaria and Bower, 2005) . Specifically, because the synapses of the ascending synapses contact only the smallest spiny branchlets of the Purkinje cell (Gundappa-Sulur et al., 1999; Lu et al., 2009), their voltage effects traverse regions of the dendrite under voltage clamp control of parallel fibers and feed-forward inhibition. We have interpreted this geometrical arrangement to suggest that the local parallel fiber/feed-forward voltage clamp mechanism serves functionally to modulate inputs from the ascending segment axons. Consistent with this prediction, we have shown using simultaneous granule cell layer and Purkinje cell recordings that any single activation of the granule cell layer does not necessarily result in a response from its overlying Purkinje cell (Lu et al., 2005)."

...

Fig. 9

Referring to Fig. 7 again and with decorrelation in mind : the actual generated PuC output signal (purely based on 'apical input' since there is no basilar input here) - after stabilized decorrelation - represents the UC (being DS + iCC), since the 'intact' DS (not a subtraction result as in MGCs) is delivered in the dendrites (came in via the AFs), and it is summed with the local input from the PF-synapses which have adjusted to represent the iCC of the DS, see Fig. 9.

Timeslice by timeslice, by sequential activation of A-path synapses, the DS is transformed into the UC, and each UC time snippet is 'boosted' : this way a very local dendritic signal is empowered to influence a timeslice of PuC simple spike firing, the PuC output being the stringing together of these UC timeslices.

But as already noted, some instance (candelabrum cells ?) is to remove the TDFS in the signal, and the APFV-VP needs attention if the GoCs have it not solved already in the GrL.

...

Let's now consider the possible function of 'pure-blooded' BaCs (with AF-type input) in the context of PuCs in a GS-patch and in a DS-patch (see the section on 'Patch and PF types' and let's ignore 'hybrid' patches).

In a GS-patch, AF activity is very sparse (GrCs AND-gating combinatorial input) and PuCs remain idle (together with the local BaCs) unless a DS is 'sent in' from elsewhere over DS conveying PFs.

If a DS-patch or a GS-patch is 'awakened' by the arrival of a DS, activity in AFs (or in DS-PFs acting like AFs) gets dense and is picked up by the BaCs.

In principle they 'average' this input like StCs did with PF input, but when a DS is coming in over all lines, then it boils down to having the DS reinjected but inverted at the soma and the primary branches of the PuC (again : with appropriate general gain tuning).

With this subtraction done (UC + iDS), the PuC outputs iCC, and delivers it inverted as CC to the CN (see Fig. 10).

Fig. 10

So, if BaCs are active, the CN receive the CC, and when not, just the iUC, begging the question if BaCs might have a 'controller' to switch them on or off, since both signals can be meaningful for downstream processing or feedback.

Surely, the already discussed observation from Valera et al. that MLIs of a microzone can be specifically 'turned on' by GrCs at a distance should incite creative thinking about their role. Candelabrum cells might turn them off (an alternative possible role for these cells).

[81] (Gao et al. 2012)

"Both types of molecular layer interneurons, that is, stellate cells and basket cells, are innervated by parallel fibres. Considering that there are functional differences in activity among different Purkinje cell (micro) zones, it is possible that the ultrastructure of the parallel fibre-molecular layer interneuron synapse is not homogeneous throughout the molecular layer."

...

BaCs are perceived as 'gatekeepers', swiftly reacting to input by shutting off the PuC output completely, although 'one synapse too late' to prevent AFs from delivering their message.

Maybe they can play also a more sophisticated role as transmitters of a modulated DS signal, picked up at the AFs, delivered inverted at the output stage of the PuC (in which case their inhibition does not shut off the PuC completely, but changes its output into another but still highly significant signal).

...

Why not have a clear distinction between StCs and BaCs? As already noted in Part 1 (section on the TDFS) a comparable situation is to be encountered in gymnotiform fish where pyramidal cells represent a cell population that ranges from 'plastic' to 'non-plastic' while only the extremes of the spectrum seem to make 'functional sense', raising the question how the system copes with the 'intermediate' cell types (it was also noted that the distinct properties of these 'end of the spectrum cells' are reminding of the proposed property differences between MGCs and EffCs in the mormyrids).

[82] (Bastian et al. 2004)

"Pyramidal cells show marked variation in their morphology, including dendritic structure, which is correlated with physiological diversity."

"A subset of cells, those with the largest apical dendrites, are plastic, but those with the smallest dendrites are not."

Maybe, the 'bias' in the MLI interconnectivity found by [83] (Rieubland et al. 2014) turns the 'gradual change' from StCs to BaCs into a more pronounced one by having BaCs not sharing their influence with the higher positioned StCs in the MoL.

[83] (Rieubland et al. 2014)

"By recording from multiple molecular layer interneurons in the cerebellar cortex, we reveal specific, nonrandom connectivity patterns in both GABAergic chemical and electrical interneuron networks. Both networks contain clustered motifs and show specific overlap between them. Chemical connections exhibit a preference for transitive patterns, such as feedforward triplet motifs. This structured connectivity is supported by a characteristic spatial organization: transitivity of chemical connectivity is directed vertically in the sagittal plane, and electrical synapses appear strictly confined to the sagittal plane. The specific, highly structured connectivity rules suggest that these motifs are essential for the function of the cerebellar network."

"Although transitive connections are a signature of the chemical network, it appears that the feedforward pattern, in particular, is a preferred motif of this network. It is characterized by an origin neuron sending two diverging connections, an intermediate neuron, and a target neuron receiving two converging connections. The transitivity of the feedforward motifs appeared to follow a top-to-bottom orientation in the ML, with the origin neuron being closer to the pia."

...

It is intriguing that we see BaCs becoming prominent in species that develop the ability for highly coordinated movements.

[74] (Bower 2010)

"Finally, there is another likely important consideration with respect to a direct role of especially basket-type molecular layer inhibition in neural coding mechanisms, and that is that this type of synaptic connection is only found in mammals and birds (Llinas and Hillman, 1969; Larsell, 1972; Larsell and Jansen, 1972) . Anatomical studies have shown that the cerebellar cortex of most fish (Waks and Westerman, 1970), amphibians (Midtgaard, 1992) and some reptiles (Llinas et al., 1969) lack basket-type connections altogether. In those fish, amphibians, and reptiles whose Purkinje cell soma's do receive inhibitory projections from molecular layer interneurons they are of the more traditional "en passant" rather than the specialized basket-type (Llinas et al., 1969; Waks and Westerman, 1970; Midtgaard, 1992) ."

[84] (Touretzky 2015)

"Although all vertebrates possess a cerebellum, baskettype inhibitory connections are found only in birds and mammals, which have the highest granule cell to Purkinje cell ratios."

...

CONCLUSION

MLIs, displaying gap junctions and reciprocal inhibition and affecting dendritic areas of PuCs, cannot have a spine-specific signalling function but are more apt to execute an averaging operation on their inputs.

While MLIs seem to be a population that gradually changes from stellate-like to basket-like with their depth in the MoL, there seem to be top-down connectivity patterns between them that promote a more pronounced functional segregation.

StCs (on the condition of having parallel plasticity rules with A-path-PFs and with calibrated gain) might be used to counterbalance the net current injected by PF-PuC synapses over a whole area, with the result that - at dendritic spine resolution - the signal becomes an oscillation around zero, and BaCs might do the same for AF (or DS-PF) input, but applying the counterbalancing at the PuC output stage.

With PF-PuC synapses (in decorrelation and when stabilized) injecting in sequence a timesliced iCC signal in disparate dendritic locations, this signal is to be added to the globally AF-conveyed DS to become a timesliced UC signal, which in turn needs amplification by De Schutter's boosting mechanism to be capable of affecting the PuC output which represents the stringing together of all these timesliced outputs.

For BaCs however, 'averaging' a global DS boils down to injecting an inverted DS at the output stage, reconvertng the UC signal back to an iCC signal, i.e. if BaCs are allowed to do it or not (steered by switching mechanisms ?), and it provides the decorrelating PuC with two useful output options : the iCC or the UC, which the PuC delivers inverted as CC or iUC to the CN.

In this way, species with the ability for highly coordinated movements (having BaCs) might benefit from having the PuCs able to output an iCC as well, and we will see what this can mean in the next section.

...

J) THE BASIC ALGORITHM

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path : a chain of sequentially activated synapses	GrC	Granule cell
AF	Ascending fiber	GrL	Granular layer
BaC	Basket cell	ISU	Input space unit
BSP	Body state parameter	MDS	Motor difference signal
CC	The correlated component	iMDS	The inverted MDS
iCC	The inverted CC	MF	Mossy fiber
CF	Climbing fiber	MLI	Molecular layer interneuron
CN	(Deep) Cerebellar nuclei	PF	Parallel fiber
DS	The signal to be decorrelated - later also : the driving signal	PriC	Principal cell
iDS	The inverted DS	PuC	Purkinje cell
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	UC	The uncorrelated component
EOD	Electric organ discharge	UMC	The upcoming motor command
ESD	Electrosensory disturbance	aUMC	The actual UMC
GS	The signal(s) that guide the activation process	iaUMC	The inverted actual UMC
		imUMC	The inverted mean or averaged UMC
		mUMC	The mean or averaged UMC

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

The similarity in design (PFs traversing PriCs, AND-gating GrCs ...) between the cerebellum and specialised structures like the ELL strongly suggests that it might also be capable of annulling annoying self-induced signals, and that on a much wider scale.

Indeed, the amount of potential DSs in the cerebellum is huge, since every movement is bound to produce self-induced sensory signals, consciously felt or not.

With a likewise huge amount of GS carrying MFs providing 'state parameters', a large set of ISUs is implemented in the GrL, enabling 'states' to be unambiguously represented in local code (GrCs being 'nodes' in the ISUs), and the so-called A-paths are 'trajectories' of dynamically evolving states in the confinement of an ISU.

Used for decorrelation or not, this large infrastructure representing states is there, and we might wonder if it can serve other purposes.

...

Correlation in time - as scientists are well aware - is no proof of causal link.

In the mormyrids, the EOD or the breathing or the tail wagging ARE the cause of the ESD or of variations therein.

But correlations can also be 'construed', e.g. by wilfully repeating the same series of movements M1, M2, M3 These movements then become correlated in time (M2 always following M1 ...).

The sequence of M1, M2, M3 ... represents a DS, and I propose the hypothesis that the cerebellum is going to decorrelate the DS with itself, but with a shift in time i.e. each timeslice DS(ts) is to be decorrelated against DS(ts-x). The PuCs are unable to do that in a direct way.

The movements M1, M2, M3 ... however, when executed, cause a series of (e.g. proprioceptive) consecutive 'states' which, when strung together, form a 'trajectory' in an ISU.

Hence, the movements M1, M2, M3 ... determine the actual A-path taken (in this ISU, but in others as well) by stringing together the segments A1, A2, A3 ... of it.

Since this involves a small delay, there is opportunity to detect correlation between A1 and the already upcoming M2 command.

M2 will then cause A2 to be 'unrolling' at the time M3 comes up, and so on : it can be seen as a smoothly evolving process, not as one chopped in discrete steps.

...

Suppose then that we construe a DS consisting of a sequence of upcoming motor commands [UMCs] (although I almost always refer to 'motor commands', the 'meaning' of UMC should be generalized to everything where sequencing may play a role like intentions, thoughts ...).

After due exercise (repeating the same sequence of UMCs at every iteration) the system will correlate each UMC component with the states of the moment BEFORE and store a negative image of it in the PuC databases (in the set of PuC-synapses allocated to the involved section of the A-path).

Rephrased : the negative image of the actual UMC [aUMC] will be stored in the synapses allotted to the A-path section bound to the state caused by the preceding UMC : important ! When this 'decorrelation' is completed, the negative image annulling the input, the PuC will produce a flat output signal

Indeed, with no UC (DS always the same), $DS = CC$, the negative image will be $iCC = iDS$ and when algebraically summed we have $DS + iDS = \text{flat}$ (zero modulation).

...

We are however no robots exactly repeating the same sequence of UMCs at each iteration.

Instead we are trying out which movement is 'the right one', and hence the sequence components UMC1, UMC2, UMC3, ... UMCx are NOT identical to themselves at each iteration (as DSs due to a changing UC at each iteration were not identical in the ELL).

So, after iterations a to x, each component, say UMC1, will have been represented by a set of variants UMC1a, UMC1b, UMC1c, ... UMC1x.

With all variants in such a set sharing a same goal they will cluster around some 'average' or 'mean' movement [mUMC], respectively mUMC1, mUMC2, mUMC3 ... mUMCx - these 'means' being the analogues of the CCs in the ELL.

...

Exactly as in decorrelation, the negative images that the PuCs are going to build and store in their synapses are those mUMCs inverted as imUMCs (the iCCs).

By doing so the PuCs as a population gather an immense database of imUMC components.

Considering the set of UMC1 variants, each element is wholly correlated to a state A1a, A1b, A1c ... since here we have a causal relationship (UMC1a causing A1a etc.).

Because of the delay, the PuC does not 'examine' correlation between UMC1x and A1x but between UMC2y (a variant of the next UMC) and A1x. If the actual UMC2y differs from what is expected (the mUMC2) then – when the negative image has formed - an UC reappears : PuC output will reflect the deviation of the aUMC from the mUMC. I will call it the 'movement (motor) difference signal' [MDS].

Having the synapses of the preceding state activated is important because it allows the variants of the UMC to affect the same synapses and hence it is possible to execute an averaging operation on them. Without the delay, each UMC variant would activate a 'private' synapse set for itself, and that precludes an averaging operation on the whole set of variants.

...

However ... it was noted that BaCs are in a position to control PuC output.

A DS receiving PuC has the same signal on all AFs contacting it, and (as we saw) the BaCs can pick up the aUMC at the AFs and reinject it inverted at the PuC base, which - after algebraic summation of UC + iaUMC gives imUMC, delivered as mUMC to the CN : the CN then receives the (stored) 'mean' motor command whatever variant of this command was given as input to the PuCs. In other words : the decorrelation procedure results in an elimination of the variability in the aUMC input.

In fact, in the proposed scheme the motor program is not calculated, but kind of 'recorded', and the 'mean' of what is recorded is stored (inverted), using a rather simple algorithm (a decorrelation procedure based on averaging !) to do it.

Maybe we should not speak of a sensory-motor TRANSFORM here anymore.

...

The BaCs allow the PuCs to 'play this recording', expanding the range of possible movements from a collection of reflex movements to a vast repertoire of learned movements (and – as already noted - we should interpret 'movement' in the broadest sense : it might be an evolving movement plan, or a thought process).

With CC output being the averaged movement and UC output the difference from this average, both signals might be of interest depending on the receiver - and with 'BaC-type MLIs' strategically positioned I wonder (again) if these can be switched on and off independently of the local PuC input. Note that when a movement became well-trained (aUMCs approaching the mUMCs (*)), a PuC that would output the MDS (the renamed UC) will appear to be almost silent (i.e. displaying almost undisturbed intrinsic firing). (*) The 'refining' of aUMCs is a cerebral job – see next section).

'Pre-BaC' animals would have to do with these 'movement (motor) difference signals' [MDSs] to correct a movement command on the spot, or to instruct higher centers to adapt a movement command, but BaC-equipped animals can also generate an automated 'mean-movement' string of commands. Rephrased : 'pre-BaC' animals always need to produce a 'voluntary' stream of UMCs, while BaC-equipped animals don't and can use the cerebellum as an 'autopilot' (see below).

It suggests that there might be an active switch between a 'voluntary' and an 'automatic' route :

[85] (Kennedy 1990)

"The corticospinal tract is most involved when a new movement is being learnt, while the rubrospinal tract is preferentially active when automated movements are being executed. However, what structure decides which system should be in use ? In this article Philip Kennedy discusses the evidence that the rubro-olivary tract switches between the two systems depending on the context of the movement."

"The CST is predominantly active when new movements are being learned, an idea first proposed by Paillard. The RST, on the other hand, is active when learnt, automated movements are executed, an idea recently discussed by Massion."

"As the movements are learnt, their execution becomes automated under RST control. The activity of CST would remain as a monitoring system ready to respond to changes in movement context. This switching function of the rubro-olivary projection is seen as acting in both directions, that is, it can switch the CST to the RST or the RST to the CST."

...

I read the well-known Albus paper of 1971 after I wrote this section (I had a policy of not reading papers earlier than 1990), and he completely surprised me by formulating what I take to be in essence the same idea (cfr the link with the 'state' of the moment before and cfr the alternative A-paths) although his implementing method (by the 'teaching CFs') is utterly different.

[86] (Albus 1971)

"Assume, for example, that the red nucleus sends a command C1 through the inferior olive and thence via climbing fibers through Purkinje cells and nuclear cells to the muscles. At this time the muscles and joints in their resting state are sending pattern M1, to the cerebellum via mossy fibers. Thus C1, is imprinted on M1. Now when C1, reaches the muscles, they respond by moving to a new position. This generates a new mossy fiber pattern M2. By this time a second command C2 is sent from the red nucleus. Command C2 will be imprinted on M2. In a similar manner C3 is imprinted on M3, C4 on M4, and so on. This process may be continued for a lengthy sequence of motor commands C1,C2,C3 ... and resulting body positions M1,M2,M3 Upon repetition of the sequence of motor commands C1,C2,C3 ... , the signals from the red nucleus will be reinforced at the nuclear cells by output from Purkinje cells responding to feedback mossy fiber patterns M1,M2,M3, Upon each repetition more and more of the muscle control can be assumed by the output of the Purkinje cells, and less attention is required by higher motor centers. Once learning is complete, the sequence of motor commands C1,C2,C3,C4 can be elicited entirely from the Purkinje cells via the mossy fiber input patterns M1,M2,M3,M4 . Little input is required from higher centers except perhaps to initiate or terminate the sequence."

"Assume that a sequence of motor commands from higher centers C1,C2,C3, ... had been imprinted on a series of mossy fiber patterns M1,M2,M3, ... as before. If the muscles upon receipt of conscious command C1 were to encounter greater than usual resistance this would delay or prevent the appearance of M2 at the cerebellum, and instead a pattern M'2 would appear, signaling the existence of extraordinary resistance to motion. The pattern M'2 would modify pattern C2, in a manner different from M2, perhaps calling for additional force or some other modification. What M'2 produces is governed by what previously had been imprinted on M'2 . If previously C'2, an additional force command, had been imprinted on M'2, the C'2 would be substituted for C2, automatically when the M'2 feedback signal was received instead of the usual M2 . By this means a sequence of conscious commands can be modified at the reflex level by cerebellar activity. This perhaps is the means by which motor activity such as running or skating can be under conscious control in a general sense but under reflex feedback control at the individual muscle level."

Note that Albus does not invoke a 'calculation' to correct a movement that is confronted with an unexpected load : he assumes that the movement has been previously and repeatedly executed with all different loads, such that the 'parameters' are already set and ready for use in all circumstances (as in a 'lookup table') : it is the equivalent of having a 'family of A-paths'. The actual 'body state parameters' [BSPs] (which change under a different load) will almost immediately lead to the appropriate A-path for the movement to be executed under a specific load.

...

Fig. 11

I will continue using the abbreviation 'DS' (we are now accustomed to it) even when decorrelation (as a method to filter out self-inflicted sensations) is no longer the goal : but 'DS' might as well stand for 'driving signal'.

Yet, for the transition to decorrelation in a motor context I introduce an abbreviation switch - as depicted in this overview diagram (Fig. 11 – compare upper with lower diagrams) - but basically there is no difference.

When the imUMC engrams have stabilized, the PuCs will output mUMC (BaCs active) whenever the correlated A-path unrolls, whatever UMC variant is presented as DS input.

Variability in the UMC is allowed but stochastically it should respect the 'mean', and if it does not the mUMC engram will gradually shift to a new mean.

Hence it is as if the cerebrum can send in UMCs somewhat carelessly since the obsessive cerebellum will anyway always correct them to become mUMCs.

It is so linked to the A-path that the whole sequence of movements can be 'played' as quickly as the A-path unrolls (which in turn unrolls as quickly as the movements are played) - automatically.

Remember that the use of state-correlated GSs – thanks to the causal relationship between DS and A-path - made it possible to maintain the synchronicity between the two, and that for an indefinite time (no more accumulating deviation with time as with a timelocked A-path - see Part 1). An 'intervening speed controller' will not change that.

[87] (Manto et al. 2011)

“An orderly succession of states may serve as “trigger points” during the production of a skilled movement, even though the overall rate of the movement may vary from one instantiation to the next.”

...

No doubt, the speedy performance of accurate movement sequences is made possible thanks to the cerebellum.

However, with performance speed increasing, is there not a point from which cognitive control (sending UMCs) cannot follow any more ? Is it not the intended goal of automation that you have no more to think about it, the next position / movement flowing from the former one, allowing attention to focus elsewhere ? Should the cerebrum even still bother about sending UMCs to the cerebellum ? The cerebrum might free itself of the task and limit itself to 'supervision' , and indeed, even with a 'flat' UMC the PuCs would merrily continue performing (as can be seen in Fig. 12).

Fig. 12

[88] (Kozioł et al. 2013)

"He (Marr) suggested that high-level commands from the cerebral cortex could access low-level cerebellar representations, "so that when [movements] have been learned a simple or incomplete message from the cerebrum will suffice to provoke their execution". In essence, the cerebellar cortex could be trained to run routine operations that result in skilfully executed movements, and these could be triggered by relatively sparse high-level command from cerebral cortical areas."

"The process often involves a transition from "controlled" to "automatic" processing in which movements that initially require problem solving and attention become increasingly efficient, stereotyped, resistant to online feedback, and importantly, require much less attention (they become immune to the distracting effects of concurrently executed tasks) ."

Hence : without BaCs, PuCs can deliver an MDS which is useful to correct (by algebraic summation) the UMCs generated by higher centers. UMCs - maybe deliberately - are subject to some degree of variability (without which 'trial and error' might be impossible).

With the BaCs active, PuCs have the possibility to deliver the corrected UMC (the mUMC) directly by themselves, and the MDS 'on demand' if BaCs are 'switched off'.

When the UMC 'becomes flat' (the cerebrum leaving it to the cerebellum to act on its own as an 'autopilot'), the PuCs deliver the mUMC irrespective of BaC presence (since a flat signal keeps them silent) (see Fig. 12 again).

With cerebral attention (the UMC) waxing and waning though, BaCs can keep PuC output stable on delivering mUMC, while without them, output would 'wax and wane' between iMDS and mUMC in following the input (see Fig. 11 again). Reason again, I think, that animals without BaCs better keep the UMC stream alive, even if Fig. 11 (left side) seems to suggest that they can move on autopilot when they stop this streaming input (flat AF signal).

...

However, if a 'flat' UMC becomes engaged in the averaging process, it will cause the mUMCs to start 'melting' away, ultimately erasing them.

Can plasticity be interrupted at these idle moments ? Playing a piece of music like an automaton with your mind/attention elsewhere seems not to improve performance quality, but does it degrade it ? And from which level of 'carelessness of cognitive control' should plasticity change be prevented ? If averaging - for which 'teaching' is not necessary - is the basic operation of the cerebellum, the primary role for CFs might be just that : enabling or disabling plasticity.

Of course it begs the question which is the controlling instance, mechanism or parameter by which the appropriate CFs can be silenced at the appropriate moments, but it feels to me that 'nature' would not ignore the possibility to exert such control :

An indication that this might be the case can be found in [89] (Lawrenson et al. 2016) on condition to reinterpret the results (and the role of CFs) as follows : 'standard' CF firing is silenced during the execution of automated movement to prevent plasticity changes when 'flat' UMCs are delivered.

[89] (Lawrenson et al. 2016)

"A major route for peripheral information to gain access to the cerebellum is via ascending climbing fiber pathways. During active movements, gating of transmission in these pathways controls when climbing fiber signals can modify cerebellar activity. We investigated this phenomenon in rats during their exploratory behavior of rearing. During rearing up and down, transmission was reduced at a time when self-generated, behaviorally irrelevant (predictable) signals occur. However, during the upright phase of rearing, transmission was increased when behaviorally relevant (unpredictable) signals may occur. When the peripheral stimulation was delivered only during the upright phase, so its occurrence became predictable over time, transmission was reduced. Therefore, the results indicate that the gating is related to the level of predictability of a sensory signal."

I believe that CFs play a different role in conditioned reflexes or when a withdrawal reflex has to be inhibited when an unexpected stimulus becomes predictable, but the essential point is that Lawrenson evokes the possibility of an active CF gating mechanism (and it is active even when no unexpected stimulations occur).

...

The other alternative is for the stream of UMCs to stay 'alive', meaning that the cerebrum is to stay actively involved even with performance speed going up : to follow the pace, automation must be brought into the cerebrum itself.

It could be one reason for the massive feedback of the cerebellum onto the cerebrum and I also believe that this same feedback is a necessity for the improvement of movement accurateness. So, without 'focus', no improvement.

Indeed, with CFs 'robbed' from their 'teaching role' (at least in the context of the above described decorrelation-dependent automation of movements) and given a plasticity gating role instead, there remains a need for a 'trial and error' system and an instance that 'consciously' evaluates the efficacy of the trial in obtaining a desired result. Therefore, I add a section on the 'cerebello-cerebral conversation'.

...

CONCLUSION

Having a comparable basic infrastructure, the cerebellum could be considered to be 'an ELL for all purposes' i.e. for annulling all kinds of self-inflicted sensory signals.

The cerebellum however found a way to apply the decorrelation procedure upon movements in tight succession, on the conditions that the movement sequences M1, M2, M3 ... M(x) are consistently repeated (wilfully exercised ...), and that there is a delay in the processing such that the sensory consequences of an actual executed movement command can be (de)correlated against an upcoming movement command (UMC).

The variability in an UMC is like the everchanging UC in a DS in the ELL, and like a CC being the averaged DS, the 'mean' UMC is the averaged UMC of all the variant UMCs as they were executed in trial and error to reach a certain goal. The negative ('inverted') image of this mean UMC (the imUMC), thanks to the delay, is stored in the PF-PuC synapses which were activated by the foregoing and already executed UMC, and not in the synapses activated by the UMC variant itself since these would be different ones for each variant.

Rephrased : the averaged negative image of the set of UMC(x+1) variants is stored in the PF-PuC synapses activated by the sensory consequences of UMC(x), the imUMC of the set of UMC(x+2) variants is stored in the PF-PuC synapses activated by the sensory consequences of UMC(x+1), 'x' being a time parameter.

The PuC can output the imUMC itself or a difference signal (MDS) depending on the BaCs adding an inverted actual DS (iaUMC) to the output or not.

After enough sequence exercise, the PuC is able to replace any input automatically by the imUMC (delivered as mUMC), 'without thinking', and by doing so can 'replay' a whole sequence, once triggered, with a speed not hampered by detailed voluntary control by the cerebrum. Without BaCs the UMC stream via AFs must be maintained, with them mUMC output is stable whatever the AF input which – in the extreme – means that AF input may go 'flat' (however, as artists with stage fright will confirm, the reintroduction of too much voluntary control due to performance under stress can be interruptive for the automated process).

The variability in the input, however, should remain clustered around the mUMC, since otherwise the mUMC shifts to a new mean or would even be 'erased' if the AF input remains flat during subsequent sequence reiterations. It raises the question if plasticity can be temporarily 'frozen' to prevent such a shifting when UMCs 'go flat' i.e. when the cerebellum is put in 'autopilot modus'. Might CFs be used for 'plasticity gating' ?

But maybe the cerebrum can be 'taught' by the cerebellum to act more rapidly (automatically) too and to maintain in due pace the stream of UMCs. In any case, the 'class of wilfully sequenced UMCs' is to be provided by the cerebrum, and it is to use the method of 'trial and error' to evaluate if its trial UMCs do what it wants to achieve its goals. It will find in the cerebellum a very valuable partner.

...

K) THE CEREBELLO-CEREBRAL CONVERSATION

Abbreviations :

A-path	Activation path : a chain of sequentially activated synapses	ISU	Input space unit
AS	The activating signal : the output signal of a GrC that activates a PF-PuC synapse :	JLN	Juxtalobar nucleus
BSP	Body state parameter	MCCD	Motor command corollary discharge
CC	The correlated component	MDS	Motor difference signal
DLN	Deep Learning Network	MR	Modulatory range
DS	The signal to be decorrelated - later also : the driving signal	PEN	Preeminent nucleus
aDS	The actual DS	PF	Parallel fiber
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	PPV	Preferred parameter value
ESD	Electrosensory disturbance	PuC	Purkinje cell
GS	The signal(s) that guide the activation process	UC	The uncorrelated component
		UMC	The upcoming motor command
		aUMC	The actual UMC
		mUMC	The mean or averaged UMC

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

A very instructive online book on deep learning networks [DLNs], intelligently written by Michael Nielsen can be found on <http://neuralnetworksanddeeplearning.com/> (one can understand 'the gist of it' even when skipping the detailed math).

DLNs almost certainly are deployed in the cerebrum, but it remains a mystery how neurocircuitry implements them.

A hallmark of DLNs is their dense layered combinatorial coding : it gives them a huge memory potential and the hierarchical subclassing endows them with the important ability to 'generalize'.

On the other hand, as long as information is combinatorially coded, an averaging operation is unfeasible without engaging relatively complicated calculation algorithms (as a pc can do on bitwise coded numbers).

The key power of the cerebellum precisely lies in its ability to perform averaging straightaway on a large scale, as explained in earlier sections, and it was stressed that a main condition for that to be possible is that GS input should be 'unambiguous' on every line, meaning that - ideally - local coding is to be the rule.

...

The boost for the development of the cerebellum came by its 'discovery' of how to (de)correlate sequenced and not just synchronous events (as the ELL does) by taking advantage of the unavoidable delay between DS and A-path progressing.

With the growing capacity of the cerebrum to put actions deliberately in sequence, a cooperation emerged that gave rise to construed automatization, and the development of physical and mental skills (speech, dexterity, thought ...).

The cerebellum might – like the ELL - implement 'external signal' extraction (of the UC – the variability in the DS) by 'internal signal' annulling (the CC) in some regions, but it broadened its focus to include UMCs, 'internal signals' in which the UC variability actually represents a component which is to get rid of.

Just noise can be a source of variability (and getting rid of that is already a bonus).

[90] (Barash et al. 1999)

"Robinson (1995) suggested that one function of the cerebellum is to reduce the large variability typical of neuronal activity to the remarkably low variability of movement size."

But UMCs sent in by the cerebrum are also variable because they are the product of an ad hoc 'good guess', itself influenced by varying attentive focus and incentive i.e. 'trial and error' almost by definition is a source of variability.

[91] (Schubert et al. 2010)

"The brain must face the inevitable variability in premotor saccade commands from one movement to the next. This variability has many sources including internal noise and the vagaries in motor commands related to the degree of attention and the value attached to the intended visual target. Nevertheless, saccades remain remarkably accurate in the face of fluctuating premotor commands."

Apparently evolution 'discovered' that 'taking the mean' of scattered but goal-oriented trials results in an outcome which is 'closer on target', making it interesting to memorize this 'mean trial', to use it to replace or correct the variable UMC trial, and to build on it to augment precision.

Take playing darts : if you intended to target the bullseye, the 'mean' of your hits should be closer to the bullseye than most of your trial throws (but probably not as close as that one incredibly lucky shot when you hit the bullseye on the spot), and you probably also never made a throw that resulted in this 'mean' hit.

No doubt, initial improvement will be due to a 'cognitive' adaptation of your throws, after seeing where your dart hit, and so you will already 'narrow down the spread' of your throws somewhat. The precision refinement which the cerebellum is starting up by a systematic correction of your trials towards an estimated 'mean', however, is much slower.

Maybe, signals of 'reward' - all kinds of 'amine'-signal conveying fibers pervade the cerebellum - can 'give a push to the mean' by bringing it still closer on target when – post-hoc – a trial was evaluated as quite successful – giving that trial some more 'weight' in the plasticity process (or vice-versa).

The cerebrum itself having no easily adaptable and usable long term 'bookkeeping' of which trials were better, its next trials are bound to be poor approximations again. Taking the mean of a larger and larger set of trials may bring this mean gradually closer on target, but even for the cerebellum it will probably prove to be very time-consuming (the law of large numbers ...). If it were to give feedback to the cerebrum about MDS and/or mUMC it would certainly boost the process.

In the MDS scenario, it would be the cerebellum itself that produces a (graded) error signal.

[92] (Raymond et al. 2018)

"The output of Purkinje cells can also carry information about the learning that is required (Miles Lisberger 1981, Popa et al. 2016, Raymond Lisberger 1998) ."

The MR width of the MDS (the smaller the better) could be a parameter to inform the cerebrum of the quality of the UMC it just came to send to the cerebellum (in analogy the UC MR might be used for the regulation by the JLN or the PEN in the ELL - cfr Part 1).

The cerebellum receives about a hundredfold more input lines from the cerebrum than it returns to it, hence we can hardly speak of one-to-one feedback, but I consider the MDS to be a signal that can be relatively broadcasted provided the DLN is able to 'bind' it to its output from just before.

[93] (Moberget et al. 2016)

"In summary, cerebellar microanatomy is characterized by an initial massive divergence of input (~40 million mossy fibers mapping onto ~70-100 billion granule cells), followed by an even more massive convergence (first onto ~28 million Purkinje cells and then onto only ~600.000 cells in the deep nuclei) ."

The DLN responsible for UMC production is to 'adapt its weights' by organizing itself 'around' the UMC which the cerebellum indicates to be the 'actual best' (the mUMC), by creating variant UMCs which are more closely centered around this preferred mUMC (like a pattern recognizing DLN does, increasing its discriminative power for detail). Refining an UMC most probably also entails a refinement of GSs i.e. an increase in PPV 'resolution' as explained in the section on ISUs.

With the DLN organizing itself, guided by the cerebellar feedback to generate more precise UMCs (allowing it to narrow down the spread of its trials), the cerebellum can start the next round of still more refined averaging : it is a tandem job.

...

We should be aware that this learning process towards 'a better movement' does not necessarily lead to 'the best movement'.

One can learn 'bad habits', and when these become encrusted it is difficult to 'unlearn' them (tennis players better learn the 'right way' to serve a ball from early beginning, music performers better detect and correct mistakes in reading a score and decide about the best 'fingering' https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fingering_%28music%29 before 'automating' their play).

Hence, to develop excelling skills, professional supervision is often needed to show where the 'global best' is, if we are not to get stuck in a 'local best', thereby introducing the cultural factor in our development.

...

The 'alleged basic algorithm' as explained before may create the impression that the cerebellum is able to 'optimize a movement' as quickly as the ELL can form 'a negative image' to cancel an ESD, i.e. in a matter of minutes.

[94] (Kennedy et al. 2014)

"Over the course of about 1000 EOD commands (approximately 5 minutes at EOD command rates typical of paralyzed fish), the membrane potential fluctuation caused by the sensory input is cancelled by the corollary discharge inputs conveyed by granule cells, consistent with the time-course over which negative images are formed in vivo."

In reality it can take months to years ! (for a baby to walk, for an adult to master a skill). That 'reiteration' through a movement sequence cannot be done at the frequency with which the mormyrid 'reiterates' through EODs (1000 in 5 minutes !) is insufficient to explain this huge difference (of several orders of magnitude !).

I believe it is mainly due to the 'sequencing' of the UMCs : in the ELL there is no sequencing, the DS is the equivalent of just one UMC. In the cerebellum the end point of UMC1 is the starting point of UMC2 and so on (it is a 'discretized way' of presenting a phenomenon that is continuous in vivo). This 'view' may be valid for an UMC sequence which has 'consolidated' after long and repeated exercising, but in the 'trial and error phase' we are confronted with UMC variants.

Hence, assuming we start from a fixed point, when say 3 variant UMC1s are executed, we get 3 different end points, of which each can be the starting point of variants of UMC2 ... and so on : the sequence possibilities multiply - you get 'a family' of A-paths, which tend to diverge out from the starting point but can also interweave (remember : A-paths are strings of ISU 'nodes', nodes defined by GSs, GSs reflecting body states caused by UMCs).

Averaging can only be done when there is reiteration through (a same portion of) an A-path and that will gradually occur more frequently when the A-path family gets 'denser' by continuing exercise.

Adaptations (towards a mean) are also very 'local' : it affects only the reiterated A-path steps and then only concerns the 'mean' of the variability in these specific steps.

Any adaptation (the PuC starting to change an UMC) also entails an A-path change : look at it as a switch to another railway track. The remainder of the old track is left 'orphaned' (adaptations already formed there are left unused), the new track might lead into 'virgin territory' (hitherto unused synapses) where adaptations for all the following steps are to restart from zero – or it might connect into another A-path section that was already used. On the whole I consider that to be a very time-consuming process.

In the long run, after hundreds and thousands of iterations, it gives the 'visual effect' that a family of A-paths that diverged out from a starting point is gradually narrowing down its 'spread' (with the earlier A-steps 'consolidating' more rapidly than the later ones due to the cascading effect of the 'track changes' which affect steps more frequently the later they are). In the end it results in a narrow band of A-paths which all represent meritorious movement sequences (statistically, your hits gather more closely around the bullseye when playing darts, but it remains to be seen if you can win a serious contest).

If, at that moment, a dart professional comes telling you that you need to change your 'throwing style' to augment your precision, there is a problem : it will be very difficult (but not impossible) 'to cut loose' from the incrustated A-paths which will act as 'attractors' by constantly trying to replace the new 'professionally advised' aUMCs by the stored mUMCs. Musicians also know from experience that 'old mistakes' have a tendency for inadvertently popping up again.

In general it is also the reason why we better start developing excelling skills early in life : ISUs are still relatively 'clean slates' then and hence can be better organized for the pursued skill.

...

In Part 1 I said that an 'A-path' is a mental image, and I started by describing it as a 'one-dimensional chain' of sequentially activated single GrCs and PF-PuC synapses. It tends to create the view that an A-path is 'a sharp track in a large landscape', a landscape that might contain a lot of 'virgin territory' (devoid of A-paths). I already noted however that, in vivo, whole populations of GrCs and PF-PuC synapses are activated in parallel, and that an A-path then becomes a 'chain of synapse populations'. That seems to turn 'sharp' tracks into 'large avenues', but in the section on 'Input space issues' I suggested a view that goes beyond that : ISUs develop by segmentation.

An ISU gets its amount of GrCs allotted from the start, but the number of PPVs on the defining axes is to increase with time, due to self-organizing mapping processes in the (cerebral) source areas. It means that the GSs gradually adapt to growing resolution in the PPVs. It means that there is no 'virgin territory' : the totality of the GrC population in the ISU is engaged from the beginning : a budding A-path uses immense 'blocks' of 'parallel' GrCs (and hence parallel PF-PuC synapses) for each step, and A-paths themselves undergo 'segmentation' in parallel with growing PPV resolution, and hence gradually 'get sharper' by a process of division of resources. It is important to have a BIE to keep PuC output independent from changing population volumes of activated 'parallel' synapses ! Plasticity is also to follow segmentation as to adapt the averages to changing and more specific GS input.

As said before, all this requires that there must be an ongoing 'cerebello-cerebral conversation'.

Consider also that UMCs for a microzone are just meant for the modulation of a specific effector. Hence many UMC sequences are to occur in parallel. The coordination and the stringing together of the activation of different effectors is to be seen as the responsibility of other microzones that handle UMCs 'of a higher order', but the 'unrolling A-paths' based on BSPs always determine the timing. This hierarchical structure of routines and subroutines will tend to keep the local chains of UMCs short (more in parallel is less in serial). It implies however that there must be recurrent loops inside the cerebellum or between the cerebellum and the cerebrum to allow the output of a 'routine' to trigger one of its 'subroutines'. It certainly makes the interpretation of cerebellar activity in experiments not easier.

...

While the former examples of acquiring skills (tennis, darts, instrument playing) assume an already 'mature' cerebellum, we should ask ourselves how the 'skill to acquire skills' is to develop itself in a cerebellum which has the hardware ready to do it, but lacks content and awaits input.

The output of a system cannot be more precise than its most basic input, since the precision of each higher level of integration depends on it.

Hence, we may assume that - in a 'virgin' cerebellum - the only ready-for-use GSs are those which are directly derived from the primary senses : their peripheral and topologically organized sensor arrays (and the ditto fiber tracts transmitting their signals) are in place and functional : we could call these 'the primary GSs'.

GSs based on 'higher order' parameters have to bide their time since associative areas are first to 'organize' themselves before they achieve discriminative power : the ISUs defined by such GSs only acquire greater 'resolution' as the number of PPVs per axis increases.

We might also distinguish 'primary' DSs from 'higher order' ones, the 'primary' ones being the executive orders (like MCCDs of crude movements) an infant brain is already capable of producing.

...

To start development it is necessary to trigger interactions between 'primary' senses which - structurally - already have precision, and 'primary' motor actions which are crude and chaotic.

With 'primary' A-paths unrolling, correlation of movement with 'the sensory state of just before' becomes possible, and when e.g. the infant repetitively attempts to grasp something (undershooting and overshooting) the cerebellum gradually records an 'average' of these movements (of all the elementary components), the average expected to yield a better movement. At the same time correlations start to emerge from what he does and what he senses and sees.

At the start, repetitive motor sequences may occur due to the activity of innate pattern generators and reflexes, but sequencing will really start to boom when wilfully repeated actions are triggered, and therefore a 'will' with an attentive, inquisitive and exploring mindset is mandatory (as a normal child displays).

Yet, it is still astounding to observe the 'readiness' of complicated movement patterns (genetically prewired) in several species after birth, capable to get to their feet in a matter of minutes, a feat that seems to be suppressed in the human infant, as if it were a prerequisite to allow for the development of superior skills later on.

Probably, many of our movements are the result of modulation after modulation of 'primordial' prewired patterns, acting as 'crystal seeds'.

...

Motor refinement starts with the formation and assembling of a collection of 'kinemes' - like 'phonemes' ([Phoneme](#) : "In linguistics, smallest unit of speech distinguishing one word (or word element) from another" - [Encyclopaedia Britannica](#)) but generalised to all movements - which I imagine to be stored in dense code in the cortex cerebri.

I define a 'simple' kineme as a short sequence of force modulation concerning a single effector (an elementary muscle unit or a 'knob or button' of an intercalated pattern generator), and a 'complex' kineme as being the concerted combination of simple kinemes of several effectors (like for uttering a phoneme).

When we think of musicians performing concertos it is clear that complex kinemes can be chained almost indefinitely.

The 'procedural memory' of it is located in the cerebrum (anatomical changes plead for it) and we can view it as the 'consolidation site' (in dense code) of the motor sequences which were also 'recorded' in the cerebellum (in local code).

[95] ([Hutchinson et al. 2003](#))

"The study of musicians offers an unrivaled opportunity to investigate the neural correlates of skill acquisition and retainment and those of unique abilities such as absolute pitch or musical sight-reading. Structural brain differences between musicians and non-musicians have been reported to exist so far in the superior temporal lobe ([Schlaug et al., 1995a](#); [Zatorre et al., 1998](#)) corpus callosum ([Schlaug et al., 1995b](#)) and motor cortex ([Amunts et al., 1997](#))."

"Behavioral correlates are noted in these studies: increased left-ward asymmetry of the planum temporale is seen in musicians with absolute pitch; larger non-dominant motor cortex is seen in key-board players correlating with higher non-dominant index finger tapping rates and earlier commencement of training; larger anterior corpus callosum in musicians who commence musical training before the age of seven. Functional studies have also found differences between musicians and non-musicians that similarly correlate with a measure of musicianship."

Some professional musicians can play dozens of concertos, even by heart, demonstrating that the memory capacity in DLNs as well as in the cerebellum is baffling.

...

I'm not sure if the quality and speed of sequential performance disappears altogether when injuries incapacitate the cerebellum : I indeed find it remarkable that e.g. speech (a chaining of complex articulation kinemes) can survive a total cerebellar breakdown (some rare cases of mutism excepted).

Quality is probably degraded by the reintroduction of variability ('ataxic dysarthria') : even if a DLN was taught to 'narrow down' its UMCs to approximate the mUMC stored in the cerebellum, it still is an approximation and the automatic replacement by the precise mUMC has gone. BSP steered A-path timing is gone and it really gets worse when skills have to integrate unforeseen input (changed BSPs) - the correction by rapid A-path switching now being unavailable, coercing to fall back on post-hoc feedback which is too slow to keep up speed and to avoid miscalculated movements.

[93] (Moberget et al. 2016)

"A wide range of subtler linguistic deficits have been reported. The most prominent of these cerebellar language impairments is motoric in nature, ataxic dysarthria. This disorder is characterized by a marked disruption in the temporal patterns of speech, including slowed rate, decreased range of syllable durations, and increased variability of between-utterance syllable durations."

"Skillful movement relies on the successful resolution of a set of more specific problems, several of which are known to critically involve the cerebellum. First, skilled movement requires precise temporal coordination across different muscles, and a breakdown in this timing is a cardinal feature of the motor deficits seen in cerebellar ataxia. These patients are unable to precisely control the timing that is essential for producing rapid movements or coordinate dynamic interactions that arise in multi-joint movements."

"Supporting a role for the cerebellum in sensorimotor prediction, patients with cerebellar damage are significantly more impaired on motor tasks requiring predictive control of movement than on tasks relying on feedback control."

With the speed of speech (the sequencing of phonemes) somewhat slowed but still relatively maintained, it is another argument (besides anatomy) that suggests that the cerebrum itself is capable of 'learning/remembering' a sequence and to reproduce it as an automat, but it will display the deficits listed above. I looked for reports as to the effects on the ability of musicians to perform a well learned piece after cerebellar injury, but couldn't find any.

When cerebral memory locations and not muscles are sequentially 'activated' by the cerebellum it might explain the 'recall of what comes next' effect, and - less linearly with parallel processing - the 'intuitive recall' effect (Intuition : "the ability to understand something instinctively, without the need for conscious reasoning" (google 'intuition meaning') (the facilitated recall of all possible associated 'come nexts' without the help of guiding context, but based on earlier experience).

Automation deficits and reintroduced variability as 'applied' on all kinds of 'effectors' probably play a role in several of the symptoms listed by Schmahmann.

[96] (Koziol et al. 2013) (Schmahmann)

"Executive function deficits include problems with working memory, mental flexibility, and perseveration. Patients experience concrete thinking, poor problem-solving strategies, and impaired ability to multitask, with trouble planning, sequencing, and organizing their activities. Mental representation of visual spatial relationships is impaired, with visuospatial disintegration and simultanagnosia. Expressive language impairments include word finding difficulties and abnormal syntax with agrammatism, long latency and brief responses, reluctance to engage in conversation. Verbal fluency is decreased, affecting phonemic (letter) more than semantic (category) naming. Mutism occurs following acute injury such as surgery involving the vermis, mostly in children but also to varying degrees in adults. Poor control of volume, pitch, and tone can produce highpitched, hypophonic speech. Short-term memory impairments include difficulty learning and spontaneously recalling new information, reflecting deficient encoding strategies, and difficulty locating information in memory stores."

...

The cerebrum may have gone a long way in sequencing actions by itself, but the necessity of a constant stream of 'guiding' information and the 'wiring density problem' coming with it may have been more restricting for it - due to its size and multiple other functions - than for the much compact cerebellum.

Evolution at a certain moment may have 'decided' in favour of a partnership with the cerebellum - better conceived for broadly distributing BSPs and for storing an immense wealth of sequenced actions for all situations with its marvellous PF-PuC system - and gave the latter a guiding/teaching role in support of the cerebral DLNs.

This advantage may have boosted the phylogenetic cerebellar expansion and maybe there is even a causal link with the volume reduction of the cerebrum seen in modern man when compared to his ancestors.

[97] (Weaver 2005)

"In the australopithecines and early members of the genus Homo, the cerebral hemispheres were large in proportion to the cerebellum, compared with other hominoids. This trend continued in Middle and Late Pleistocene humans, including Neandertals and CroMagnon 1, who have the largest cerebral hemispheres relative to cerebellum volume of any primates, including earlier and Holocene humans. In recent humans, however, the pattern is reversed; the cerebellum is larger with respect to the rest of the brain (and, conversely, the cerebral hemispheres are smaller with respect to the cerebellum) than in Late Pleistocene humans. The cerebellum and cerebral hemispheres appear to have evolved reciprocally. Cerebellar development in Holocene humans may have provided greater computational efficiency for coping with an increasingly complex cultural and conceptual environment."

"Late Upper Paleolithic humans appear to have encountered increasing cognitive demands as social and cultural complexity increased. These new demands may have taxed the information processing capacities of Late Pleistocene Neandertals and early modern humans. Information processing in these humans may have been limited ultimately by the sheer size of their neocortical processing networks. The secondary expansion of the cerebellum observed in Holocene humans would have streamlined neocortical networking by providing the infrastructure for rule-based, procedural organization of sequential operations across many cognitive domains in response to cultural pressures."

"In terms of their NetBrain volume, recent humans appear to be able to do more with less, thanks to secondary cerebellar expansion that permitted efficient processing of cognitive operations without an increase in NetBrain volume."

[98] (Vandervert 2018)

"The last million years of natural selection toward the three- to fourfold increase in the size of the cerebellum, especially its cognitive areas, was the key to the rise of Homo sapiens."

The 'cause' would be that the cerebellum, implementing sensory-executive integration with such efficiency in a relatively small space, allows the cerebrum to 'let go' on this issue of space consuming wiring, and it is speculated by some that it also gave an accessory survival advantage by reducing the total brain volume (without loss of efficiency), since its spectacular expansion gave birth problems by cephalopelvic disproportion.

...

Is a cerebral DLN being taught by the cerebellum a far nephew of the written digit recognizing DLN (see Fig. 5) ? Maybe ... when a DLN has been taught to 'rise' the flag at output 'x' when a specific event is recognized to occur then it might be linked to the triggering of a specific action 'y', physical or mental.

The trap of the 'deus ex machina' explanation might lurk around the corner by assuming that the DLN has an array of action programs ready at its disposal.

The point is that this 'array' also has to be 'developed' out of the dense coded DLN by the combination of the 'trial and error' of the DLN and the 'teaching' of the cerebellum - a teacher which is in a reciprocal position of development.

While a flag up at output 'x' is the result of a convergent operation, action 'y' is a divergent operation since the chosen action (which was 'assembled' in the learning process) must now be hierarchically decomposed again into the effector components (the simple kinemes) which the 'final path' microzones of the cerebellum expect. The cerebellum itself might continue to play a reciprocal role in it by harbouring 'higher order' components that trigger 'lower order' ones.

...

CONCLUSION

Averaging is easy for the cerebellum, but for cerebral DLNs it is difficult due to their combinatorial coding strategy which is much more suited for generalizing.

While the averaging in the ELL subserves (de)correlation applications of synchronous events, it came to be applied in the cerebellum for sequenced events, thanks to a delay which is introduced when DSs and GSs have a causal relationship.

This delay allows the average of a set of variant but goal related UMCs to be recorded in the synapses activated by the specific UMC just before, while without delay the covarying GSs (and ASs) would have activated different synapses for every UMC variant, precluding the averaging operation.

While originally it may have served the purpose of eliminating 'noisy variability' in the UMCs, the cerebrum took advantage of it by sending 'trials' of UMCs to the cerebellum, 'knowing' (by evolutionary intelligence) that mUMCs will be 'better movements' (but not necessarily the 'best').

Feedback of the MDSs (or mUMCs itself) in turn allows the cerebral DLNs to refine their trials in a continuous 'conversation' with the cerebellum (a strategy applicable to all kinds of actions on all hierarchical levels) until UMC variability is minimized around a precise mUMC.

It boosted the emergence of all kinds of skills, and - maybe - it relieved the cerebrum to try to do it on its own, allowing it to cut on space consuming wiring, thereby reducing its birth threatening volume.

...

Skills develop in the long run by repeated trials starting with prewired reflexes (acting as 'crystal seeds') and basic sensory input available at birth (or even before it ?), resulting finally in the assembling of ever more complex kinemes.

These kinemes are stored in dense code in the DLNs, and in local code as imUMC sequences which are addressed by A-paths in a few trillions of PuC synapses in man.

Thanks to the same DS-GS causality, the cerebellum can 'play' a sequence of mUMCs in 'automatic mode' with the possibility 'to change route' immediately when BSPs are disturbed by unexpected factors.

Let me cite Albus again :

[99] (Albus 1971)

"Assume that a sequence of motor commands from higher centers C1,C2,C3, ... had been imprinted on a series of mossy fiber patterns M1,M2,M3, ... as before. If the muscles upon receipt of conscious command C1 were to encounter greater than usual resistance this would delay or prevent the appearance of M2 at the cerebellum, and instead a pattern M'2 would appear, signaling the existence of extraordinary resistance to motion. The pattern M'2 would modify pattern C2, in a manner different from M2, perhaps calling for additional force or some other modification. What M'2 produces is governed by what previously had been imprinted on M'2. If previously C'2, an additional force command, had been imprinted on M'2, the C'2 would be substituted for C2, automatically when the M'2 feedback signal was received instead of the usual M2. By this means a sequence of conscious commands can be modified at the reflex level by cerebellar activity. This perhaps is the means by which motor activity such as running or skating can be under conscious control in a general sense but under reflex feedback control at the individual muscle level."

(It promotes the view that the cerebellum is a giant lookup table, all 'real life' movements needed for a wide variety of circumstances collected, recorded and refined as explained, avoiding time-consuming 'calculation'. It explains the astounding correcting swiftness of the cerebellum, but also the long duration of the process to 'fill' and refine the lookup table).

When the cerebellum defaults, skills can more or less 'survive', although in execution slower, coarse and vulnerable to disruptive events, giving the typical symptoms as described in [96] (Koziol et al. 2013) : the 'Schmahmann syndrome' or the 'cerebellar cognitive affective syndrome (CCAS)'.

The DLN example for the recognition of written digits (see Fig. 5) may be prototypal for the converging process of decision taking based on situation analysis, but it lacks in rendering the diverging process of the decomposition of the decision in its executive elements.

It would lead me away from the 'cerebellar topic' to venture in this very interesting and still more complex research field.

...

DISCUSSION

Abbreviations :

AF	Ascending fiber	GS	The signal(s) that guide the activation process
AS	The activating signal : the output signal of a GrC that activates a PF-PuC synapse :	LTD/P	Long term depression/potentialiation
BaC	Basket cell	MB	Mushroom body
CC	The correlated component	MDS	Motor difference signal
CF	Climbing fiber	MGC	Medium ganglion cell
DLN	Deep Learning Network	MLI	Molecular layer interneuron
DS	The signal to be decorrelated - later also : the driving signal	PF	Parallel fiber
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	PuC	Purkinje cell
GoC	Golgi cell	UC	The uncorrelated component
GrC	Granule cell	UMC	The upcoming motor command
GrL	Granular layer	aUMC	The actual UMC
		iaUMC	
		mUMC	The mean or averaged UMC

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

I propose the hypothesis (which I will denote as 'H1') that the cerebellum implements a same decorrelation procedure as does the ELL, but applies it to wilfully sequenced commands. Hence, the 'basic algorithm' (determining the PF-PuC synapse strength) is in essence an averaging operation.

In the case of the ELL the averaging of a recurring DS (containing a variable UC) results in a CC which is to be subtracted from the DS to get the desired UC (the signal which approximates the actual information coming from the environment), while in the cerebellum the averaging of a recurring UMC (which displays a variability due to noise but also to trial and error attempts) results in an mUMC which is to be subtracted from the aUMC to get a 'motor difference signal' (MDS).

This MDS can be used for the immediate transformation of a variable aUMC into a stable mUMC ($aUMC - MDS = mUMC$), and BaCs have the possibility to reinject the iaUMC to transform the MDS into a directly executable mUMC.

...

I find it very difficult to compare H1 with the 'perceptron' hypothesis (which I will denote as 'H2') – to which many adhere.

In both H1 and H2, PuC 'synapse memory' needs to be addressed recurrently. In H1, GSs are called upon to implement a 'pointer system' to address specific memory locations by combinatory use of state-bound parameters (or internally generated time-bound parameters). In H2, the combinatory use of incoming signals is called 'expansion recoding' and it is assumed to result in 'spatially separated' patterns, i.e. patterns that each activate specific PuC synapses without overlap (common use) of these synapses (which some also denote as a 'decorrelation'). Where is the difference ?

Both hypotheses allow the sequenced activation of synapses. For H1 it was stressed that there are 'requirements' to respect (reproducibility, uniqueness, resolution), which led to considerations about AND-gating and signal digitalization, and that connectivity rules should be in vigour. Should H2 also not have to comply with these requirements ?

An important difference is that in H1, the GSs – although most often derived from 'meaningful sources' – are considered to be inherently meaningless - in contrast to the separate DS, while in H2 the 'pattern' is supposed to be meaningful (*) AND capable of a memory addressing function at the same time. In H1, the 'meaninglessness' of the GSs allows them to be digitized, while any change in the 'meaningful' DS is to be avoided. It seems to pose a problem in H2 if it does not distinguish between two kinds of signals which are to be treated differently.

(*) It remains to be seen if 'combinations' of different modalities are 'meaningful'. Compare with the mushroom body (see hereafter) where the combining of elementary odours is meaningful for the recognition of real world complex scents.

Having a DS and GSs as in H1 suggests the use of two separate entry routes : in the ELL it is anatomically obvious (the basilar versus the apical dendrites of the MGCs), in the cerebellum it might be the AFs versus the PFs. It would support the hypothesis formulated by Bowers and De Schutter that AF input is modulated by PF input [100] (Bower 2010) (and amplified by a booster mechanism [101] (De Schutter et al. 1994c)). H2 treats PFs and AFs as functionally equivalent entities [102] (Dean et al. 2010).

Another important difference concerns the role of the CFs. In H1, the output is the result of 'a cancellation of variability', an operation that can hardly be called a 'sensori-motor transform' and it is one that needs no 'teacher' : CFs seem to take the role of protecting the synapse memory from corruption by 'gating' plasticity when necessary, rather than of determining it by LTD or LTP. In contrast, in H2, it is believed that a sensory-motor transform is implemented by the use of 'LTD masks' that change one pattern into another one, the masks being sculpted by the CFs under the control of 'teaching instances' which lie outside the cerebellum.

Complicating for H1 is that the different AF/PF functionality compels to postulate that there are functionally different GrC populations, PFs and PF-PuC synapses – OR – that PF-PuC synapses are so designed that the physical nature of the transmitted signal (DS or GS) itself determines how PF-PuC synapses behave (e.g. only inducing plasticity for the GS-derived ASs [103] (Bidoret 2009)) (*). H2 offers no explanation for how the appropriate 'LTD-masks' come about, and 'teaching CFs' seem to be a rare species : the sensori-motor transform remains a mystery.

(*) This will not necessarily corrupt the transmission of the DS if it were conveyed by PFs : GS-derived ASs are sparse, DS-derived ASs are dense, and hence the DS will 'pass' through a majority of 'AF-type' synapses that were not affected by plasticity.

...

It is my impression that H2 found a large part of its inspiration in the capacities of DLNs.

The striking similarity in wiring between the mushroom-body [MB] of the *Drosophila* fruit fly and the cerebellum probably adds to it (see Fig. 13). In the MB, 'cerebellum-like' wiring indeed seems to implement a (relatively) simple DLN which is to recognize the odour 'patterns' that matter. The olfactory input consists of multiple 'elementary odours' as identified by specific antennal receptors.

Expansion recoding is applied to produce an array of different combinations of these 'elementary odours' (even including some other modalities that relate to the odoriferous object). All these 'components' have a direct meaningful relation to the complex scents in the real world which are a combination of them (not so in the cerebellum ...).

Several 'teaching' signals (conveyed by 'the dopaminergic fibers') are involved to indicate which of these random combinations are existentially meaningful for the fly so that it can link attraction or avoidance behaviour to the recognition of specific odour patterns.

The 'behaviour motor programs' however are stored elsewhere, and even if this DLN would be able to trigger a host of different behaviours, it is not the same as a process that results in a refinement of the motor programs themselves.

Fig. 13 from [104] (Feng Li et al. 2020)

[104] (Feng Li et al. 2020)
"The shared circuit architecture of the mushroom body and the cerebellum.

In both the insect MB and the vertebrate cerebellum sensory information is represented by sparse activity in parallel axonal fibers; Kenyon cells (KCs) in the MB and granule cells (GCs) in the cerebellum (reviewed in Modi et al., 2020) .

In general, each KC or GC has claw-like dendrites that integrate sensory input from a small number of neurons, called projection neurons in insects and mossy fibers in vertebrates.

In the MB, teaching signals are provided by dopaminergic neurons (DANs) and in the cerebellum by climbing fibers.

Learned output is conveyed to the rest of the brain from the MB lobes by MB output neurons (MBONs) or, from the cerebellar cortex, by Purkinje cells."

...

As already noted in the main text, I consider the cerebrum to be the 'DLN master', and the cerebellum should not try to be a 'copycat' : its power lies elsewhere, and it does not possess enough 'layers' to implement it (even in the *Drosophila* the layering does not seem to end with the output neurons).

The attractiveness of a DLN also lies in that it does not require the demanding strict AND-gating, but the flip side of the medal is that synapse weight adaptations depend on a 'backpropagating error signal'. There seem to be no indications that such a system is at work in the GrL.

...

H1 posits that the cerebellum 'helps' the cerebrum in its trial and error attempts by a 'bookkeeping' of the trials for every situation in the form of their average (for each specific situation). Each trial is then immediately replaced by its 'average in store' (allowing reflex adaptations when situations are suddenly perturbed), but the MDS can be (or is) sent to the cerebrum to inform it of the quality of its trial. It is up to the cerebrum to 'do' something with this error signal i.e. it should adapt its wiring in the DLN to 'converge' the future trials to the indicated 'mean'. It was also noted that this 'mean' not necessarily results in a 'best' motor program, and that 'professional guidance' can be indispensable to avoid the incrusting of 'bad habits'. What is the position of H2 here ?

...

Is it possible to formulate a hypothesis without gathering arguments that 'fit' in it and intentionally ignoring those that do not fit in it ?

I do not automatically take citations 'in favour' to be 'proof' of my argumentation, but I nonetheless see them often as surprisingly 'corroborating' and they should at least induce some open-minded 'rethinking'. A fresh look might even reveal other research findings or interpretations to be in favour of H1 – be it only for its 'core idea'.

It is only natural that many will react by pointing to findings that do NOT fit in the 'scheme of H1'. One should not automatically take that to be 'disproof' either.

Consider that some research is outright conflicting (the findings can only be mutually exclusive).

Consider that research based on direct stimulation of MFs or PFs may be very difficult to 'interpret' if it would appear that MFs and PFs are not functionally 'homogeneous' populations.

Consider that research based on the triggering of 'non-standard' CF firing will lead in almost all cases to LTD.

Some 'conflicts' might be explainable. Take the discussion on the role of the PFs and the AFs : even [102] (Dean et al. 2010) and [105] (Gundappa-Sulur et al. 1999) might be reconciled if they accept the possibility that different types of PFs exist.

The cerebellum is evolutionary so old, that it had ample time to introduce 'trick' specialisations and specific wiring connections in every nook and corner, prohibiting the 'generalization' of result interpretations.

Consider the eye blink reflex which might rely on a 'cohabitating' intracellular timing mechanism [106] Johansson et al. (2014) and not on the 'basic algorithm'.

Consider the saccades (and maybe even the vestibulo-ocular reflex) which might find themselves corrected via MF route, and relying on kind of 'delayed plasticity' (but need the cerebellum to correct for 'orbital eye position').

Consider that sensory stimulations may take the role of motor commands in withdrawal reflexes or in exploratory behaviour.

Consider that – in overhead - the cerebrum may exercise direct control of the cerebellum itself by sending in commands to GoCs, MLIs, CFs

Especially the (intracellular) timing functionality of the cerebellum may be so important that it might constitute a 'second basic algorithm', and one that can be used in tight cooperation with 'the first one'. The different signalling (especially in CFs), may obfuscate the general picture even more.

This all is to say that a 'simple' basic algorithm does not necessarily 'simplify' the cerebellum as a whole.

I omitted intriguing topics such as the 'zebrin (+ and -) stripes', the bistability of PuCs, etc. since I fail to 'incorporate' these phenomena into a sensible 'scheme'.

...

I'm aware that many of the proposed ideas and 'constructions' are highly speculative and might be classified as 'se non è vero, è ben trovato'. It is up to the reader to judge. I hope that at least some suggestions may 'survive' and may prove to be interesting to direct further research.

...

ADDENDUM : 'RANDOM CONNECTIVITY EXAMINED'

Abbreviations used in this section :

A-path	Activation path : a chain of sequentially activated synapses	GrC	Granule cell
CC	The correlated component	GrL	Granular layer
CWA	Correlated wrong addressing	ISU	Input space unit
DS	The signal to be decorrelated - later also : the driving signal	MF	Mossy fiber
ELL	Electrosensory lateral line lobe	PF	Parallel fiber
EO	Electric organ	PPV	Preferred parameter value
EOCD	Electric organ corollary discharge	PuC	Purkinje cell
GS	The signal(s) that guide the activation process	RA	Right addressing
		RTL	The relevant timelapse
		UBC	Unipolar brush cell

Abbreviations used by authors in citations are to be understood in the context of their respective articles.

For the subject at hand it might be necessary to have a look again in 'Part 1' at the sections on :

- 'Decorrelation in silico' (to refresh acquaintance with the basic demo program) and
- 'Correlated Wrong Addressing' (to understand why CWAs are called 'correlated' and why there is an equivalence between WA and 'wrong timing').

In the CWA section it was demonstrated how corrupting CWAs are for the decorrelation process.

Recall that CWAs occur when GrCs fire more than once during the RTL (in doing so they corrupt the averaging process at the PF-PuC synapse they activate by compounding DS timeslice values meant to be averaged at other synapses).

Two possible reasons were given :

- The lack of GS 'uniqueness' : the same combination of inputs is presented to the GrC more than once during the RTL.
 - The failure of 'AND-gating' by the GrC : it is triggered into firing at several of the unique GS input combinations.
- A third reason was given in the section on 'AND-gating' :
- "Proper AND-gating per se is not enough : to be meaningful as a 'memory pointing device', the right signals must converge onto the GrC, and this poses a problem of 'connectivity'."

I will focus here on the connectivity problem, assuming that the requirements of GS uniqueness and proper AND-gating are fulfilled.

...

In the CWA-section demos it was assumed that WAs could be picked at random over the whole A-path (the sequence of activated synapses). Every synapse (every 'address') had the same chance to be chosen. In the context of the ELL with its EOCD and use of UBCs to 'generate an A-path' it seemed the logical thing to do. However, with the 'advent' of state-locked GSs conveyed as PPVs over arrays of MFs which project into the GrL in a 'mapped' fashion, another restriction emerges.

Fig. 14 from [107] (Gilmer et al. 2017)

Let's consider a 4D-case : with 4 axes a, b, c, d (w, x, y, z in this picture) with on each axis 4 PPVs, the MFs in the grid can be labelled as a1, a2, ... a4 till d1, d2, ... d4 .

A particular GrC - a 'node' in the grid - can be characterized by its input configuration e.g. a3 b1 c4 d4, and when it fires (only when all inputs are 'on' !) it activates a specific PF-PuC synapse.

Now take the case of a 'deviant' GrC with the following input configuration : a2 b2 c4 c1. It lacks a connection with the d axis, which is replaced by another input from the c axis.

Such a GrC - strictly AND-gating - will never fire since only one discrete PPV can be the 'actual' one (we cannot be in two different 'bodily states' - say a joint angle - at the same time). Hence c4 and c1 are never both 'on', and when AND-gating is not so strict the GrC might fire when c1 OR c4 is 'on'.

However, when PPVs are mapped (causing physical distancing of MFs 'carrying' different PPVs)(*), the occurrence of this input type is precluded and we only can have cases like a2 b2 c1 c1 where lacking inputs are replaced by purely redundant inputs (as if it were simply an a2 b2 c1 3-dendrite GrC).

(*) (i.e. if we consider PPVs to be 'discretized' - in vivo the PPVs change gradually with distance, but anyway relevant PPV difference goes together with relevant distance).

We can formulate it as a 'first connectivity rule' :

"MFs from same axis (modality) but carrying a different PPV may not converge onto a same GrC".
Mapping of the PPVs enforces this rule.

With this rule enforced, a redundant input to a GrC of a same modality implies a redundant input of a same PPV - no additional degree of freedom to choose here - and so we only have to consider what happens when dimensions are left out in the input configuration of a particular GrC.

Otherwise said : once a specific GrC 'chose' a set of dimensions (out of the coordinate axes a,b,c,d) to be connected with, the PPVs (1,2,3,4) are determined too and hence 'we can leave the digits out' and need only to look into the 'combinatorics' for abcd (and the consequences of allowing 'repetitions' in the connections).

The 'second connectivity rule' evidently is :

"A particular GrC should receive input from every axis that defines the grid (the ISU)".
Allowing repetitions in the combinatory possibilities of connectivity is a violation of this rule.

Let's switch for a moment to the following 2D grid (since it can easily be displayed on 2D paper) :

Fig. 15

The a and b axes stand for two independent ‘modalities’, each axis showing (a lot more than 4) ordered (mapped) PPVs from which parallel lines emerge which cross orthogonally with those from the other axis and imagine these lines to be MFs which contact two-dendrite GrCs at the crossing nodes.

A series of GrCs firing in sequence make an A-path in this ISU.

Blue lines show the row and column of the GrC at the start of the A-path (encircled in yellow). (I will refer to a column as a row too since it is a row in the a-direction).

Such a grid layout is ‘a construction in our mind’, in vivo MFs are not laid out in such a schematic fashion.

Yet, if PPVs are mapped in the GrL, the physical distancing of PPVs is reflected in the grid by the fact that parallel lines never meet in a node.

Now imagine that the GrC at the the start of the A-path (at the crossing of the rows a6-b10) lacks a b-input and gets two (redundant) a6-inputs instead : it will then fire every time that the A-path intersects the a6 row i.e. once when it rightly should do (at b10 at time T0) but also (wrongly) at b18 (at a time T1) and at b4 (at a time T2), thereby compounding the DS-timeslice values at the times T1 and T2 into the averaging process meant to occur at every iteration for the timeslice value at T0 at the synapse under the control of this GrC.

The same reasoning goes for a redundant b10 input and is also valid for every GrC on the A-path. You can see that the route of the A-path itself is a factor of influence : ‘deterioration by compounding’ can be avoided/minimized by avoiding/minimizing the intersecting of already ‘used’ rows. In the 2D situation here the only ‘pure escape’ routes for the A-path would be to go straight out in a diagonal from the starting point : improbable in vivo.

You can also imagine that the situation gets more complicated when dimensions are added : in 3D each GrC is common to 3 rows and also to 3 planes, in 4D to 4 rows, 4 planes and 4 ‘volumes’ ... as the number of possible ‘lacking inputs’ grows with the number of dimensions.

With the help of some programming I tried to ‘visualize’ the effect of WAs on the decorrelation of an unchanging signal (S1 in the demos of Part 1), and that for more-dimensional situations.

Without going too much into detail :

Without WAs the correlated output (S4) of the decorrelation procedure should equal S1.

In 1D the A-path is a section of the ISU and a single loop is used ‘to sweep over the timeslices’. In multi-D this single loop sweep is replaced by a ‘multi-nested’ loop sweep. In this demo the A-path covers the whole ISU – node by node, row by row, plane by plane ... which is not the case in the 2D example shown above, but that doesn’t matter for the principle.

Next, each timeslice is supposed to be represented by a synapse that is affected, not by one GrC but by as many GrCs as the permutations of input possibilities permit (and for each such GrC an input combination is picked at random out of the pool of these possible permutations). Such convergence does not exist in vivo but I take it that the PuC itself would average the output of as many ‘parallel’ synapses.

In the upcoming example a 4D ISU with 4 PPVs on each axis is considered. $4^4=256$ input permutations are possible out of which each of 256 GrCs get a randomly chosen input combination, the combined output of these 256 GrCs affecting the averaging done at the one synapse that represents a timeslice (and not 256 synapses). Same for all 256 timeslices of the DS (which uses up the whole 4^4 ISU). Four decorrelation runs of 50 iterations each are executed, each one allowing for one repetition more in the combinatory input possibilities of the GrCs. See Fig. 16.

Fig. 16

Videolink : <https://www.dropbox.com/s/gepf59be8v33pgg/demo-4-1.mp4?dl=0>

The result is better than I expected : S4s (the CC) produced with WAs are ‘noisy’, erasing detail but preserving the gross modulation of S1 (as seen in the upper S4 where S4=S1). Note that most of the degradation is already visible with ‘one input may be lacking’. Permutations with more inputs lacking are increasingly rare and do not add much to the degrading any more.

A major reason for the relatively good result is that the averaging of a DS timeslice value is only slightly affected if it is compounded with a ‘nearby’ timeslice in which the DS value is almost the same : it is the case when a low frequency component in the DS is ‘chopped’ in timeslices. Which WAs (which GrC input combinations that contain repetitions) have ‘nearby’ or ‘faraway’ effects depends on the direction of the A-path in the ISU grid.

Counts of ‘right addressings’ [RAs] and ‘wrong addressings’ [WAs] in function of dimensionality, number of PPVs per axis and even number of ‘available’ dendrites can be made. You can find the source code for it at

<https://www.dropbox.com/s/hiqgx9cu2aj9bo4/Source%20code%20RA%20WA%20counts%20-%20Visual%20Foxpro.docx?dl=0> ...

It is clear that the RA % goes down when adding more dimensions and PPVs. The RA % goes up considerably however when a ‘surnumerary dendrite’ is added : a 5 dendrite GrC that is to randomly ‘collect’ input from a set of 4 dimensions has 25% more chances to collect a more complete set than a 4 dendrite GrC, raising RA and lowering WA occurrence. It might be a cardinal reason for the presence of surnumerary dendrites, but it is limited by the AND-gating power of the GrC and the ‘digitization’ quality of its input signals.

...

A multimodal ISU can be viewed as a ‘grid’, but so can the ‘pseudo-multimodal’ environment created by the intercalation of multi-type UBCs in the MF-circuitry, since a very simple stereotyped signal is spatiotemporally expanded in the GrL into diversified signals which are then in combinatorial fashion used by GrCs as coordinates to define points in memory space just as they would with multimodal inputs.

I wondered if cascaded UBCs might cause a mapping effect too. In the ELL of the mormyrid the decorrelation of the electrical disturbance caused by the electric organ itself relies on the timing diversity which is created by UBC cascades after they are triggered by the EOCD. There are no PPVs here that relate to a ‘bodily state’ (they enter the scene only when the effects of movements have to be dealt with).

Fig. 17 from [108] (Mugnaini et al. 2010)

It is never explicitly stated, but drawings like Fig. 17 suggest that cascaded UBCs 'line up' (taking each time a step in the GrL in one direction), and cause GrCs hooking in at the top of the cascade (firing earlier) to be distanced from those lower down the cascade (which fire later), creating sort of a time biased map.

It would lower the probability that a same GrC is connected to MFs 'of a different timing', which under strict AND-gating would mean that such a GrC would never fire – just as GrCs that receive different PPV inputs of a same modality would never fire (cfr earlier).

...

CONCLUSION

Random connectivity from MFs onto GrCs seems to contradict the essence of the idea that GrCs should function as 'pointers' to a specific address (the PF-PuC synapse).

Indeed, to be able to do that unambiguously, GrCs should be organized to lie in a (multi-D) grid structure which guarantees that each GrC receives a specific PPV input ('the first connectivity rule') from every dimension (coordinate axis) ('the second connectivity rule'), by way of the MFs.

Mapping - by physical distancing of MFs - enforces the first rule by preventing GrCs to make contact with MFs of same axis but clearly different PPV.

In such a setting, random connectivity still can lead to 'lacking inputs' (violation of the second rule) and with a number of conditions to fire removed, such GrCs will fire more often, i.e. not just at the appropriate time for a specific timeslice (hence compounding averages).

Probability determines the frequency of occurrence of 'types of malconnectivity' : while each input permutation (order mattering, repetitions allowed) has an equal chance to pop up, it is the combination (order not mattering) which will determine the final effect. The degrading effect is determined by 3 parameters :

- How often does a specific class of malconnection occur (when left to chance) ?
- How often does a specific class of malconnection trigger a GrC to fire during the RTL ?
- How close in time are these misfirings to the appropriate time of firing ?

The formulas for permutations allowing repetitions give the frequencies of occurrence. More lacking inputs lead to more misfirings (which then 'spread' more over the whole RTL), but there will always be a fraction of misfirings which occur close in time to the appropriate firing time – which fraction depends on direction and 'course' of the A-path in the ISU landscape. If DS change is slow compared to A-path step, 'close misfirings' do not much harm.

Surnumerary dendrites may have a reason of existence by 'reducing the number of lacking inputs'. UBC cascades may 'mimic' PPV mapping by creating a time-biased map in the GrL.

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Addendum: Random connectivity examined

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